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SUPER MoRRI – Scientific understanding and provision of an enhanced and robust monitoring system for RRI

D5.3 Pathway Studies Report

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 1: Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronyms/Abbreviations	Definition
CCN	Country Correspondent Network
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
GE	Gender Equality
OS	Open Science
PATSTAT	European Patent Office – Worldwide Patent Statistical Database
PE	Public Engagement
R&I	Research & Innovation
REI	Research Ethics and Integrity
RFO	Research Funding Organisations
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SwafS	Science with and for Society

Executive Summary

This report summaries selected results from empirical studies conducted to provide data and information for a monitoring framework to support open and responsible research and innovation. The final output of this process and the SUPER MoRRI project is an online portal named 'Platform for the Support of Responsibility and Openness and their Monitoring in Innovation and Science Ecosystems (PROMISE, www.promise4era.eu).

The aim of the Report is to elaborate on markers of responsible research and innovation – specifically *citizen science, gender quality, open science, public engagement, research ethics and integrity, sustainability* – regarding their pathways towards attaining benefits. The pathways are related to specific societal, economic, democratic, and scientific benefits.

The Report focuses on qualitative pathways relating to interventions into the research and innovation system. The interventions studied in this report relate to open and responsible research and innovation practices and tries to understand how these practices interact in defining or influencing research and innovation processes. Underlying this work is a model of institutional change that connects these various pathways and their benefits, whether they have been fully realised in the empirical work or theoretically sketched for future research and policy directions.

The cases were developed within the SUPER MoRRI consortium through a multistage collaborative process. The cases aimed at including all six RRI keys (*Ethics, Science Education, Gender Equality, Open Access, Governance and Public Engagement*) although did not limit themselves to the keys given the EC's policy evolution towards similar efforts such as Open and Responsible Research and Innovation. A series of open calls within the Consortium and feedback rounds resulted in cases in which consortium partners had interest and which could contribute to the PROMISE portal in the form of narrative content. These cases consist of *Coding of ethics and values into autonomous systems, Transdisciplinary Research (funding), and CSOs at Science-Society interface*. The other cases were designed to draw more substantially from the quantitative datasets generated by the SUPER MoRRI project and to further investigate the patterns identified (see D5.2). These cases were *Public value research careers, Gendered eco-innovation, and Alignment of preferences, practices, and repertoires in public engagement with science*.

Each case study is presented as individual narrative chapters in this document. These narratives can be used as stand-alone narratives about what occurs when responsible research and innovation interventions enter a research context. Individually, the cases represent a range of emphasis on empirical and or theoretical work. However, their shared focus is to apply a case specific Theory of Change (ToC) in order to clarify pathways of responsible practices and policies to benefits. The theoretical underpinning of this ToC model and how the SUPER MoRRI project approaches the topic of benefits is described in detail in Chapter 3.

As the cases demonstrate, pathways cannot be taken for granted and involve complex intricacies between actors, institutions, individual motivations, administrative hurdles and translations between policy, research, and practice communities. A summary of these pathways is presented by first outlining the ToC for each of the responsibility markers. These markers are then elaborated upon using the cases as material to understand how the pathway unfolds. As case studies, these pathways are context specific and therefore are not used to make general claims about pathways, but rather to provide a deeper level of analysis for how certain factors support or impede them. The findings presented in this report will inform further work in the Deliverable 5.4 Analytical Synthesis Report.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

This Pathway Studies Report (Deliverable D5.3), abbreviated as Pathways Report shall contribute to the development of a monitoring framework for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) by summarizing the empirical research efforts regarding pathways to RRI benefits. It presents the full narratives of the six empirical cases comprising the work on *Scientific, Social, Economic and Democratic Benefits* (WP5) and a first analysis of pathways. The main objectives of WP5 are:

- To specify and to systematize the scientific, democratic, societal and economic benefits of the six RRI keys;
- **To clarify pathways from RRI practices and policies to benefits, and their interrelation between different keys;**
- To investigate and identify patterns of RRI and its benefits using large scale data sets;
- To synthesize the results and identify sources of replicable data from which indicators to monitor the benefit of RRI could be developed.

This Pathways Report addresses the second objective of clarifying the pathways from responsible practices to different kinds of benefits and important factors which support or impede this process.

1.2. Background to Deliverable 5.3

This Pathways Report has a closely related companion report titled, the *Pattern Studies Reports* (Deliverable D5.2) which summarizes the quantitative work using large-scale datasets to connect markers of responsible research and innovation with impacts or benefits. In our understanding, markers link patterns and the pathways, they are basically indicators for RRI identified in the pattern studies and studied in the pathways study.

D5.2 and D5.3 share case studies which had both qualitative and quantitative dimensions and represent different approaches to contributing towards the monitoring framework. On one hand, the aim is to understand patterns as prerequisite conditions and behaviours within research and innovation processes that enable or lead to responsible practices and on the other hand, to understand the pathways from which different kinds of impacts and benefits emerge from responsible practices.

The two deliverables adopt a common and overlapping structure addressed to the following markers of open and responsible research and innovation that can contribute to these benefits: citizen science (CS), gender equality (GE), open science (OS), public engagement (PE), research ethics and integrity (RE&I), sustainability (SUS), and the third mission (TM). Over the lifespan of SUPER MoRRI, extensive and continuous interactions occurred between tasks based in WP2 and WP5. This allowed the development of complex case studies that could address both patterns and pathways toward benefits of open and responsible research and innovation.

Taken together, D5.2 and D5.3 are the outputs of the empirical work conceptualised in the Strategic Development Plan (D1.2) which outlined three research programme pillars for structuring the definition, selection, and operationalisation of the project's main research questions¹. As **Fehler!**

¹ SUPER MoRRI strategic documents are available at the project Open Science Framework home <https://osf.io/z95gw/>

Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. below shows, the case research plan was a pillar in the development of the data vehicles and thus structured the implementation of SuperMoRRI's empirical work.

Figure 1: SUPER MoRRI project structure

At the end of the project, a final WP5, D5.4 *Analytical Synthesis of Cases* will bring the findings of D5.2 and D5.3 together. WP5 concludes with a policy brief on the benefits of RRI.

1.3. Relation to Other Tasks and Deliverables

The Pathways Studies Report (D5.3) is the first deliverable produced by Task 5.3 of SUPER MoRRI. D5.3 is closely related to Tasks 5.2 and 5.4 leading to Deliverable 5.2 (Pattern Studies Report) and Deliverable 5.4 (Analytical synthesis report of experimental cases) respectively.

The Pattern Studies Report (D5.2) and the Pathways Studies Report (D5.3) provide the input for the Analytical Synthesis Report (D5.4). D5.2 and D5.3 also relate to the revised Strategic Development Plan (D1.3) in that the data and information highlighted in these two deliverables summarises the major content to be delivered publicly through the PROMISE portal (<http://www.promise4era.eu>).

D5.2 and D5.3 also relate to the Sustainability Plan (D7.5) which summarises options for the updating and development of the datasets provided by SUPER MoRRI and the monitoring elements hosted and made available at PROMISE.

Finally, data and visualisations developed from the pattern studies are summarised in three Monitoring Reports (D2.2, D2.3 and D2.5). These Monitoring Reports also include details of the patterns of open and responsible research and innovation, including national level indicators, constructed using secondary data sources, including Eurostat, Eurobarometer, She Figures, and Unpaywall.

1.4. Deliverable Structure

This report consists of eleven chapters and is structured as follows. Firstly, the Executive Summary briefly presents the purpose and contents of this report. Chapter 1 introduces the background and objectives of the deliverable, its relation to other tasks within the project, and its structure. Chapter 2 summarizes the design and development of the case research program including a methodological overview of the individual cases. Chapter 3 outlines the conceptual approach developed within WP5 to guide the individual cases in a systematic understanding of RRI impacts and benefits.

Chapters 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 present individual case studies in the following order: Engaging Civil Society in Research, Coding of Ethics into AI, Public Value Research Careers, Transdisciplinary Research (funding), Gendered Eco-Innovation, and Public Engagement Repertoires. Chapter 10 then presents the markers of responsibility in research and innovation derived from the Pattern Studies Report (D5.2) and elaborated on in terms of the pathways found within the case studies. Chapter 11 then briefly concludes with a summary of the pathways and benefits, as well as the next iteration of WP5 which is to be taken up in the Analytical Synthesis Report (D5.4).

2. Overview of WP5 Case

This section describes the case study program and provides an overview of cases.

2.1. Development and Implementation of WP5 Case Studies

The design and development of the empirical research programme of WP5 was defined in Task 5.1 and reported in detail in Deliverable 5.1. The main objective of Task 5.1 was the development of research projects that could provide new insights regarding how to monitor RRI and produce new data suitable for indicator development.²

The process involved many discussions amongst consortium members to determine a set of criteria to ensure studies were aligned with the overall needs of the project. The discussions revolved around the interest in addressing different RRI keys, pathways to different types of benefits (scientific, democratic, societal, and economic), levels of analysis (macro, meso, micro), actor groups and countries. Also emphasized was the importance of understanding how outputs, benefits, and impacts emerge to be able to grasp internal and external factors that foster and hinder RRI. Critical to understanding these factors was using the cases to investigate why different stakeholders engage in RRI (or not), elucidating their motivations and the circumstances under which they act. The consortium agreed that cases capturing these elements would help monitor institutional support in fostering/hindering RRI and the role of institutions in supporting individuals' RRI behaviour and practices.

Additionally, the topic of benefits was much discussed in the development of the research program. Although there was agreement about the importance in the benefits topic, there was also scepticism whether it would be feasible to address all benefits in each case study. There were reservations about the feasibility of constructing indicators of an RRI benefit per se, given the challenges of time lag and attribution in such highly complex systems as research and innovation. Thus, a Benefits Discussion Paper (Wicher et al. 2022) was produced to systematize this aspect of the empirical program. The following Chapter 3 goes into detail about the conceptual guidance of this paper. After consecutive discussions in 2019 in two Consortium meetings as well as a stakeholder workshop in Brussels, an Open Call within the Consortium for a first wave of research projects took place³.

2.2. Case Selection and Quality Criteria

The consortium aimed for a variety of cases that address a wide range of RRI aspects and focus on RRI pathways from diverse perspectives. The logic for an initial open call was linked to members' research competences, areas of expertise and interests, and the potential to maximize the use of resources. Additionally, discussions led to the consensus that the cases should not over focus on the Commission's RRI keys.

A template was sent around to SUPER MoRRI partners to collect ideas with a resulting ten potential cases. It was determined there should be two further consortium meetings in late 2019 to further develop individual projects and the empirical programme overall. These meetings were set up as workshops in a co-creational way to discuss in plenary (e.g., in creative dialogue session), as well as in

² More information on the SUPER MoRRI approach to responsible indicator development can be found in the Strategic Plan, D1.2.

³ Detailed information on the sequence of events can be found in D5.1 Section 2.1 'Development of the SUPER MoRRI Case Research Plan'.

group settings (e.g., reflecting teams), issues and decisions towards concerted steps in developing the strategic, implementation and case research plans.

Three further waves of feedback rounds and narrowing down cases took place from the end of 2019 to the beginning of 2020. The cases were finalized in May 2020. To facilitate comparison between potential project cases and reinforce quality criteria within WP5, an elaborate questionnaire (Annex I, pg. 113) was set up by WP5 lead. This included several questions referring to the definition of RRI, RRI practices and key(s) used in the specific case, connection to WP1 and WP2, securing to assessment pathways for RRI and defining methods and resources for implementing the single case studies. Responsible partners for cases were required to provide multiple iterations of the protocol. Fields were added over time to reflect emergent information needs. The protocol accompanied the extensive collaborative elaboration process required in WP5.

All cases needed to align with the goal of WP5 to assess pathways of RRI and further line up with the strategic plan. The studies have different starting points for their empirical work (e.g. either have a more inductive or deductive approach on the pathways to be assessed), but they needed to have a clear and reflexive understanding of their definition of RRI (which needs to be based on the theoretical assumptions made in D1.2), RRI practices and the way the studies intended to explore the pathways to benefits of RRI.

2.3. Overview of Case Projects and Methodologies

These selection of the six case projects has been described in D5.1 in terms different dimensions relating to the objectives of WP5 including:

- Focus on RRI keys,
- Focus on types of organisations/actors,
- Level of analysis,
- Geo-spatial scope,
- Focus on types of RRI benefits,
- Type of intervention studied,
- Research methods used.

All key dimensions of RRI are covered to a differing degree. The project selection covers diverse actor groups including Research Performing Organisations (RPO), Research Funding Organisations (RFO), industry, Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) and policy makers. The SESL (Science Education Science Literacy) key dimension is the one least addressed in this first wave of WP5 studies. Cases focus on the meso-level, but also cover the macro and micro level. Most studies will be implemented in countries that are connected to the consortium members (Austria, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, and Spain). Each of the cases include a context specific logic of transformation or implicit “theory of change” (ToC) (Vogel, 2012) that problematizes and brings into focus the opportunities and challenges associated with efforts to make research and innovation more open and responsible. The cases were also chosen to provide a set of examples that could inform possible future monitoring efforts.

The six qualitative case studies applied qualitative and quantitative analysis. The case projects and their methodological approaches are presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Methods and data used in the WP5 case study programme

Case Study	Methods used	Data sources
CSOs at Science-Society interface	Ethnographic observation, document analysis, interviews	Policy and other documents; SUPER MoRRI primary data (observation, interviews)
Coding of ethics and values into autonomous systems	1) mapping of actors and networks (RFOs, RPOs, Swafs), 2) data collection through Eurobarometer and secondary sources, 3) interviews with select researchers identified in (1)	Eurobarometer, policy, and other documents; SUPER MoRRI primary data (interviews)
Public value research careers	Qualitative content analysis, interviews, survey	Policy documents; SUPER MoRRI primary data (RESU dataset, interviews)
Transdisciplinary Research (funding)	Qualitative content analysis, interviews, focus group	Policy documents; SUPER MoRRI primary data (interviews, focus group)
Gendered eco-innovation	Patent data analysis; qualitative content analysis, interviews	PATSTAT / Greentech Database, policy documents; SUPER MoRRI primary data (interviews)
Alignment of preferences, practices, and repertoires in public engagement with science	Statistical analyses	Eurobarometer; SUPER MoRRI primary data (CCN-RPO and RESU datasets)

3. Connecting markers of openness and responsibility in R&I to scientific and societal benefits

As part of Tasks 5.3 and 5.4, a Discussion Paper on the topic of benefits, hereon Benefits Paper, was prepared on pathways to impact and benefits of open and responsible research and innovation (Wicher et al. 2022). It addresses how markers of open and responsible research and innovation can be linked to pathways to impacts in science and society. The Benefits Paper focuses on the development of “impact narratives” in which researchers, R&I stakeholders, and citizens reflect on what they understand by beneficial impacts of R&I. This section introduces the conceptual framework developed in the Benefits Paper and explains how this framework shapes the analysis contained in this Pathways Studies Report (D5.3). This analytical procedure is consistent also with that used in the Pattern Studies Report (D5.2) and the Case Synthesis Report (D5.4).

3.1. Constructing impact pathways

At the level of actors and agents involved in institutional change processes, benefits are an inherently normative construct. Impacts need to be perceived and understood as „beneficial’ by situated stakeholders and other actors. The perceptions and understandings of relevant actors need to be investigated and interpreted in relation to an „impact pathway’ model. That is, the perceptions and understandings of situated stakeholders should be interpretable in terms of a coherent logic, or model, regarding how openness and responsibility in research and innovation contributes to beneficial impacts. An impact pathway thus should be interpretable in terms of an explicit or implicit theory of change, a series of steps connecting a practice or set of practices and an expected outcome that can be connected empirically or theoretically to benefits for science and/or society.

The Benefits Paper develops a model that does not seek to pin down all the (often overdetermined) factors that may contribute to the series of steps that can be interpreted as constructing an impact pathway. The focus is on the activities undertaken and the embedded logic, explicit or implicit, strongly defined or vague, that shapes the construction of an impact pathway from the perspective of stakeholders and participants. These perspectives need not be consistent, in fact they are more likely to be in relations of tension or even contest as stakeholders’ interests and objectives are not homogenous. The Benefits Paper thus introduces a „transducer’ effect, which includes a recognition of the endogenous processes contributing to change that occur in the work of constructing impact pathways. The extent to which actor „intentionality’ shapes impact pathways remains an empirical question. What matters for the transducer model is to recognize that stakeholders’ perceptions, actions, and understandings of desirable transformations can contribute to the construction of theoretical impact pathways. However, establishing linear and direct linkages between inputs and outputs, interests and outcomes, is unlikely to be feasible from a monitoring perspective and is theoretically likely to invite reductionist interpretations.

Figure 2: Signal transduction between input and output

Source: Wicher et al. (2022)

The transduction process is thus neither monolithic nor consistent. Institutional and socio-cultural conditions that are configured in specific ways in different „intervention contexts’ shape the outcomes that actors strive to achieve. Transduction occurs in at multiple levels and in interlinked contexts in constructing an identifiable impact pathway. Transduction can be iterative and recursive; it can lead to consolidation as routines or to innovation through emergent events or structures. In the SUPER MoRRI model then, the transducer is the moment where endogenous and exogenous elements combine and catalyse possible future scenarios. In the Benefits Paper, this thinking underlies a model of impact pathways from the perspective of monitoring benefits for science and society.

3.2. From impact pathways to benefits

The Benefits Paper proposes a model designed to align the assessment of impact, impact pathways, and benefits from the perspective of monitoring to support open and responsible research and innovation. While to a certain extent broadly transformational impact pathways do have a certain „direction’ they involve plural and uncertain dynamics that may be far from linear in their trajectory.

Figure 3: Model of impact pathways

Source: Wicher et al. 2022

While the model includes „classical’ research impact assessment concepts including outputs, outcomes, and impacts, it does not indicate a linear and/or univocal pathway at the level of actors and activities. Rather, from an empirical monitoring perspective, actors’ interests, actions, and perspectives and evolving processes of „transduction’ in which they are involved, construct context dependent understandings of desired impacts and expected benefits. Multiple such context dependent interventions or active scenarios construct broader impact pathways (Figure 3), not necessarily in an additive or cumulative way but also through struggle, contestation, and messy co-existence.

From an analytical monitoring perspective these interventions and scenarios can be viewed as contributing in diverse ways to the macro-level depiction of broad transformational impact pathways illustrated in

. Activities associated with knowledge production and translation, or innovation, for example, can be expected to generate relatively shared or contested conceptualisations of impacts and benefits with different degrees of clarity and specificity. Monitoring should then support activities and processes of openness and responsibility that can actively contribute to and help shape contextualised configurations of impact and benefits, which over time define transformational impact pathway leading toward benefits for science and society.

From the practical perspective of experimenting with empirical monitoring tools and processes, three fundamental principles thus seemed appropriate and relevant regarding the question of benefits.

- All effects of interventions are difficult to monitor and, due to time lags and problems of causality, difficult to attribute reliably.
- Accepting that benefits are (a) normative and (b) depend on interests and values, monitoring needs to question who or what is mobilized as a „beneficiary.
- Monitoring activities reflexively impact the R&I system. We need to use responsible approaches to monitoring the contributions of open and responsible research and innovation to benefits for science and society that make their own assumptions and potential effects as transparent as possible.

3.3. Types of benefits

As mentioned above, the notion of benefit adds normativity to outcomes and to impacts from research and innovation. The basic rationale for monitoring the contribution of open and responsible research and innovation to benefits for science and for society is the argument that public investment in science, research, and innovation should improve societal well-being and the environment (MoRRI Final Report). The category of „benefits’ is thus obviously broad and nebulous, seeking as it does to isolate „positive’ or „enriching’ effects and impacts from the complex and overdetermined maze of contributions that lead toward societal transformations. Benefits can thus only be thought of at a general or abstract analytical level.

In 2013, the European Commission issued a call for tender for the assessment of “economic, social and democratic” benefits of RRI. In its final report (Peter et al., 2018), the ensuing MoRRI project

discussed the conceptualisation of benefits and how to connect markers of open and responsible research and innovation with markers of benefits.

The concept of RRI benefits cannot be simply read off this intervention logic as an inevitable extension of the impacts of RRI. Although RRI benefits may indeed be partly or, in some contexts, largely based on an accumulation of positive impacts of RRI, this conceptualisation is not sufficient to capture what is meant by RRI benefits (...) RRI benefits cannot be sensibly interpreted, or systematically monitored, in the absence of a framework that guides expectations about the (expected) qualities and (desirable) directions of change”, (Peter et al. 2018: 30).

The ensuing MoRRI project identified a fourth category, “scientific” benefits knowledge production and the research system itself (Peter et al., 2018).

In the empirical monitoring efforts of the SUPER MoRRI these four high-level categories – societal, democratic economic, scientific – continued to be used to distinguish different types of benefits that monitoring would endeavour to associate, as plausibly as possible, with open and responsible research and innovation. A dual strategy was adopted, to use patterns and pathways data as distinctive methodological approaches to describing apparent connections between markers of open and responsible research and innovation and markers of benefits of different types. This Pathways Studies Report (D5.3) uses qualitative information and narratives as markers of open and responsible research innovation contributions to benefits. The separate Pattern Studies (D5.2) uses patterns produced by quantitative data collections as markers of open and responsible research and innovation contributions to benefits. Together these two reports highlight the distinctive challenges of monitoring that seeks to inform about both the scope and the dynamics of generating impacts and benefits through open and responsible research approaches.

4. Civil Societies at Science-Society interface

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4.1. Introduction

The European Commission's (EC) Horizon 2020 (H2020) framework programme includes several calls for the broader inclusion of diverse actors within the research and innovation system. Central within this is the call for including civil society organisations (CSOs) within the research and innovation system. The H2020 funding calls for Science with and for Society (SwafS), which contained the areas of Ethics, Science Education, Open Science (Open Access), the promotion of Gender Equality in Research and Innovation, and most central for this study, Public Engagement in Responsible Research and Innovation are focal in this effort. SwafS funding calls, and the language employed within them surrounding efforts for engaging civil society organisations in the research and innovation system will be explored in more detail below.

This project explores the experiences that CSOs have with these research funding calls seeking to interlink science and society more closely. Specifically, the study will critically investigate what kinds of impacts these new funding schemes are having on CSOs at the science-society interface by conducting semi-structured interviews with representatives from environmental CSOs in the Netherlands.

In the paragraphs below, first some theoretical work on citizen science and civil society involvement in science will be described, and next a description of how civil society / citizen involvement of science is described in the documentation of the European commission.

4.2. Civic involvement in the research and innovation system

This case study explores the ways in which civil society organisations (CSOs) can engage with the research and innovation system. The phrase „civic involvement' is used in this case since the topic of interest lies not purely in what are explicitly referred to as „citizen science' projects, but rather collaborations with CSOs (representing citizen concerns) and the research and innovation system. Persson and Edholm (2018) note that consultations with CSOs function to serve as a compensatory function for the democratic deficit that exists within EU institutions, highlighting their role of representing the needs and interests of citizens (Persson & Edholm, 2020). The same democratic deficit has been perceived within the research and innovation system, which is particularly challenging to combat due to the role of formalized expertise and a concomitant high threshold of participation. Furthermore, the initial intentions behind the SwafS research program are to align the research and innovation system to societal needs and values, which requires civic society involvement in the process of research and innovation. Civil society organisations' inclusion in the scientific process is being promoted. However, there are few attempts to understand the role of civil society organisations in research (Llorente et al., 2020).

The input of civil society in the research process can result in the production of alternative forms of knowledge which would otherwise be unlikely to be developed. The contemporary constellation of funding organisations and universities is increasingly dependent on private funding sources, working towards technology transfer programs, and economic competitiveness, and consequently the knowledge produced within this system will suit the needs of these dependencies (Bickerstaff et al., 2010). Frickel and colleagues (2010) describe that because of these influences on the research and innovation system, knowledge which serves the function of reducing inequalities, challenging

economic and political elites, and that which would benefit thus far neglected populations and movements goes underfunded and under supported (Frickel et al., 2010). They continue in saying that it is precisely this „knowledge that could have helped a social movement or other civil society organisation to mobilize the intellectual resources needed to confront an industrial / political elite’. The knowledge which is left unsupported because of the entanglement of political and industrial pressures is termed „undone science’.

In a series of case studies ranging from alternatives to chlorinated chemicals, and the pushback of environmental and public health NGOs in the United States, to civil society organisations challenging the requirements of restricting air pollution, Frickel and colleagues (2010) highlight the various roles that civil society organisations have changed regulatory standards, scientific practices, and the forms of knowledge which are developed within research, innovation, and regulatory systems. It is also for this reason that the current case study focuses on the small and medium sized CSO’s that emerged from social movements.

In the context of the policy device of RRI, it has been noted that the inclusion of CSOs in projects has been more diverse and multifaceted than originally expected (Moore et al., 2011). Ahrweiler and colleagues (2019) note that when CSOs have been able to engage within European RRI projects, these organisations often go beyond their expected roles, which are often defined as being the „moral voice’ of projects (Ahrweiler et al., 2019).

Unfortunately, the study described above had various theoretical and methodological limitations. Theoretical limitations included insufficient attention to potential factors that limited the participation of CSOs who might not have been able to participate in the projects investigated. A considerable methodological limitation is that the interviewees and survey respondents were, to a large extent, not representatives working at civil society organisations. This present case study seeks to remedy at least partially some of these limitations.

It cannot be assumed that funding calls which seek to include CSOs in the research and innovation system will have an inherently beneficial impact on those organisations; nor can it be assumed that these funding calls will have an inherently beneficial impact on the distribution of power and resources within civil society more broadly. It is likely the case that very large CSOs, with considerable resources at the outset are more able to apply for funding through these funding opportunities, as opposed to smaller, less resourced CSOs, resulting in the commission’s funding device potentially feeding into existing inequalities between organisations. In an investigation into the impacts of the funding of CSOs by the European Union by Persson and Edholm (2018) show that funding often results in *more support* for organisations that represent populations and causes that are already overrepresented. The same may be true of the forms of CSOs which are able to engage with the research and innovation system through SwafS calls. Calls for a more democratized science system fall flat if those organisations being supported already depart from an advantageous, well-resourced, privileged position.

4.3. Public engagement with science at the European Commission

Whilst the assumption of the RRI keys is that they lead to benefits, the reality is that the keys of public engagement and citizen science may lead to benefits, if we improve the pathways towards them, including addressing barriers. This case study has the intention of exploring the ways in which CSOs can engage with funding opportunities provided by the EC through the SwafS program. This document will not provide an extensive discussion and analysis of the documents provided by the EC describing

the intentions and goals of this engagement, but it will be useful to explore the rhetoric of inclusion that is provided by the documents of the EC.

Central within the EC's plans for the broader public engagement of civil society in the research and innovation process is the policy device of Responsible research and innovation (RRI), which is described as the following „Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) implies that societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of society'. In the successor programme, Horizon Europe, Open and Responsible R&I practices are central, including Open Science, Citizen Science, Science Education, Gender, and Ethics. Especially citizen science and working with CSO's is expected to empower that the outcomes of R&I are understood, trusted, and increasingly used, by educated informed scientists and citizens to the benefit of society (European Commission, 2022).

Evidently, the rhetoric describing the policy device explicitly calls for attending to the values of society to be incorporated into the research and innovation system in a more comprehensive and systematic way to be able to contribute to the green deal, digital transition and the welfare and wellbeing of European citizens.

4.4. Objective and method of the study

The objective of this study is to generate knowledge which would benefit research funding organisations in working to include CSOs more systematically within the research and innovation system.

Specifically, this study seeks to understand the impediments that prevent CSOs from participating in research calls funded by the European Commission, with a particular interest in calls contained within SwafS and other RRI related funding.

The primary definition of RRI that is adopted within this study is the form introduced by Stilgoe and colleagues (2013), which thinks of RRI more as a process to incorporate social values and participatory efforts into the research and innovation system. While we incorporate this model conceptually, we also utilize the specific dimensions proposed by the European Commission's model which features the „keys". The principle RRI key that is addressed within the study is the RRI concept of Public Engagement with science. In the study, we take as an assumption that CSOs represent, to some extent, relevant „publics' within science-society relationships². Consequently, since the case study examines the degree to which this institutionalized representation of certain “publics” can participate in the process of research and innovation through SwafS and RRI related calls, Public Engagement with science becomes the most addressed dimension.

During the SUPER MoRRI project, RRI was conceptually included in the Open and Responsible R&I practices that focus on open science and citizen science. This study includes the citizen science key as being part of and overlapping with aspects of Public Engagement and Open Science.

In citizen science, and likewise, in CSO's participating in research, in addition to the scientific goals there are multiple additional goals that come into play, and for each project there may be a multiplicity of expectations set. Such goals, from the perspective of scientists and funders may include raising public awareness to the scientific issue underlying the project, production of scientific knowledge and outputs, ensuring a sampling methodology, or facilitating the geographical and temporal coverage at scales that are impossible otherwise. Projects might be expected to be inclusive in terms of gender,

ethnicity, educational attainment, and increase scientific literacy, while also finding ways to access people's resources (e.g., time) and create an enjoyable and engaging experience (EC, 2022).

Whilst these broad aims could have been expected, the reality of the interviews showed that the funding barrier for CSOs prevailed completely, as shown by the interviews.

The case study consisted of 10 semi-structured interviews. Most interviewees were representatives of CSOs (8 out of 10 interviewees) and in several cases these were the directors of the organisations of interest. Two of the interviewees came from research funding organisations; this was to provide an alternative perspective on the experience of CSO and research and innovation system interactions. Other than one organisation which was in Italy, all the organisations were in the Netherlands.

A main criterion for inclusion in the study was that organisations must, to some extent, either wish to engage with the research and innovation system in the future or must have already engaged with the research system in the past. This criterion was used to ensure that SwafS calls would be relevant for the CSOs that we investigated.

To narrow the potential organisations that could have been selected for the case study, we decided to make a thematic limitation on the kinds of organisations that we would include in the project. Ultimately, it was decided to conduct interviews with organisations that worked on issues of *sustainability, climate change, and climate justice*. This topic was selected for its relevance for public interest, civil society, and the research environment alignment with other projects being conducted at the institute.

A final criterion was set regarding the forms of CSOs that were included regarding both their size and ideological foundation. We decided to conduct the study in the context of smaller to medium sized CSOs since a major component of the study is investigating how less-resourced CSOs can participate in the research funding calls that seek to engage actors from civil society in the research and innovation process.

Furthermore, in terms of ideological foundation, we decided to seek out organisations who self-identify as related closely to „social movements, which is a delineation made by Ottinger (2017) to describe the ideological foundations of citizen science projects. Ottinger makes a distinction within citizen science efforts between those that originate from social movements, which are closer to challenging forms of authority or incorporate forms of scientific authority in ways which serve an interest as defined by the social movement / citizen science effort. This is contrasted to „scientific-authority-driven’ citizen science, which is described as projects which originate with the research questions being driven by scientists and academic professionals, who subsequently enlist citizens in some aspects of the project. We use the same conceptual distinction in selecting organisations within this project, however we adapt it to civil society organisations related to the research and innovation system rather than more narrowly on citizen science projects. The decision to focus on organisations with this foundation is to position the origin of the projects of interest as being more closely in line with the needs articulated by some form of society (in this case, represented by CSOs), rather than those being articulated by more incumbent forms of authority such as within the research and innovation system. Additionally, we chose this inclusion criteria to explore those organisations which may be relatively less-resourced when compared to those originating from the position of science-authority driven organisations.

Whilst reducing barriers for small CSO's to participate in R&I projects is one side of the narrative, the other side is how researchers themselves see the contribution of citizens, and the benefits this may have. This includes the role of funders. Therefore, in this case study, some of the results of the SUPER MoRRI researcher survey (Patterns Study, D5.2) represented, to further identify patterns of citizen science and public engagement. The data were selected from the Dutch respondents and compared to the results of the rest of Europe because the interviewed CSO's were all Dutch.

4.5. Results

The results of the interviews paint a complicated and tense relationship between the selected CSOs and the research and innovation system. There were a wide range of expressed experiences by CSOs, with some interviewees expressing acknowledgement and support of funding calls seeking to support CSOs in the research system, others expressed considerable dismay at the composition and functioning of these calls, whereas others were completely unaware of the presence of these calls in the first place.

This narrative will continue with discussing the results in different sections, highlighting key observations and themes that came to the fore throughout the interviews.

4.5.1 Absence of knowledge needs at CSOs

The notion that there is a distance between the kind of knowledge needed at CSOs and that which is produced by the research and innovation system is often mentioned as a justification to keep the two domains separate, with the claim often made that CSOs are unable to express realistic research projects that would benefit them and that the research and innovation system could provide.

This was frequently dispelled throughout the interviews as CSO representatives were frequently able to express different research topics that would be of benefit for their organisations.

For example, interviewees were able to provide an abundance of research topics that would benefit their work, such as research on the impact of advertising on perpetuating the need on non-renewable energy sources, as well as the impact that this advertising has on consumer behaviour regarding making more sustainable lifestyle choices. An additional research question which was presented as benefitting the CSOs was an exploration into the quantity of funds being invested by pension funds within Europe on fossil fuel related industries. Furthermore, multiple CSOs expressed a desire for research onto the potential impacts that their work was having on the discourse surrounding environmental debates. Social movement studies and other social sciences are likely well-equipped to provide CSO representative with research on this topic, which would bolster the legitimacy of these organisations and their efforts.

Another example of research that was mentioned pertained to the kinds of ecological impacts that the Delta works (a major land and water management infrastructure project in the Netherlands to prevent flooding) might have on the local ecosystem. The director of one major Dutch environmental CSO expressed that this is a study object which would benefit researchers, CSOs, local communities, and the environment, as this is a context in which each different group has considerable stakes, and the opportunity for intellectual as well as material innovation is high.

Evidently, when queried on the forms of knowledge that CSOs could benefit from having from the research and innovation system, CSOs are able to articulate concrete and realistic research questions which could generate useful collaborative opportunities for these organisations. While there is likely still considerable distance between CSOs and the R and I system, the distance is not a result of a lack

of thematic overlap. Rather, as many CSO representatives expressed, the distance exists because of institutional barriers between the ways in which the two different groups work (described in more detail below).

It is important to recognize the limitations that CSOs face in terms of resource constraints and expertise. It should also be acknowledged that a potential benefit of reducing barriers of participation for CSOs within research and innovation work is that research could provide knowledge and expertise that would benefit CSOs without them having to expend resources which would otherwise be taken from their core missions as CSOs. This is similarly beneficial for the research and innovation system in that there is an impetus and desire for researchers to conduct research which is more readily usable for the rest of society, and by having projects articulated and originating from CSOs, research projects could have more direct beneficiaries and users. Furthermore, increasing the active dialogue (along with a corresponding increase in resources for participants) between CSOs and the research and innovation system, from the very outset of creating new research projects, could provide a creative stimulus for the creation of research which is societally relevant, while simultaneously bolstering the work and functions of CSOs. Naturally, these efforts are costly in terms of resources and time, and these efforts must be readily supported materially for CSOs, rather than presumed to be feasible within current resource constraints.

4.5.2 Resource constraints as a barrier of participation

Several interviewees expressed resource constraints as a considerable barrier for their participation in the research and innovation system and articulated this barrier specifically in the context of seeking out funding from grants. This was expressed even (and especially) through grants that were intended to serve as bridges between the two communities, such as SwafS and other RRI calls.

These resource constraints manifest themselves as a lack of financial resources, insufficient employees, excessively demanding existing workloads, knowledge pertaining to the ways in which one should write proposals for a higher likelihood of success within these funding opportunities, among others.

Many CSOs expressed dismay at the conclusion that to receive funding from these calls, it appeared that the challenge lay not in producing the best proposal, but rather in being able to align the language and format of calls with the (often opaque) expectations within funding organisations. One interviewee noted:

“The rules of the game are very subtle, it’s difficult to know what exactly is expected in these calls... It’s not transparent how to successfully write a call that will get funded, since the decision is often ultimately made by inaccessible third parties who only give advice and feedback once the proposal has been submitted”.

Evidently, while rules for proposals may be transparent, this interviewee feels that there appear to be unspoken rules and expectations that exist within the funding procedure. While those within the research and innovation system may have considerable resources to apply for funding opportunities frequently, interviewees often expressed that this process could result in considerable challenges to the continuation of their organisations:

“Unlike universities, who have many individuals working on project design, in small organisations like ours the same person has to take care of state of the art reviews, preparing the scientific argument...”

This interviewee went on to note that expanding this quantity of resources for funding calls that ultimately have a very slim likelihood of success take up considerable resources that jeopardize the working capacity of the organisation.

Indeed, several CSOs noted that it’s often the directors of the CSOs who ultimately must do the majority of the work involved in writing proposals for calls, and that this is often done on non-working hours, resulting in a higher likelihood of work-related stress and burnout. One interviewee compared temporary funding for their organisation to a drug addiction, noting:

“Our organisation is addicted to these funding cycles. It’s like with the end of each funding cycle, we have to get another hit, and without it we’re just not going to survive. We’re having a very active discussion at the organisation to cut our funding and the size of our organisation by two-thirds, because we can’t keep running after funding calls like this.”

The same interviewee went on to explain that at times, more than half of the organisations’ FTEs were working either on new funding calls or writing accountability reports for funders, resulting in the actual work related to the mission statement of the organization as taking up less than half of their working hours.

This is the picture painted of smaller CSOs of the kinds of barriers expressed within seeking funding for research and innovation system related grants, However, interviewees mentioned that these constraints are not identical for larger organizations. They noted that much bigger and well-resourced CSOs have considerable internal infrastructures with dedicated staff working on funding calls and seeking out new sources of funding at all times. What results is the perpetuation of distance between bigger and smaller CSOs; larger CSOs, who already have considerable resources, further benefit by being able to win the majority of funding opportunities, further shrinking the quantity available for smaller organizations. The current system of funding appears, then, to be increasing the inequality between these forms of organizations, rather than serving to remedy it. Persson and Edholm (2018) have made similar observations of European Commission funding for NGOs serving to reify, rather than diminish, inequalities between organizations through their funding mechanisms.

This likely has consequences on the kinds of projects undertaken (and the subsequent knowledge produced), as the kind of work conducted by smaller and larger CSOs likely differ considerably. Where funding calls to be created more in line with the capacities of small and medium sized CSOs (by communicating with CSOs how to better align their funding proposal systems according to the means present at smaller CSOs, or learning from funding proposal systems present at other foundations more amenable to the needs of CSOs), the creation of a more diverse landscape of voices and views could be established within the relationships between CSOs and the research and innovation system. This requires acknowledging the reality of resource inequality between large and small CSOs and making the explicit decision to incorporate and support countervailing views within collaborations between the civil society and the research and innovation system. A more diverse and equitable system of collaboration between CSOs and the research and innovation system require consideration of, and active intervention within, the current state of resource inequality between different organizations, and especially in supporting small under-resourced organizations that represent views which may

challenge incumbent structures of power. In short, the potential benefits of Public Engagement and citizen science to take on more diverse topics depend on reducing barriers for small CSO's to participate in R&I. By doing so, engaging with small and medium sized CSO's help to make sure that scientific agendas are well aligned with grand societal challenges and thus it enhances societal trust in science and could help funding bodies to make a better investment into research development and open innovation.

4.5.3 The accountability burden and its constraints on mission related activities

Accompanying successfully obtained grants from research and innovation funding bodies are a swathe of accountability measures, as well as demands for a set of extensive deliverables, to track the development of funded projects. Many of these accountability measures are composed in ways which align with the working habits of academic workers; however, these do not necessarily extend well to the context of CSOs.

Interviewees highlighted that they felt as though having to report so frequently, and in the form of long formed texts, detracted away from the kinds of work that the CSOs intend to complete. Hence, it was not only the quantity of accountability measures imposed upon organizations that served as a challenge, but also the quality and form of the accountability measures themselves. Interviewees expressed that it was not their missions to produce a steady output of articles, deliverables, or other forms of written documentation of their efforts, and that having to complete these tasks often drained their already scarce resources.

As mentioned above, interviewees expressed that the funding acquisition process can at times take up more than half of the FTEs available at organizations, and this in addition with the accountability procedures they are requested to supply and can ultimately result in significantly less resources being expended on their actual practical and „on the ground' work which they hoped to complete.

In contrast, CSOs gave the example of accountability measures which were requested by private foundations, which were often the main source of funding for these organizations. Interviewees noted the greater degree of trust, flexibility, and accommodation of working rhythms of private foundations with their work. Many of the accountability procedures from private foundations consisted of several meetings per year to discuss the status, progress, and existing challenges within CSOs in accomplishing their stated goals and objectives throughout the progress. CSO representatives mentioned that these meetings were often organized to coincide with existing internal evaluations that the CSOs already conducted, resulting in no additional resources being spent on accountability checks than what would have been conducted anyways. CSO representatives expressed that the accountability forms within private foundations felt as though they were exercises for funders and funded organizations to learn from one another, rather than hold the organizations to account for their activities.

Interviewees highlighted the greater feeling of trust and collaboration which took place in these discussions with private foundations and felt that this lacked with the ways in which research and innovation funding organizations undertook their accountability work. Furthermore, they felt that the private foundations served more as a resource to help them attain their common objectives, rather than serve as an opportunity for funders to exert their will and extract certain goals from the funded organizations.

This highlights that the ways in which research and innovation funding organizations have failed to curate their project designs, and especially the accountability designs, to the needs and modes of work contained within small and medium sized CSOs. It should not be expected that CSOs share the same

objectives and intended outputs with the research system, nor can it be expected that this is the best mode of output for the funded projects. The greater flexibility and trust contained within private foundations provide an infrastructure within which more impact can be attained by CSOs; in contrast, the lengthy and extensive forms of accountability imposed by research and innovation funding organizations likely distract and reduce resources for these kinds of impacts, hindering rather than helping to produce relevant knowledge.

By opening the process of knowledge creation beyond the limiting borders of academia and research institutions, citizen science and CSO's enable the inclusion of local expertise and lay knowledge in the scientific process. It enriches the research findings. This was confirmed by the results from the researcher survey.

Were more ambitious, flexible, and trusting accountability regimes to be implemented within these funding calls, potentially greater transformative change could occur with collaborations between civil society organizations and the research and innovation system. This could take place by considering existing accountability methods that already exist within CSOs to reduce the additional burden of accountability measures of research and innovation funding organizations. Furthermore, accountability discussions between funders and the funded should be reorganized and reconceptualized as opportunities to assist CSOs and for mutual learning. Central within this conceptual shift is to emphasize trust and a willingness to listen and learn from small and medium sized CSOs.

4.5.4 Closed networks and mission movement

Interviewees expressed a lack of knowledge about the kinds of funding opportunities that exist to bridge the world of CSOs and the research and innovation system, with multiple interviewees expressing that they had never been aware of SwafS calls. This was particularly the case in the smallest CSOs that were interviewed, highlighting that there existed a lack of efforts from the research and innovation system to reach out to CSOs and seek novel relationships and collaborations.

Most interviewees expressed never having heard of the terminology of responsible research and innovation (RRI), and upon hearing its articulation throughout the interviews, remarked on its necessity. This was even prominent among organizations that had made explicit intentions to engage with the research system through collaborative projects with local universities. This highlights the need for funding organizations to form new ways of engaging with and communicating with civil society, rather than presuming that CSOs will find their ways to funding devices if they are made available to them.

It was remarked by representatives from larger CSOs that were interviewed that their more typical way of engaging with these research calls was to activate the same network of institutions and actors whenever seeking out funding. This was to reduce the resource costs of applying for funding, and to make the process as swift as possible. This stands in direct opposition of the stated goals of these funding devices to actively create novel opportunities for collaborations between institutions and organizations that were distant and not involved within the research and innovation system. Furthermore, this results in more hegemonic projects being produced, which do not seek for more innovative projects which challenge existing practices, as the same actors tend to be able to locate and apply for funds more successfully. The end-product is a system which is more narrow, singular, and exclusive than conceptualized in the rhetorical background of these funding calls.

Furthermore, many interviewees expressed that the ways in which funding devices were designed resulted in these organizations having to shift their modes and topics of work away from their initial missions – a phenomenon that was termed as „mission movement’ by CSOs. This manifested itself both in the ways that CSOs worked (less „on the ground’ and more bureaucratized and written output / deliverable focused), as well as the content of the projects that these organizations designed. Furthermore, the stated functions of CSOs within the projects were often narrowly defined by the ways in which the projects were designed, and many CSOs felt as though their inclusion was rather more a tokenistic exercise than a legitimate extension of equitable participation of civil society.

Indeed, this is likely to some extent intentional, as funding devices are methods to steer the products of research and innovation. However, with the stated goals of RRI being to recreate the research and innovation system into one which is more just, more equitable, more participatory, and more in tune with the values of society, the direction of change should be reversed. Indeed, the aim and benefit of RRI could be to support civil society in changing the content and form of the research and innovation system, at least to an extent. Research and innovation funders should provide more opportunities (and coinciding resources) to facilitate the creation of new networks with CSOs rather than operating under the assumption that CSOs will be able to locate these funds through their own efforts. Furthermore, there should be more direct resources given to organizations in the stage of consortium building to facilitate the position of thus-far excluded CSOs who wish to participate in these projects.

If this were to be taken up by research funders, the benefits of civil society to participate in R&I could support novel opportunities, in topic and in participants, leading to innovative projects with a legitimate and equitable participation of society.

4.5.5 Researcher survey findings on citizen science

Cooperation of academic researchers with citizens, consumers, patients, and other non-academic actors is still limited, it ranges from around 20% to even less of the research where such collaboration is taking place regularly. Collaboration with other actors of the quadruple helix, such as policy or companies, is a bit higher, around 25%. It also means that in 80-90% of the research hardly any such collaboration is actually taking place.

One of the explanations that such collaboration with non-academic actors is not taking place, may be the uncertainty as regards the requirements of funders for such collaboration or funding opportunities. If you look at the motivations of researchers for engaging with non-academic actors (all of them), there is a tendency of 40% of the respondents to rather agree that it is a requirement of the research funders, and even may provide further opportunities to attract further research funding, against around 30% that disagrees. You could say that researchers understand that such collaborative practices are supported by funders but the actual level to which is unclear.

Motivations to engage with non-academic actors are rather positive: Around 80% of the researchers do think that that they should engage more if they want to maximize the impact of their research. And more than half actually agree that benefits could be positive for them, although a substantial part (35%) doesn’t see how.

In terms of other benefits, a good one third of the researchers already has observed recognition of citizens knowledge in research and an increase in citizens competencies. Another one third, hasn’t observed that, but would expect it to arise. This indicates that there is a positive attitude towards these benefits in around 70% of the cases. There is not a specifically Dutch attitude in these topics, as

the percentages of the Dutch respondents compared to those of the rest of Europe are roughly similar. It was important to check this as the case study was executed in the Netherlands.

4.5.6 Recommendations articulated by interviewees

Interviewees were able to express various recommendations for how to ensure a more legitimate and productive inclusion of civil society within the research and innovation system. These were as follows:

- Greater clarity on how funders expect NGOs to be able to participate in calls to facilitate the entrance of a more diverse set of CSOs to participate within the research and innovation system.
- Funders must make intentional efforts to reach out to small and medium sized CSOs to expand the network of organizations that participate in their funded projects.
- CSOs should participate in the creation of calls to better tune them to the needs and capabilities within CSOs to reduce the burden of project seeking activities undertaken by CSOs; this will facilitate the entrance of less resourced and smaller CSOs in participating in research and innovation projects.
- More flexibility, more trust, fewer accountability checks, and a curated approach to accountability for the practices of CSOs; this will allow for accountability procedures to be more in tune with the goals of mutual learning and support to facilitate the effective completion of projects according to both parties rather than serving as a regime of punishment and control.
- Ambition in stepping out of the prototypical model of project-based funding with deliverable based production methods; the short-term project funding cycles limit the kinds of projects that organizations are able to accomplish, increase labour precarity among CSO workers, and create cultures of short-term thinking within organizations and funders.
- Material support for the creation of networks and relationships between hitherto excluded CSOs to provide a more inclusive and diverse set of organizations engaging with the research and innovation system.

4.6 Results and pathways towards RRI impacts and Benefits

In the case study the keys of public engagement (PE) and citizen science are primarily addressed.

Within efforts to create a more socially responsible research and innovation system, the engagement of the public (and in this case, CSOs which represent particular forms of publics) is among the principal methods that this is thought to be possible.

Through investigating barriers to participation in research and innovation projects experienced by CSOs, a more inclusive and participatory research and innovation system can be developed which more directly engages with representatives from civil society. CSOs represent diverse values and publics and contain value-driven mandates within their mission statements; by facilitating their involvement within the research and innovation system in a more equitable way, more just and diverse research and innovative developments can take place.

CSOs and their expertise also represent a great opportunity for innovative projects that may not come intuitively to researchers, and hence represent a currently neglected source of new research topics. Furthermore, CSOs represent a direct community of practitioners who could use the outputs and

knowledge created by researchers within their work. This raises the legitimacy of the work of both research and CSOs, in accomplishing impact through their activities.

On the side of the researchers, these benefits for citizens and for engagement with other non-academic actors are recognized and supported.

Finally, aligning research and innovation funding organizations to be more in tune with the needs and capabilities of CSOs represents a step towards remedying the present resource crisis (driven by short-term project-based funding devices) that are broadly experienced by CSOs (as well as in the academic sector). This gap of resources (and the dependency on rapid and short project-based funding cycles) inhibits the creation of longer-term and sustained projects and likely impacts the kinds of impacts organizations are able to manifest, as well the kinds of research that researchers are able to conduct.

Regarding open science further, as indicated by the collaboration of researchers with non-academic actors ranging from citizens, consumers/users, to policy and companies, the results indicate that this is taking place in 20-25% of the projects.

4.6.1 How do the actors in the study describe the pathways towards impacts and benefits?

CSO representatives that were interviewed in the context of this study describe a broad swathe of potential benefits from reducing the barriers preventing their participation within the research and innovation system. They note a bidirectional benefit of legitimacy that could be granted to both researchers and CSOs. CSOs would gain legitimacy by having research to inform their practices and researchers would gain legitimacy in creating a research system which is more in tune with the needs of society, as well as through engaging practitioners more directly.

Additionally, considering that CSOs represent certain forms of society, by reducing the thresholds of participation for CSOs and working to include a more diverse array of organizations, the research and innovation system will benefit from a greater variance of views and perspectives contained within projects.

The case study, taken from the perspective of the social movement CSO's who are not regular participants in projects funded by the typical R&I funders, would suggest the following on social, democratic, and economic benefits:

Social and democratic benefits of R&I are likely to occur if the barriers for funding of CSO's would become better aligned to their needs. In turn this would allow addressing other topics of research that address societal challenges and better democratic representation of groups usually not included in R&I projects due to the demanding nature of such projects.

Also, researchers (80%) expect more social impact of their research as a result of more collaboration with non-academic partners and recognition of citizens knowledge in research.

In terms of scientific benefits, the case study as such doesn't address the scientific quality per se, since that is not usually the prime objective of small and medium-sized CSO's. However, from the researchers' perspective, the expectations on the quality of scientific outputs as a result of engaging with non-academic actors are largely positive: 58% already has seen an increase in the quality (25%) or is actually expecting that to occur (33%), whereas another one third has not seen a change and is not expecting it either.

Economic benefits, again seen from the perspective of the small and medium sized CSO's economic benefits are not necessarily expected or pursued other than happening as a consequence of

addressing socially relevant topics. Researchers on the other side, do expect improved products and services and more innovations as a result of engagement with non-academic actors, around 60% reports such a positive benefit, of which 30% already has observed such benefits.

Together, the findings suggest that funders can play an even more critical role in making sure that CSO's and all other non-academic actors are more frequently include in research projects.

4.6.1 Consideration of contextual factors relevant for assessing pathways and impacts of RRI
If we were to consider indicators from this case study, it would relate to the Research Funder Organization Study (RFO), and support, contextualize and finetune findings therein. For instance, the categorization of funders policies towards citizen science and public engagement could be scrutinized for the presence of specific needs and criteria to empower citizens and citizen science organization to apply for funding in a meaningful way. It would mean to go into the nitty gritty details of call text preparations, applicant requirement and reporting modalities.

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5. Coding of ethics and values into autonomous systems - (How) Can you build morality into artificially intelligent systems?

Kjetil Rommetveit, Ingrid Foss Ballo

5.1. Introduction

As more and more technological systems become 'intelligent' and autonomously operating actors enabled by machine learning, robotics, and artificial intelligence (AI), doubts about the ethical and societal viability of such technologies come to the fore of public policies. According to Eurobarometer, Europeans are increasingly concerned about impacts of AI, especially automation of tasks at work (Eurobarometer 2021), and specific websites dedicated to mapping of AI incidents have become popular.⁴ Initial debates were predominantly infused by science fiction and voiced by prominent people in science and technology: fears of super-intelligent machines ("general AI") gaining autonomy and turning against its human users and developers, even eradicating the human race (Boström 2002). Yet, as AI to some extent becomes reality, debates are about by more mundane issues, such as social sorting (Pasquale 2015), "bias", power imbalances and justice, election manipulation (Van Dijk 2021), ubiquitous surveillance (Zuboff 2019), privacy infringements (Rommetveit and van Dijk 2022) and accidents provoked by self-driving cars. One immediate response to this situation has been a flourishing of ethical reports, analyses, and meta-analyses, of the 'ethics of AI' (for an overview, see Fjeld et al. 2020). In Europe, a prominent example of this is the so-called AI regulatory package, which includes law and soft law regulation, and foreshadowed by an ethics report by the High-Level Expert Group on AI Ethics (hereafter AI HLEG).

A precursor to present practices based in values-in-design occurred in Asimov's three principles of robotics, introduced in science fiction as early as 1942 (Asimov 1942)⁵. In Asimov's story, these ethical principles are described as "built most deeply into a robot's positronic brain" (Asimov, 1942). Yet, it would take several decades before any such possibility would start to be imagined and experimented with in actual robotic or digital systems (including so-called AI), or by ethicists and philosophers. The ethics of ICTs were increasingly discussed and analysed in novel fields such as computer ethics (Moore 1985, Tavani 2007), engineering ethics and robo-ethics (Lin, Abney and Bekey 2012) during the 1980s and 90s. Yet, it was not until later, i.e., in the 1990s and 2000s, that prospects of hardcoding moral principles into a robots' architecture became a topic, triggering imaginations and prospects of a new field, machine ethics, where moral principles can be designed and hardcoded into the robot's 'brain' (Allen, Varner and Zinser 2000, Allen and Wallach 2009). Robot morality and rights for artificial agents have been hotly debated in political arenas, such as the European Parliament's debate over "electronic personhood" in 2016 (Rommetveit et al. 2020). It is also presaged in global documents and standards, such as the IEEE Ethically Aligned Design (IEEE 2017, 2019), and in the IEEE's 7000 Ethics for Autonomous and intelligent Systems series (IEEE 2023).

⁴ <https://incidentdatabase.ai>

⁵ 1) A robot may not injure a human being or, through inaction, allow a human being to come to harm. 2) A robot must obey orders given it by human beings except where such orders would conflict with the First Law. 3) A robot must protect its own existence as long as such protection does not conflict with the First or Second Law.

These regulatory developments are novel in a least two ways: first, by embracing a risk-based approach to values-based regulations, i.e., focusing on 'significant risk to the health and safety or fundamental rights of persons', (Trilateral Research 2022). The language of risk assessment and management is historically alien to the universe of moral and legal principles, but this is now changing (Van Dijk et al. 2016). Second, new approaches in values-based design will assess such risks, as well as ethical (and legal) principles, and try to take them into account at the earliest stages of designing AI systems (AI-HLEG 2019), rendering them in principle “ethical, lawful and robust” (Ibid.) by design. Whereas these developments do have precursors, i.e., in the field of values-based design, their introduction to governance and regulation is new. In the context of the AI-HLEG report, specific guidelines for ethics-by-design have been developed by a European Commission expert group (EC 2021), providing specificity for implementation of the principles outlined in the AI-HLEG report. This turn to risk- and design-based solutions also entails a shift in the sites of governance: towards engineering and infrastructuring work. They render normative standards part of the very building blocks of technologies, infrastructures, and markets, and so also displace the focus of governance. There is by now a plethora of standards oriented towards implementation, protection and enhancement of human-centric values, such as (in order of historical emergence) the (British) BS8611, the IEEE Ethically aligned Design initiative (IEEE 2016, 2018), followed up by the IEEE 7000s-series (including more than 10 'ethical standards', IEEE 2023), and the ISO ISO/IEC 38507 on Governance implications of the use of artificial intelligence by organizations.

In previous research on data protection, we have identified this turn towards design-based regulation as inscribed into a techno-regulatory imaginary (Rommetveit and van Dijk 2022), whose defining characteristic is that the very problem articulation is now imagined to be situated inside the technologies and infrastructures themselves, partially outside of classical regulatory sites (government, parliament, state bureaucracies) oriented towards standardisation and infrastructuring. Their main mode(s) of implementation reside in exactly the risk- and the design-based approaches to management and regulation.

In this brief report we investigate these developments, pursuing the question of what happens to values and principles as they become matters of design and engineering. As stated in the Super-MORRI D5.1 the case study will investigate efforts (in governance and research laboratories) to build ethics and values into autonomous (digital) systems. It will focus on how ethics in design is being implemented in practice, where and by whom. The aim is to document changes to policy practices as indicated by the increasing use of design-oriented language and practice. The policies addressed by our research are specifically relevant for the RRI keys “Ethics” and “Governance”. Our study can be situated within an RRI framework both through its emphasis on the product and process of AI technologies (Von Schomberg 2011), and through emphasis on mutual alignments of variously involved actors regarding reflexivity, responsiveness, anticipation, and deliberation (von Schomberg 2011, 2013; Stilgoe et al. 2012; Owen 2015; see also Callon et al. 2001; Guston 2014; RRI Tools 2014).

Table 3 demonstrates broad changes to the ways in which two RRI keys, ethics, and governance, are talked about and practiced. In broad terms, these are changes to the fields of ethics and engineering, through which these are brought into closer contact and mediation (Latour 1994, Verbeek 2006). The mediating factor in this case is the language of design, which holds out the promise to align digital technologies more closely with ethical values, such as autonomy, fairness, privacy, and accountability (EC 2021). As analysed by mediation theory, the meaning of “ethics” and “values” can be expected to change as they become embedded within technical and material infrastructures, and with (software and hardware) engineering practices. And, as already mentioned, this shift in the meaning (of ethics

and governance) is inseparable from shifts in site, where practices of ethics and governance become implemented in more privatised, market-based, and technology-centred sites.

Table 3: Time-series for hits on search words 'artificial intelligence' AND 'ethics' AND 'design'

Period / Site	Google	Springer	Nature	IEEE
1990-95	5 370	554	4	40
1995-2000	7 800	762	6	76
2000-2005	14 200	1 022	6	150
2005-2010	17 400	1 842	11	256
2010-2015	18 400	3 647	43	301
2015-2020	27 600	11 975	566	447
2020-2023	136 000	26 911	1 343	474

Source: Time series from searches made on the search engines of Google Scholar, Springer, Nature and IEEE.

For the IEEE the search words were limited to 'ethics' and 'design'. From 2015 and onwards we see sharp intensifications of occurrences.

Hence our research question: What happens to rights and values as they become subject to design and engineering? Because there is not (as we will show) one single answer to that question, we shall proceed in this text to lay out five design articulations, each of which describes the space of mediation (captured by the term “design”) differently. This does not mean that our design articulations are mutually exclusive: at least some of them are likely to co-exist and mutually fortify each other; others may come into conflict or be mutually exclusive. We first lay out our five design articulations, then comment on some such overall relations between them.

5.2. Design articulations

Our first two design articulations correspond with classical positions, according to which (institutional and philosophical) ethics and engineering are different knowledge practices with distinct ways of knowing and different claims on truthfulness and veracity (Latour 2013). This implies that, when brought together, one of these tends to dominate or dictate the other involved parties and knowledge practices, in an asymmetrical relation (Gorman 2010).

Ethics and engineering as knowledge practices are brought together.

5.2.1 Ethics rules

On the face of it seems clear exactly who knows about values and ethics, namely professional ethicists, many of whom have a background in philosophy. Accordingly, the task should be to articulate the right and fitting principles for AI systems, such as a recommendation system, a driverless vehicle, a face recognition system, or a care robot. This way of configuring the problem and its design space begins and ends with ethics, insofar as the main emphasis is on the ethical analysis and its resolution in philosophical and ethical terms. Within philosophy this tendency towards solving problems in philosophical terms is strong, and this also has a strong impact on philosophical ethics. Yet, our category is somewhat broader, insofar as we include any position that implies that the problem is primarily a normative one, and that the normative question should be settled before (e.g., as a legal principle), and outside of, the task of designing and implementing a technical or organisational problem. Examples of this approach from our ethics corpus include (Bryson 2018, Ryan 2020, Liao et al. 2020).

The ethical problem, then, could be framed according to several ethical and philosophical positions, and also legal ones. In the AI ethics literature, typical positions are virtue ethics, Kantianism (duty ethics or de-ontological ethics) and utilitarianism. Other approaches based in philosophical ethics could be care ethics, feminist ethics, meta-ethics, phenomenology, and hermeneutics. Whereas there is great diversity, a possible common denominator would be the tendency to mainly use the AI ethical problem as a case in which philosophers and ethicists get to exercise their arguments, frequently grounded in long-standing debates between theoretical positions. As such, autonomous digital systems and AI do not pose radically new requirements but serve as occasion for re-casting philosophical ethics in a new setting. That is, the problem framing is largely discipline-based, and not emerging from a context of application. Yet, the question then becomes: presuming that the ethical problem is dealt with: how is it to be translated into material and technological practice? Is this question dealt with, or is it treated as insignificant? Yet, commonly, this question is not answered within the frame of this articulation.

5.2.2 Engineers in the driver's seat

A second position becomes almost the opposite of the previous: here, the engineers take the lead. By defining the problem space as a task for engineering, the ensuing disciplinary spaces and intellectual relations of problem solving are also shaped. As one instantiation of this position, consider the statement by Prof. Ali Hassami at an open panel at the main privacy conference in Europe (CPDP), Can ethics be standardised? Hassami claimed that philosophers have had the chance of setting ethics on a firm basis since the times of Aristotle, but basically, they have gotten nowhere: “Aristotle’s virtue ethics is more than 2,000 years old, still there are no standards for it”. Hassami did not refer to standards in an “old” sense (i.e., as applying to people and to norms of proper behaviour, rather than to technical things, cf. Busch 2011); rather, he was referring to technical standards for engineering. Hassami was the chair for the IEEE’s ethics standards series and has been vocal on the need to include ethics as part of engineering discipline and practice. A main example of this approach can be found in the IEEE standard 7007, where various ethics approaches (virtue ethics, utilitarianism, Kantianism) are transformed into machine-readable formalised language. According to Hassami, the aim of this standard series is to “... offer a way of addressing ethical concerns to engineers and scientists who were involved in articulating, designing and developing autonomous intelligent systems ...” (Bussemaker and Hassami 2022). This inclusion of ethics into engineering practice is necessitated by the evolution of autonomous intelligent systems. It entails that we “throw in one other category (ethics) that has been eluding us, if you like, until AI came about.” The reason for this argument is that AI (and, more broadly, machine learning) enable more autonomous behaviours in machines, including simple decision-making capacities (ibid.).

The audience of this approach is “engineers and developers” as it is they who will have to render ethics an object of engineering interventions. It is “...largely a technocratic approach” although “the standard recommends consultation with key stakeholders” (ibid.) for inputs on key ethical and moral (even religious) matters. This design articulation therefore exists in a rather tense relation: between the requirements of engineers aiming to standardise language and render ethical considerations machine-readable, and the need for broader “stakeholder involvement” and inclusion of a great variety of values and interests. It is reflected in how Hassami refers to the need to keep an open mind to different ethical positions, including non-western ones, whereas when it comes down to the making of machine readable “ethical ontologies”, the alternatives are reduced to the classics: virtue ethics, de-ontology and utilitarianism. That this approach is not shared by all, or most, engineers, is clear: within the 7000 standards series it makes for an exception. It is specifically pursued however in IEEE

7007, Ontological Standard for Ethically Driven Robotics and Automation Systems, which seeks to formalise and operationalise virtue ethics, Kantian de-ontology, and utilitarianism. As an example, within this articulation, the codification of ethical and moral theories into the AI infrastructure will have to be translated into rigid rules. For instance, this may look as follows:

A Norm is a Method entity that describes a set of rules and methods governing behavior expected for norm-aware agents. Norm types are derived from respective ethical theories and are possibly influenced by agent social contexts. An ethical theory is a systematization of concepts specifying or recommending aspects of morally correct behavior based on philosophical values and the characterization of right and wrong conduct. For norm aware agents, normative ethical theory is concerned with the practical means of determining a moral course of action.

```
(forall (n) (if (Norm n) (ERAS-TLO:Method n)))
(forall (t) (if (EthicalTheory t) (ERAS-TLO:Method t)))
(forall (n) (if (Norm n)
  (exists (t s)
    (and (EthicalTheory t)
      (SocialCollection s)
      (specifies_norm_modality t n)
      (is_prescribed_by n t)
      (influences_norm_applicability s n))))))
```


Figure 4: Operationalisation of ethical and moral theories

From the IEEE 7007 standard, p. 25

This approach seems to bypass the tricky question of whether this can be done, as the language of normative principles and values is very different from highly formalised language needed for machine readability ones⁶. In a well-known work on machine ethics (Allen and Wallach 2009), the authors proposed the idea of full moral agency for machines, but they later backtracked and argued the need to pay more attention to the practices and environments in which machines are developed and used. Experiments have also been carried out to implement simple ethical rules in robots (Vanderelst and Winfield 2018), concluding that ethics should not be built into machines. The decisive fact however is the *ethical simplicity* of the experiment: whereas highly sophisticated in technical terms, the experiment is still very far away from actual implementation in complex, unstructured environments, or from anything approaching the complexity of a real-world moral dilemma. It is highly dubitable, therefore, if this approach can be implemented in the sense of rendering machines as full moral agents. It may however serve other purposes, such as mobilising the engineering community by assigning to it its own proper engineering approach to ethics.

In the next two design articulations, we describe proponents of design that regard such limitations as fundamental, and therefore direct attention to the human designers, creators, and operators of intelligent and 'autonomous' digital systems.

⁶ As stated by one expert in human-computer interactions: There is a difference between the moral reasoning linked to human rights and the attempt of solving an engineering problem, which is technically and mathematically specified (cited from: Rommetveit and Van Dijk 2022).

5.2.3 Educating the engineers

We have traced strong commitments, amongst policy makers and people implicated in AI ethics, for more human-centric approaches to AI ethics (AI-HLEG 2019), including in our literature review and amongst our interviewees. Most iterations of this commitment do not take the routes described above. Rather, they are human-centric, in the sense of focusing standards on the behaviours of human creators, designers and operators of AI systems. As stated by two interviewees, both with a strong foothold in philosophy:

“So, my own view is we should not be trying to have more ethical technology, we should be trying to normalize and help people learn about processes that will have more ethical results” (philosopher A).

“what’s really grounding my current projects ... it’s really human wisdom about machines, not wisdom in machines, although I think the two issues are not completely independent” (philosopher B).

This realisation comes in part from thinking about limitations to what both humans and machines can do, and from a general scepticism about anything approaching human-like artificial intelligence (“general AI”). Philosopher B described this as a learning process through which he came to focus less on the machines, and more on their socio-technical context and surrounding environments. It was described as more realistic, and (critically) contrasted with science fiction-like scenarios and transhumanist imaginations, which nevertheless have strong impacts on public discourse:

“I think people immediately want to jump to Bostrom-like scenarios, which say what if the AI decides that making paperclips is the-, you know, it’s like no, that’s not the issue here” (philosopher B).

Against such speculative positions on ethics, this philosopher claimed a need to focus on more everyday mundane tasks, and the consequences they may have on people and everyday relations. Here, the threat perception and “the problem to be addressed” is more directed towards a thousand mundane operations and technologies, as this is where most impacts of AI will be, and are being, experienced. This problem was associated to the ways in which engineers and technologists are educated to not be aware of a thousand ethical decisions made during system's development, design, and implementation:

“They’re saying this is what matters in the world, this is the thing we want our algorithm to be good at, and that is to say that some things are more valuable than others. And it’s fine for them to do that, you have to make value choices in the process of design. The question then becomes which value choices, and now most recently where my work has gone to is how do we help computer scientists and technologists and roboticists, how do we help them to make those decisions in an intelligent way. They’re going to have to make these ethical choices, these value-based choices, they have to do that in order to build the technology, so how do we help them do it better” (philosopher A).

Hence, the need to teach ethics to engineers, and to include this in a design process in which more and better awareness of ethical issues can become part of engineers' everyday work tasks. This position makes good sense, as it addresses a *sine qua non* for the implementation of systems of all kinds, i.e., the engineers and software developers. However, it may also have come from a close

vicinity of practices: it is after all much easier to move into the engineering department at your university, than into Google or other large AI-developing companies. For instance, the firing of Google ethicist Timnit Gibré was specifically mentioned as an example of such alienation and lack of agency relating to large companies. Yet, if you can influence engineers to think more ethically, they may bring this skill even into large powerful companies at later stages, and so this is one possible way of circumventing a lack of influence on main societal institutions and corporations.

Arguably, this position held stronger sway with our US respondents than the European ones. This was not necessarily due to any strong difference in opinion, but rather to differences of culture, economy, and institutional arrangements. One (philosopher B) described the US environment as 'Wild West', another (philosopher A) described a highly fragmented environment with little or no coordination across actors, institutions, and sectors. The argument was that, whereas there is great emphasis and urgency underpinning efforts to integrate ethics, AI and design, there is no concerted movement or organisation to take care of and coordinate such efforts, at least not in the US.

The perception was also prominent that these things are, in some ways, handled in better ways in Europe. Both philosophers (A and B) were highly aware that this approach, focusing more on what is going on in education, is insufficient, as significant developments take place in privatised centres of power. Here, standards-based solutions may hold some promise, as they (arguably) involve a greater set of actors (stakeholders), including private ones. Yet, these informants were sceptical of such efforts:

“I guess I’ve just seen enough of these kinds of efforts, that they take 20 years and they end up with something that’s not terribly useful. We need things right now, so let’s put at least some kind of tools into people’s hands so that they can start to make real progress now” (philosopher A).

Philosopher B referred to Europe, and European experiences with 'having a multiplicity of viewpoints represented', through user involvement and public engagements, but also more public regulation, amongst them lately “multi-stakeholders” included in standardisation processes. Whereas this was partially explained by a lack of familiarity with those (regulatory, European) settings, the argument was also coupled to the kinds of expertise required for properly training and transmitting ethical skill and sensibility. He referenced experiences from engineering, computer, and business ethics, where (gradually) teaching had been taken over by non-philosophers, and “increasingly not by people who have been trained in philosophy departments”. This pointed to another boundary drawn around this articulation: it certainly came nowhere near the ivory tower approach in which ethical principles would be imposed top-down, which was also strongly criticised. This pointed to a difficulty, and relative novelty, within the community of academic philosophers and ethicists: on the one hand, ivory-tower philosophy is not sufficient; on the other, non-philosophers may not be capable of transmitting the moral and ethical message. Thus, the contents that enter into the standards may end up quite empty, at least in expert ethical terms.

5.2.4 Educating the stakeholders

A next set of actors comes close to the previous design articulation by sharing many of the same concerns: the potentially harmful and de-humanizing role of AI technologies on human relationships, and their threats to human dignity and autonomy. Also, these informants articulate the means of

addressing such threats through human-centric means focused on the human designers, operators, and users rather than the machines themselves:

“My opinion is that ethics is something that is proper to human beings, maybe some animals, but that’s disputable, but to human beings. And ethics is a reflection, it’s not something that you can really automate” (engineer C).

Perhaps because these were closer to European governance structures, and coming out of engineering and robotics, they did not however articulate the same scepticism towards standards and regulations. Indeed, robo-ethics has been an established part of European innovation and governance since the early 2000s (Veruggio 2006, Rommetveit et al. 2020). Our informants described their encounters with AI ethics therefore as gradually emerging out of these developments, and as closely related to standards and regulations:

“I mean there are lots of ethical aspects to standards. One which I didn’t realise until I got heavily involved about ten or twelve years ago when I started to work in standards” (engineer A).

All referred to maturing technological capabilities, initially in robotics then gradually also encompassing AI and AI-like technologies and networks, through which machines take on more human-like, simple decision-making capabilities. This triggered ethical reflection and brought them into various ethics and governance boards and fora.

The description of a complex and unstructured technological and regulatory environment is also shared with the informants of the previous section. Much of this resides in the technology itself, which is much more distributed, networked and privatised than for instance bioethics regulatory efforts:

“the body is kind of a natural safe for the actual DNA, and we (won’t have) [0:13:46] the equivalent for the virtual DNA. So, this is the difference the way I see it. And many people, they distribute their virtual DNA without being aware (engineer B).

This ubiquitous nature of data and information (“digital DNA”) is one reason why efforts to tackle ethical problems should be addressed at infrastructural levels, as these are extremely encompassing and indeed in many cases the main enablers for the global spread of data and (autonomous) computation:

“Standards are a kind of invisible infrastructure of the modern world. Everything around us. You’ve only got to look around your room to see standards in everything. The quality of the mug that I’m drinking out. Obviously, the laptop, the Wi-Fi, the fact that we can speak to each other like this. None of that wouldn’t happen without standards” (engineer A).

Our engineering informants were not all located in Europe, but were closely aligned to various European governance initiatives, and to the IEEE. They described an evolving regulatory landscape, beginning with efforts to regulate robotics. As already mentioned, many such initiatives were traced back to the early 2000s, but it would take almost 20 years for many of them to come to fruition, institutionally speaking:

“Anyway, so we started this initiative, the launch was in April 2016. And the mission of this initiative that I was chairing, still chairing but it’s going to be probably ending soon now, in 2016 was to raise awareness about ethical issues related to AI” (engineer C).

This quote refers to the IEEE Global Initiative on Ethics of Autonomous and Intelligent Systems, whose main outcome eventually became the *Ethically Aligned Design*, a written textual document elaborated in a bottom-up way by engineers, ethicists, and other 'stakeholders' (IEEE 2016, 2019), with the latest version (of three) being officially adopted by the IEEE board. The drafting process of the text took close to five years and was conceived as bottom-up process open to anybody with an interest. This initiative fed into the IEEE 7000 standards series, with at least a dozen different expert groups engaged in various topics dedicated to ethical alignment. As stated, most of these are not machine-centric but rather targeted at the human operators. Whereas engineers remain important, at this point much larger groups (“stakeholders”) come into view, as standards require commitment from groups as various as government regulators, business corporations, technology developers and vendors, and (to some extent) civil society. Processes of standardisation may also be linked to more downstream initiatives, such as certification schemes (based on the standards), and to efforts to “educate the public”, although how that is supposed to happen was not clear from our interviews (nor from the document study).

Finally, the work of the AIH-LEG expert group in many ways superseded and built on this work of standardisation:

“In 2018 the European Commission has wanted to build their AI plan, every country was doing this of course, you know why, and the Commission to create its own AI plan put together this high-level expert group of 52 members. And I applied and I was selected, so this is how IEEE and the high-level expert group in a way conflated together. And we produced as you know the ethics guidelines and the policy recommendations as well within the high-level expert group.”

There is therefore a history to be told here, about the emergence of this articulation: it starts with early (European) robo-ethics initiatives (Veruggio 2006), passes through the IEEE Ethically Aligned Design, then goes onto the IEEE 7000 series, and culminates (for now) with the AI High Level Expert Group.

5.2.5 AI transformation?

Our fifth and final design articulation is possibly more radical than the previous four, insofar as it seems to take the mediation of “ethics” with AI more seriously. It does so by blurring the distinctions between human and artificial intelligence, yet such blurring may take place in very different ways and based on highly differing accounts of both human and technological agency. There are two versions here, one that believes in “strong AI”, that is a general AI, both as threat and as possibility. We have seen that this possibility is largely rejected, at least by the previous two articulations; not as in principle impossible, but rather as unattainable based on the present state of art. One case in point was articulated as follows, by an engineer that works for a well-known civil society organization:

“I would say it’s the social implications of the prospects of the technology, because once we get past a certain level there are implications that ... you know, it’s pretty clear that things would change qualitatively, and that society is just not prepared for that” (interviewee CSO).

Next, there is a “weak AI” version, one that does not believe in a radically transformative potential, at least not in the sense conveyed by the previous informant: *“I don’t think general AI is a very sensible or a well-theorized concept”* (engineer D). This informant works for an organization that carries out fundamental research into “intelligence” in its various aspects, nevertheless, finds the potentials of merging human and machine intelligence:

“We found ourselves more interested in the capacity of AI to foster, support human morality, largely seeing it as a conflict between what’s sometimes called the paradox of automation, which is as you use a tool you get less good at doing things without it. So, to the extent that AI could support human morality, it might also tend to supplant moral decision making. So, the question that we were focusing on, continue to focus on really, is how AI tools, modern technological tools can strengthen our human capacities rather than replace them” (engineer D).

As an example, a robot or an AI could be used in therapeutic situations, to support therapists in work considered repetitive and tedious. Or an AI could be used to sift through large amounts of (big) data on a certain moral dilemma (he mentions kidney transplants), to come up with alternative suggestions not immediately visible to human decision makers operating through an ordinary qualitative understanding of the problem at hand. This articulation, then, is similar to the “strong AI” version in that it considers moral and technological change simultaneously. However, it is much more sceptical (or: scientifically experimental) on behalf of what AI can deliver.

5.3. Discussion and conclusion

The five AI design articulations demonstrate in and by themselves moral, or techno-moral change: the introduction of morality and ethics to the world of standards and engineering is shifting the meaning of morality and ethics. On the standard account (“ethics rules”) the philosophers and ethicists are still in charge, and the question remains how to articulate the right reasons and best arguments. However, this is only one out of five articulations: the next one, where the engineers are taking the driver’s seat, poses decisive limitations on the articulation of ethics. First, ethics is delimited to (mainly) rules-based accounts (deontology and utilitarianism), with a possible minor exception for virtue ethics (where ‘morality’ emerges in a somewhat more bottom-up fashion, drawing on machine learning techniques. Articulation number 3 may be seen as taking us back to a more classical, human-centric, notion of engineering ethics, as it becomes a matter for the ethicists (or similar) to educate the designers and programmers of AIs, preferably in engineering school. Whereas similar in philosophical orientation (i.e., pragmatism), articulation number 4 moves further into the landscape of standards, although seeing them more as foci for human, organizational, business and engineering efforts. Yet, the meaning of a “right” or a moral principle can here be expected (and observed) to be shifting towards meanings accessible to all, not any longer the exclusive property of ethicists. Articulation number 5 moves even further from a classical understanding of ethics, as here it becomes a matter for human and machine intelligence as a joint, possibly enhanced, enterprise.

None of this however implies, by necessity, actual socio-technical change: ethics is “soft law” and may not come with hard effects although that has certainly been argued with force (Tallacchini 2009). Yet, what it does signify, is an increasing emphasis on (digital, AI) infrastructures as centres for governance: it signifies therefore a partial movement out of traditional institutions (governance), or rather their possible extension and merger with digital infrastructures as increasingly central to several important and critical functions. The main sites of this shift are the standards organizations and committees. This shift can be seen in law (a more reliable indicator than ethics due to its important societal and

regulatory function), and in increased emphasis on (digital) infrastructures in science and technology studies, data studies and governance studies. This is sufficient for outlining a “theory of change” in the Super-MORRI project: prior to the emergence of machine ethics and ethical standards such as the IEEE 7007, “ethics” was always human-centric in the specific sense of targeting the professional (human being) making or using a technological artefact.

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6. Public value research careers

Richard Woolley

6.1. How do public value research careers make a difference to the science-society gap?

Research careers can be understood as a specific social structure that mediates between science and society. As Jochen Gläser (2001: 699) described:

“Research careers link individuals and institutions and they link social structures with knowledge production...careers provide a channel for societal influences on knowledge production...one of the phenomena that mediate between the scientific and non-scientific social structures, on the one hand, and knowledge production, on the other hand”.

As a mediating structure, research careers should reflect both the professional demands of the scientific community in which it lived as a working life, and the values and expectations of the broader society in which it is embedded. In the case of public funded science, responsibility exists not just to perform professional tasks to the best standard possible, but to uphold and reflect the values of that society and polity which has designated science as a priority area for investment, in the interests of collective well-being and quality of life. While the differentiation of society into social fields, such as science, inevitably leads to the institutionalisation of norms of behaviour that are specific to that field, in liberal and social democratic societies an expectation endures that such context specific characteristics remain congruent with those of the society as a whole. Yet, in the everyday working life of a research scientist how are such anchoring „public values’ (Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011) that tie science and society together maintained and enriched? How easy is it for the challenges, trials, and the structure of ubiquitous evaluation that characterises scientific work life to become all-consuming and self-referential, challenging researchers’ perseverance and ethical propriety? Public value research careers are a reflection on how the working life of research scientists can be shaped by institutional conditions and disciplinary practice norms that do not only face inward on the goal of scientific discovery and knowledge production but are also open to a broader societal panorama in which the purpose and value of scientific work is ultimately located.

From a theoretical perspective, research careers enter the structure and agency problem in sociology. To what extent are research careers the product of accumulated patterns of individual behaviour or the products of a set of institutional conditions that shape how research careers are performed? From the perspective of a “public value” approach to research careers we can consider that careers are produced through the interaction between scientists’ epistemic activities on the one side and societal forces on the other, particularly the institutional conditions which govern scientific knowledge production, but also, crucially, those broader non-scientific institutions, structures, and public expectations that characterise the social world.

The vast majority of studies of research careers investigate the interrelationships between the specific social and intellectual organisation of scientific fields and disciplines (Bourdieu 1975; Whitley 2000) and the varying institutional conditions that characterise the national research systems in which these activities take place. The governance of research is dominated by national investments in universities, research performing organisations, infrastructure, and funding support (Whitley et al. 2010). Epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina 1999) are distributed networks that are increasingly global in scope,

connecting scientists using similar methods and working on common or connected problems in contexts with highly varied levels of available resources and rewards.

The public value approach to research careers also understands them to be produced in the interplay between science and society, but with an emphasis on how non-scientific societal institutions and structures shape scientific careers. Only a relatively small discussion has occurred in the scholarly literature regarding the interconnections between non-scientific social institutions and structures and knowledge production. This discussion has three main threads: science as reproducing social stratification; science as situated in socio-political contexts; and science as a professional field in need of reform or realignment.

First, Bourdieu studied the academic field as an example of social reproduction. He highlighted how the academic field was reproduced through its domination by a particular class of French society. The homogeneity of the French scientific profession as a field occupied by individuals endowed with the range of social and educational capitals that made them a „natural’ fit for the academic world (Bourdieu 1988) is a situation that is replicated around the world. The consequences of this historic domination of the scientific field by a sub-population that does not reflect the broader socio-economic and cultural composition of society is thought to have consequences for knowledge production. These include a reduction in the scope of research topics and questions that are considered important in scientific communities. For example, the historical focus of health research in developed countries on topics that concern men reflects the persistent underrepresentation of women in science and in positions of leadership in scientific communities (EC 2021). Recent initiatives to improve the “equity, diversity and inclusion’ (EDI) of the scientific workforce and academia reflect an acknowledgement of this phenomenon of the lack of correspondence between the population structure of society and the make-up of the scientific workforce (UKRI 2022; Wellcome Trust 2021).

The second way in which non-scientific social structures are considered in relation to knowledge production is in relation to the importance of broad socio-political factors in the attractiveness of national science systems. Availability of and access to free public health care, including for family members, free public education for children, and labour market access for a spouse or partner are important in decisions to move to a national scientific system to work (Gläser 2004). Religious freedom and relatively low levels of institutional and personal racism and discrimination, and the right to retain dual or multiple citizenships, can also be considered important non-scientific factors that affect immigration decisions. Finally, societies with relatively low levels of corruption and crime, and relatively open and transparent systems of public administration also have an advantage in recruiting researchers. In short, societies that embody a range of positive “public values” (Bozeman and Sarewitz 2011) in their social, economic, and political institutions, are more attractive destinations for migrants, including relatively high-value and high-earning professionals such as scientists.

Third and most important for the idea of public value research careers, non-scientific societal institutions and knowledge production are increasingly connected through discussions of the need to reform or re-orient science. On the one hand, the framing of science and technology as the engine of economic growth and development placed increased demands on public funded researchers and research organisations to (co-)produce knowledge with social utility (Gibbons et al. 1994). The emergence and institutionalisation of whole of society responses to what are variously known as global or societal grand challenges has also had significant effects on the institutional conditions governing science and by extension the epistemic decisions of scientists. Scientists’ research agendas in virtually all fields are being shaped by the increasing emphasis on mission-oriented funding that is

designed to “direct” a greater proportion of public funded research toward topics and problems prioritised by socio-political actors and citizens. The institutionalisation of the Sustainable Development Goals monitoring framework provides a governance mechanism by which science generally, and research performing organisations in particular, can be assessed in terms of responsiveness and contribution to these societal demands.

On the other hand, there has been a rising level of public concern about the conduct and outcomes of research and innovation. Historically citizens have tended to regard science as a vocation that has integrity and legitimacy and scientists as worthy of public trust. However, the failure of research culture to evolve in ways that are aligned with broader social values and expectations can undermine this historical status. Scientific research and academia have been beset by a wide range of cultural failures, including research fraud, ethical misconduct, the institutionalisation of questionable research practices (QRPs) in many disciplines (Vitae 2020), along with socially unacceptable behaviour in relation to bullying, the exploitation of junior colleagues, and sexual harassment (UKRI 2020). The emergence of values-based initiatives within science governance, such as responsible research and innovation (RRI) (Owen et al 2012) and EDI movements, reflect evolution in non-scientific societal institutions that can be expected to shape the scientific field over time.

In summary, PVRC thus represents a starting point for a systematic consideration of how research careers can be concerned with not just knowledge production and the hierarchical intricacies of scientific communities, but also be alive and open to evolution in societal demands and public expectations, broadly understood. PVRC is thus concerned with how research careers can contribute not just to the production of new knowledge, but to the institutionalisation and the reinforcement of those public values on which social structures as a whole are based.

6.2. Opportunities and shortcomings in reforming recognition and rewards

To answer this succinctly, the opportunity presented by reform of systems of reward and recognition for researchers is to provide incentives and rewards for a more expansive range of contributions to knowledge production, to science, and to society more generally. The potential shortcoming in this endeavour is that reforms lack a framework or rationale for anchoring recognition also in non-scientific societal institutions and expectations. The risk then is that reform simply reflects specific “internal” concerns that are most pressing to scientific communities in the short-term, stopping short of a reform that opens research careers to the influence of non-scientific societal institutions in the medium and longer term.

Critics of this line of thinking would argue that one of the current major problems with science is that it is already too open to societal influence, particularly the “neo-liberal” co-opting of research and innovation to the objectives of multinational corporations and “platform capitalism” (Mirowski 2018). This is undoubtedly a legitimate concern, however one of the advantages of taking a public values approach to the governance of science and the scripting of research careers is that different activities can be weighed and assessed in context and translated into recognition and rewards based on contributions to public values. Rather than a relatively universalist approach such as that constructed by Merton (1973), which treats science as ultimately governed by a narrow set of intrinsic values, a public values approach can be anchored in both scientific practice and social institutions and be more versatile and sensitive to heterogeneity in contexts of knowledge production and in research careers.

Linking research practices to public values can help move beyond assessments that focus predominantly on narrow definitions of productivity (publications) and impact (citations) that overly value rewarding the products of research over the processes. A reformed research assessment would not just recognise and reward what science was done, but *how* it was done. Such an assessment framework should strengthen incentives for doing science in a way that is aligned with and reinforces public values. Such an assessment would provide incentives and rewards for the kinds of example practices included in Table 4. These incentives and rewards would need to be built around expectations about research practices that are adjusted for career stage and avoid one-size-fits-all approach. Public value contributions could thus be assessed at a scale and intensity relevant to the career stage and achievements relative to opportunities of individual researchers, and to the collective actions and institutional initiatives of research groups, for example. Table 4 summarizes how attributes of research careers can be linked to a framework of public values.

Table 4: Research career attributes and public values

Attribute: Invent, adopt, train,	Public value practice examples	Public value mechanism	Public values
Open Science practices	FAIR data, open-source tools, shared in scientific community and beyond Rapid data sharing & dissemination Documentation of methods	Efficient knowledge production, enhanced inclusion of stakeholders Accelerated responsiveness to societal challenges Reproducibility of results	Efficiency Transparency
Research Integrity practices	External ethics approval acquired Research data management plan Pre-registration of research approach	Assessment of potential harm Process for protection of personal information Reduction in questionable research practices (QRPs)	Integrity Privacy Fairness
Public Engagement practices	Societal relevance of research results Societal relevance of research outcomes	Co-creation of research agendas Co-production of knowledge	Legitimacy Efficacy
EDI practices	Elimination of discrimination or bias in training, hiring and promotion	Diversity and gender balance in the workplace	Equality Fairness
Gender content analysis	Consideration and integration of gender issues in the design of research	Research outcomes that address both women and men	Equality Fairness Legitimacy

(Source: Own contribution by the author)

In Table 4, an attribute refers to an aspect of research practice that can be considered to contribute to enhancing the public value of a researchers' work and career. The mechanism that features in each row relates to how the specific practices included can be considered to generate public value, with the specific public values that might be expected to be enhanced through the operation of this mechanism appears in the column to the right.

Recent approaches to research assessment reform, most prominently the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), whilst not directly anchoring reform in the rewarding of contribution to public values, attempt to balance traditional assessment criteria of quality and impact with criteria of diversity, inclusiveness, and collaboration. The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (2022) on which CoARA's activities are based, defines its purpose as to „broaden recognition of the diverse practices, activities, and careers in research, considering the specific nature of research disciplines and other research endeavours' (p.4). An impressive wish list of activities that could foreseeably be deserving of recognition and reward within science is compiled. As the attributes in Table 4 highlight, many of the types of tasks and activities that reformed research assessment seeks to incorporate do line up with fundamental public values.

Systematizing and categorising the public value contributions of research activities to anchor research reform more thoroughly in both scientific and societal institutions does not seem a particularly complicated challenge. However, there are two main reasons why such an approach could benefit research assessment reform in the longer term. The first of these is to reassure researchers and scientific communities that research assessment reform need not be regarded as an attack on research freedom or as a distraction or burden on scientific discovery processes. Second, such an approach can help make explicit that public values may be in tension or conflict in specific contexts of knowledge production, necessitating a process of evaluation and prioritisation of actions that can be grounded in a coherent rationale.

The first point refers to the fact that researchers tend to react in a defensive or antagonistic way to any policy or other initiatives that they perceive could infringe on academic freedom. Policies that can be seen as demands that scientists “do more” or “do things differently” can be viewed as creating additional burdens that distract from the essential work of scientific discovery. Scientists' research agendas are built around those disciplinary specific tasks that are “epistemically necessary”, all those elements of their work and role set that are associated with moving the frontier of knowledge and their own “cognitive career” (Laudel and Gläser 2015) forward. New demands are likely to elicit a response in the organisation of disciplines to “buffer” the scientific division of labour to protect epistemically necessary tasks and researchers' availability of time and resources to focus on those tasks.

The response to increased demands that can currently be observed in many fields is the construction of roles sets that protect epistemic necessary tasks, activities and functions from unnecessary interference or dilution. The emergence of such role sets, stretches the scientific division of labour, creating new positions that have a partial or non-existent dedication to epistemically necessary tasks, but rather are engaged primarily in activities such as project, stakeholder, or research data management. Researchers engaged in these role sets may find themselves excluded from the main currency of academic evaluations, authorship of scientific articles, with negative consequences for the progress of their research career. Indeed, such role sets are not recognised or effectively supported by institutional conditions in science systems.

Roles that are not dedicated to epistemically necessary tasks thus struggle for recognition. In the context of research assessment reform, adding additional activities and tasks to assessment protocols seems of somewhat limited value. Peer review processes in science will continue to privilege epistemic necessity in evaluating the worth of a scientist's contributions. Roles that are more directly involved in responding to non-scientific societal structures, such as managing liaisons with patient organisations, will struggle to compete for recognition in such contexts. An approach to research

assessment reform that simply adds more tasks and activities as eligible for consideration in evaluation processes risks maintaining a hierarchy between those tasks perceived as epistemically necessary and the everything else. If only epistemically necessary tasks are reward with authorships of papers and patents, then this essential divide can remain fundamentally unchanged.

A public value perspective re-frames the question of what is worthy of recognition and reward beyond lists of tasks to the relevant public values to which any specific research should contribute and reinforce. To use an example, advances in genetic diagnosis in rare diseases rely on collaboration with patient organisations for bio-samples. The work of discovery reported in a scientific journal may reflect a public value of „progress’. However, this work of discovery should not be considered independently of the value of “privacy” embedded in work of patient and patient organisation liaison and collaboration that ensured the safety and integrity of processes of using personal information and bio-samples that made the epistemically necessary work ethically and scientifically possible. Rather, a public values approach requires that positive evaluation of such research is dependent on contributions to a range of public values, to ensure that not just research results but all processes integral to their production are also integral to research assessment.

The second point refers to the idea that a public values approach can help make explicit the tensions that can emerge between public values in different contexts of knowledge production. This can support reflection on research objectives and designs that reach beyond a singular focus on the successful execution of epistemically necessary tasks. An example can be described using the adoption of Open Science (OS) research practices. Resistance to adopting OS practices can come from scientists that argue that if OS is epistemically necessary, then a scientific discipline or specialization will already be doing it. Researchers may understand any expectations that they view as not epistemically necessary as undermining or interfering with their capacity to further their cognitive contributions to knowledge in their field, making their research agenda needlessly uncompetitive („it will be done anyway’). In such circumstances a researcher may change their research agenda, change their organisational context to a more laissez-faire environment, or they may expand the division of labour to buffer their time focusing on epistemically necessary tasks by hiring someone to deal with what are perceived as additional OS tasks (data management plans and procedures, metadata preparation, ontologies, etc.). It is this expansion of the division of labour that leads to the emergence of positions and role sets in research that are not supported by traditional academic evaluation systems.

Nevertheless, as we can observe, Open Science Communities (OSCs) (Armeni et al. 2021) are emerging within scientific disciplines precisely with the intention to transform disciplinary norms in the interests of promoting public values such as transparency and efficiency of resource use at a collective or systemic level, over „traditional’ values of competition and primacy. These OSCs are found to be thriving particularly in contexts where there is organisational policy and strategic support for advancing OS, again for normative reasons associated with the integrity and accountability of public organisations that equate to a promulgation of broader public values in scholarship (Armeni et al. 2021).

A continuum can be expected along which aspects of OS are integrated into research agendas and designs. Partial adoption of OS philosophies and practices can be expected. Workflows, role sets and the division of labour can configure and institutionalise OS in different ways in specific contexts of knowledge production. There may be reasons that are separate from epistemic necessity that motivate researchers to adopt OS in some ways: to satisfy funders; to satisfy organisational policy „pressure’; to unify and simplify training processes; or to improve accountability for resource use, for

example. There may also be reasons that are integral to epistemic necessity that limit the integration of OS in disciplinary knowledge production practices. For example, in much qualitative social sciences work ensuring the anonymity of participants in data collection methods such as interviews is paramount. Here the public value „privacy’ should be prioritised over „transparency’. In some biochemistry or virology research fields the public value „safety’ should be the highest priority. Anchoring research assessment in public values can thus provide a framework for recognising and rewarding researchers also for the reflexivity and judgement they exercise in balancing tensions between public values, between privacy and transparency for example, of for decisions they make to shift their research agendas due to ethical or safety issues that concern the greater public good. This contextual sensitivity of a public values approach to research careers and to the reform of research assessment shares some characteristics with the perspective of post normal science which has already described how values, politics, and epistemic practices are differently configured in diverse contexts of knowledge production and utilisation (Ravetz and Functowicz). PVRC thus argues assessment practices should not be governed by de-contextualised assessments of productivity that reward only a limited set of outputs recording the performance of epistemically necessary tasks and activities. Rather, how tasks were done, how vital tasks that are not epistemically necessary were integrated, and how all these can be assessed to have contributed to, and reinforced, a range of public values, should all be fundamental to research evaluation.

Incentives for researchers and scientific communities should then be a consequence of a consistent orientation toward and imbuing of the public values that are thought to matter in publicly funded science organisations and institutions. There should be a recognition of the plurality of ways in which contributions can be made to those values throughout a research career. Some contributions may be relatively context dependent and situated in and for society, while others may be relatively abstract and generalised epistemic contributions that mainly serve the academic community. What characterises a public value research career approach or framework would be the consistency of the public values that orient diverse scientific occupational role sets and flexibility and versatility to recognise and reward contributions in those terms. Public value research careers would integrate these values in the entirety of the research career, from undergraduate and graduate education and doctoral training onward.

6.3. Responsibility in Career assessment, Career stage and Open Science

Empirical data from the RESU is being analysed for the PVRC project and preliminary results are share below in Table 5 and Table Table 6These data have to date been used to compare perceptions of RRI, and motivations and practices of researchers in relation to Public Engagement and Open Science. Entering these preliminary analyses, it was anticipated that there would be a higher level of take-up or responsible practices among early career researchers (R1 and R2) than amongst senior researchers (R4). However, preliminary results suggest that this is far from a uniform outcome and that close attention will need to be paid to identifying exactly where career stage differences can be clearly discerned. The dimensions of Gender Equality and Ethics have not yet been analysed by career stage.

Table 5: Researchers’ cooperation with societal stakeholder, by career stage

Stakeholder type	R1	R2	R3	R4	TOTAL

Citizens	45,8%	54,1%	58,7%	64,5%	57,3%
Government	52,6%	63,1%	69,6%	79,5%	68,5%
Firms	36,6%	45,1%	52,2%	59,9%	50,4%
NGOs	54,2%	57,1%	64,1%	69,9%	62,7%
CSOs	34,6%	37,4%	37,4%	43,8%	38,8%
Average all stakeholders	44,8%	51,4%	56,4%	63,5%	

Table 6: Researchers' participation in Open Science practices, by career stage

Open science practice	R1	R2	R3	R4	TOTAL
Pre-registered studies or shared in other ways	48,6%	48,8%	42,5%	51,9%	47,5%
Considered how to make data and analysis openly available in the planning phase of the project	66,0%	70,7%	68,9%	74,6%	70,5%
Published working papers that are freely accessible	73,0%	76,2%	80,2%	83,5%	79,2%
Shared data in open repositories	58,3%	68,0%	69,9%	75,3%	69,3%
Published Open Access	85,7%	92,5%	92,7%	95,7%	92,4%
Improved data infrastructures to ease the use of data	43,2%	47,5%	45,8%	52,3%	47,6%
Made data available for free to other researchers after it was requested	64,4%	72,1%	72,3%	79,3%	73,0%
Average all open science practices	62,7%	68,0%	67,5%	73,2%	

Secondary data relevant to PVRC has been gathered from the MORE surveys. Results from the most recent MORE4 survey showed that on average 19% of PhD students in EU27 countries „received training in Open Science approaches (publishing in open access journals, sharing research data, participating in citizen science events, etc.)’ (PPMI et al. 2019: 139-140). Countries with the highest proportion of PhDs receiving open science training included Romania (72%), Croatia (42%) and Sweden (37%). Countries reporting the lowest proportion of OS training included Germany (11%), the Netherlands and Spain (14%). No data are available for this question for other career stages in MORE 4.

Results from MORE4 also show that 83% of EU27 researchers published in, or sent articles for review to, open access journals. Countries reporting the highest rate of open access publishing included

Romania (96%), Latvia (94%) and Poland (91%). However, no significant differences were found between countries in terms of the share of researchers engaging in open access publishing activities. These results are being analysed by career stage as part of the PVRC project.

Overall, the case argues that more attention should be paid to the pathways through which researchers contribute to the institutionalisation and reinforcement of public values over the course of their careers. These contributions will vary by scientific disciplines and by career stages but can form a thread of continuity across the career trajectory. It seems evident that there is significant variation between the extent to which individual researchers may be motivated to contribute in ways that reinforce public value. The key point is that the „script’ of the average research career could shift, through changes in training processes and disciplinary norms, and in the levels and dimensions of institutional support for responsible research cultures and practices. This is the medium-term goal that imagines the typical research career of the future to be more open and connected to non-scientific societal institutions and expectations that is currently the case.

What the PVRC case teaches us about responsibility in research and innovation is that transformation of research careers requires multiple transformations in institutional settings, professional expectations and disciplinary norms and practices. As the initial data analysis (Appendix 1) suggest, the extent to which different aspects of responsibility are recognised by researchers at different stages of the career may vary considerably in relation to some aspects of ORRI, but less so in others. It will be necessary to build further knowledge about how career stage impacts on perceptions and practices related to responsibility in the future.

From a theoretical point of view, we should not think of this as simply a matter of „directed’ or „planned’ change, although this can be part of the story. Disciplinary norms and practices also transform due to the requirements of epistemic necessity and the cultural environment advanced by leaders in fields and organisations. The integration of responsible practices in research training is one essential element of shifting the script of research careers. Shaping early career researchers to adopt norms and practices that advance and reinforce public values is an achievable objective. However, it cannot be achieved without the support of senior researchers, mentors, and doctoral supervisors. Very senior scientists who have worked in a closed competitive model of science throughout long successful careers cannot be expected to switch to open science at the end of their careers – and resistance to both policy advocates and OSCs from senior researchers is well known and understood. However, senior researchers supporting (or at least not obstructing) the acquisition of OS skills and practices by junior researchers in their lab or department is an achievable objective, which could also be incentivised and supported institutionally.

A framework such as public values can thus orient the „scripting’ of research careers in subtle and incremental ways. If researchers who understand their careers as a journey that can contribute to a range of values held in esteem by society, beyond a twin focus on discovery and economic exploitation, become the norm, then the public value of research careers will be enriched, to the benefit of society and science.

6.4. Reflecting on the Impact and Benefits of Public Value Research Careers

PVRC is particularly relevant to aspects of open science, research integrity, public engagement, and gender equality. Public value research career attributes relevant to these dimensions are summarised in Table 4 above. The mechanisms by which these attributes contribute to deepening a range of public

values are also set out. Reform of research evaluation to recognise and reward these dimensions as contributing to the public value of research and innovation would shift research career scripts in the direction of more responsible cultures and practices along the lines of these RRI key areas.

The whole premise and rationale for PVRC is that the research career, as a social structure that mediates between science and society, could provide greater returns to public values than is currently the case. It follows that if research careers can, over the several decades of their trajectory, be more open to co-creation of research questions and co-production then there should be benefits to society. Similarly, if research careers more strongly integrate research integrity, then the results and outcomes of research are more likely to withstand public scrutiny and appear legitimate to citizens. Research careers that integrate open science practices which enhance the transparency and accountability of often resource intensive activities that rely on public funding seem to logically provide a benefit to democratic values.

Influencing the 'scripting' of research careers to integrate different types of responsible practices depends heavily on training and mentoring processes. While it may not be pragmatic for a late career research Professor to switch his own research practices to Open Science, for example, supporting financially and intellectually the taking up of appropriate OS practices by ECRs in their labs or institutes can be viewed as an also important contribution. The reform of evaluation systems to incentivise and reward such contributions is key to the shifting of disciplinary career scripts toward an enhanced contribution to and reinforcement of public values. While the most obvious areas of benefit from PVRC would seem to be social and democratic benefits, changes which improve (among other values) the transparency, legitimacy, and integrity of research seems likely to bring with it a profound benefit to scientific knowledge production. If research careers are also made more accessible and fairer for incoming cohorts of young scientists who more closely reflect the composition of the general population, then benefits to science in terms of more diverse research agendas, and to the economy in terms of research outcomes that are relevant to a broader cross-section of society, might also be assumed to emerge in the medium- to longer-term horizon.

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7. Transdisciplinary Research(funding)

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7.1. Introduction

Compared to its predecessors, the current and third generation of innovation policies can be differentiated by its focus on directing research towards addressing societal and environmental challenges in ways that change, or rather transform, underlying socio-technical systems (Schot & Steinmueller, 2018). In the past years, Transformative Innovation Policies (TIPs) have emerged as a key concept and model for policy experimentation following the characteristics of third-generation innovation policy⁷. Amongst other mechanisms of addressing complex socio-economic challenges, TIPs involve multi-stakeholder consultation and reflection about the desirable or undesirable directions in which research and innovation steer society. In other words, TIPs seek collaborative, reflexive, and experimental co-creation in the transformative processes of research and innovation to maximize outcomes for societal benefit.

More recently, the literature on TIPs has started to address the complex issue of evaluating TIPs (Molas-Gallart et al., 2021; Palavicino et al., 2023). In such a research context where experimental processes and multiple iterations with multistakeholder groups are desirable, Molas-Gallart et al. (2021) argue for the use of a formative approach to evaluation inspired by Luederitz et al. (2017). This entails that evaluators actively co-create the evaluation process with the relevant stakeholders and keep the process open to learning and reflexivity along the way.

With a formative evaluation approach, the implementation of a research program and its evaluation should go hand in hand. For the evaluation, administration and performance of research, TIPs provide a landscape for experimentation with research processes at multiple levels dealing with complex topics. For these reasons, this case study takes a research context where the characteristics of TIPs are present, and which targets the complex challenge of climate change. Within this context, this case study follows a formative evaluation of a 2019 call “Enabling Societal Transformation in the Face of Climate Change” (SOLSTICE) which was opened by a trans-national research effort called the Joint Programming Initiative on “Connecting Climate Knowledge for Europe”, otherwise referred to as JPI Climate (Council of the European Union, 2011).

The aim of the case study is to evaluate how characteristically TIPs-oriented aspects of transformative research were conceptualized and implemented through the JPI’s funding program. The study begins with background information on how the case came to be as well as the methodological approach taken. It then outlines the conceptual development of the SOLSTICE call focusing on the aspects that were most relevant to the transformative, TIPs-oriented aims of the call. This part of the case study follows the sequence of events from theoretical beginnings of the call, to coordinating with the trans-national funding bodies to arranging the evaluation and proposal selection. A major milestone for the evaluation team was the development of a first analysis of the SOLSTICE call, which was handed over to JPI before the mid-way evaluation of the projects. The study then concludes with the results of the midway evaluation which provides some indication of project level impact. However, because this study concludes before the projects are completed as well as because of resource constraints, this study focuses primarily on the policy and program level. The study then concludes with lessons

⁷ For a systematic review of TIPs literature see Haddad et al. (2022).

regarding the pathway towards benefits associated with the SOLSTICE case, namely what the case teaches us about transdisciplinary and public engagement, funding transformative research and attempting to direct funding and researcher practices in transformative ways.

7.2. Background and methodology

Following the formative evaluation approach proposed by Molas-Gallart et al. (2021) the authors sought concerted engagement with the program as the call and its funded projects unfolded, rather than acting as external evaluators. The aim was to engage in the evaluation process in a way that would allow the outcomes of the program, including the evaluation itself, to be more transformative. The authors of this case study approached JPI to suggest a mutual exchange. As members of the SuperMoRRI project, the authors wanted to study the development of the call from concept to project results which entailed access to materials, time, and willingness to co-create from JPI. In exchange, SuperMoRRI would provide the formative evaluation which was mutually beneficial because the SOLSTICE Call Secretariat had no third-party funding for an external evaluation of the call and projects (this was the responsibility of the national funding bodies on the project level).

The formative evaluation included two formal workshops between JPI and SuperMoRRI partners, the first in December 2021 and the second in May of 2022. More informally, many exchanges occurred over the course of the collaboration, resulting in primary data in the form of minutes of meetings, participation in critical stages of the call such as the Kick-Off meeting and Mid-way evaluation, formal written analysis, and input regarding qualitative questions for the project mid-way evaluation and reporting templates and questionnaires. In exchange for these inputs, the authors were given access to interviews with Lead Principal Investigators (LPIs) for the selected SOLSTICE projects, as well as interviews with policy makers who were instrumental in the realization of the call. At the time of writing in March 2023, the projects still have some months until the end of 2023 to finalize their projects, with some applying for extensions. However, within the frame of this case study, the formative evaluation concluded with the midway evaluation of the projects on November 16th, 2022.

In addition to the primary data produced by the formative evaluation, access was given to a variety of secondary data sources produced or commissioned by the JPI for their internal review processes. The authors were given access to research proposals, the evaluation grid used to assess the proposals, confidential documents such as minutes of preparatory meetings from the call design process. The evaluation team benefited from interview material with the funders, conducted and transcribed by a master's student who was working for the JPI at the time. The findings of this interview material were summarized and published in the public policy brief, "Ex post analysis of the SOLSTICE Call" (Göd et al., 2022). These materials were analysed in a qualitative manner, through mapping, coding, and systematic use of a Theory of Change model (Vogel, 2012).

A preliminary version of the ToC (Figure 5) was prepared and presented during a first workshop in December 2021 which included the Call Secretariate and the formative evaluation team.

SOLSTICE ToC

Figure 5: ToC of the transformative design of the SOLSTICE program

(Source: Own Contribution)

The ToC was intended as a framework to be further development and elaborated on together with the JPI. The diagram shows the core elements of the program from the theoretical assumptions of the call to activities of the call, outputs of the projects and outcomes defined as outputs which produce a systemic effect. The aim of the ToC diagram was to reflect these elements back onto the transformative aims to ensure alignment course correction.

During the first workshop, the main objective was to discuss the proposed ToC and agree upon how to think and evaluate transformative change. Evaluation of TIPs is still an emerging field of study, and there is debate about how to evaluate funding programs based on transformation.

Some of the questions raised were, *Is transformation one element of systemic change? What is the transformative part of the change? Is SOLSTICE about supporting pre-conditions for transformative change?* In addition to the lack of easily operable metrics as in other fields of evaluation, one workshop participant noted:

“The further you get away from a project, the less control you have over the projects and the more society starts to intervene. Tracking outcomes and impacts gets more difficult, also predicting where they are going and what they are doing. As you move away from projects it will become much more complicated to scale up and direct the outputs.”

Given the nascent scholarship, and the ambiguity surrounding what transformative aspects are, one participant argued that the interpretation of the call by SOLSTICE applicants is one way to develop a bottom-up ToC on the call level. The interpretations and research designs are themselves ToC’s of the transformative aspects of the call. This approach to a collective understanding of a ToC can be somewhat validated by the observation that the projects interpreted the call guidelines in a similar way.

7.3. SOLSTICE Call: Design and Development

7.3.1 Theoretical Background of SOLSTICE

The conceptual development underpinning the SOLSTICE funding program was grounded in work done in 2018 by a JPI Action Group, “Enabling Societal Transformations in the Face of Climate Change”. As stated on the website⁸, their objective is to “promote the Social Sciences and Humanities as key disciplines in the sustainable societal transformation in the context of climate change”. In 2019, the Action Group published a White Paper titled, “Operationalizing knowledge on and for societal transformations in the face of climate change” (West & Worliczek, 2019). This paper was a key driver of SOLSTICE becoming a funding program by serving as a theoretical starting point and set of recommendations for the eventual design. While the paper does not include an explicit ToC, it contained all necessary elements including a series of assumptions and a chain of anticipated results linking the characteristics of SOLSTICE to transformative outcomes for addressing climate change.

The primary recommendations of the paper were as follows. First, to stimulate Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) perspectives and leadership on the topic of climate change and through this, increase the likelihood of trans and interdisciplinary research practices. The call to action for the SSH community is stated as the “critical need to move beyond a focus on describing climate change challenges, towards devising effective societal solutions and actions...” (West & Worliczek, 2019, pg. 2). To meet these needs, the White Paper outlines specific thematic areas which are “particularly well-suited to be led by SSH researchers but that can attract wide interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary engagement”. This suggests that epistemically, the SSH community has the appropriate frameworks for asking transformative research questions. Furthermore, the quote suggests that these questions are also inviting to other discipline.

The assumption is that interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary will further research from knowledge production to catalysing change,

“...[transdisciplinarity] provides an opportunity for learning and reflexivity that can stimulate new methods and new paradigms for solving climate change issues, not just problematizing them”.

Relating this notion to the ToC, research is positioned as a mechanism of action such that funded research should not just describe or problematize climate change but help solve the climate challenge. In other words, this is the desired impact of SOLSTICE.

7.3.2 Selecting transformative topics

To identify specific SSH topics, the JPI Action Group conducted stakeholder consultations, a scoping process of previous JPI Climate calls, collected recommendations, reviewed the issues and agenda framework of Horizon 2020⁹, and referred to the JPI Climate Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (JPI Climate, 2016). The result was a comprehensive outline of the current SSH relevant research topics and knowledge gaps which were synthesized into five thematic prioritizations and two cross-cutting issues across these themes (cf. Table 5).

⁸ <https://jpi-climate.eu/programme/solstice/>

⁹ <https://wayback.archive-it.org/12090/20220124080607/https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/what-horizon-2020>

Table 7: Topics and Cross-Cutting issues identified in SOLCISTE White paper.

SOLCISTE relevant research topics and knowledge gaps	SOLCISTE cross-cutting issues
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance • Visions and scenarios • Social justice and participation • Sense making and cultural meaning • Transformative finance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politics of knowledge co-production • Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)

(Source: West & Worliczek, 2019)

While there is no explicit definition of transformation in the White Paper, these research topics were chosen because on the one hand they are SSH relevant topics, and the White Paper included the following assumption:

“SSH researchers perform a dual role in these knowledge and solution production processes. On the one hand, inclusion of SSH perspectives can help to bridge gaps between science, policy and practices and make research results more relevant and applicable. SSH researchers also provide critical perspectives and insights on power and other dynamics that are bound up in knowledge production processes and that influence the application of new knowledge and the distribution of societal benefits derived from it” (Driessen et al., 2013).

On the other hand, these topics were thought to include mechanisms that would steer the research towards transformative outcomes. For example, conducting research on visions and scenarios of climate change might lead to imagining and designing desirable visions and scenarios for transformative change.

In terms of relevance, SSH have epistemic expertise and disciplinary ownership over current knowledge gaps (knowledge-based needs). In terms of applicability, SSH can steer production of “effective societal solutions and actions” based on SSH’s ability to organize research more inclusively and justly with non-academic stakeholders due to their perspective on power dynamics. Taken as part of a ToC, both the knowledge and the application of the knowledge are given equal weight in terms of their contribution to transformation. This would mean that within the funding program and the research projects themselves, the researchers require support mechanisms for both practices. However, it is important to remember the White Paper was the first and conceptually ambitious phase of the eventual call. The process of further designing, developing, setting up and launching the call involved external factors and practical challenges which played a significant role in how the SOLSTICE unfolded.

7.3.3 Development into a call for funding

Following the White Paper, a workshop was organized to initiate a first draft of the call and the formative evaluation team was granted access to the minutes. This workshop was the beginning of a negotiation process amongst multiple actors and institutions about how the “pure” ideas presented in the White Paper could be translated into a funding program. Widely accepted was opening the application to all JPI countries and disciplines and by doing so, aim for interdisciplinarity on the one hand and alignment of different national funding strategies on the other.

The deviations from the White Paper to the workshop discussion included transdisciplinarity shifting from being described as critical for “help[ing] overcome disciplinary silos and science-society divides”

to “highly encouraged where appropriate”. Additionally, the five thematic prioritizations were reconfigured and narrowed into three (cf. Table 6).

Table 8: Topics and Cross-Cutting issues manifested in SOLCISTE Call

SOLCISTE relevant research topics and knowledge gaps – White Paper	SOLCISTE relevant research topics and knowledge gaps – Call for Applications
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governance • Visions and scenarios • Social justice and participation • Sense making and cultural meaning • Transformative finance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social justice and participation • Sense making and cultural meaning • Transformative finance

(Source: Own compilation)

In trying to align the topics and themes with the national priorities of the participating JPI countries, it was a challenge to identify shared needs while also avoiding competition with existing national funding. This presented the challenge of balancing desirable themes with potential overlaps with the pre-existing research policies of the national member states. Adding to this challenge was the aim of filling different gaps across different national policies, however these gaps were not so obvious considering the lack of common framework.

However, across almost all countries was a shared interest in promoting the SSH perspective and new combinations of disciplines including SSH as an innovative approach to climate research. This was seen as innovative because arts and humanities are often underrepresented disciplines in these fields. Although this was not explicitly linked to arts and humanities or SSH leadership, it was noted that funders in each member state want to move from knowledge to actionable research that has policy impact.

Another goal was to provide unusual combinations of disciplines an opportunity to collaborate which would otherwise not exist. To do this, the call needed to attract a wide range of disciplines. A mechanism for encouraging interdisciplinarity to compliment the thematic topics was devised in the form of three “lenses”. Proposal writers were to choose at least one of the following:

- 1) “Qualitative upscaling” meaning to look at concrete examples on a micro level and their transferability to a wider context,
- 2) “Normative framing” meaning to question the norms in the respective theme, and
- 3) “Structural approach” meaning to address the chosen topic through a systemic approach.

While the thematic topics are meant to attract SSH leadership to the calls, these lenses are intended to be more interdisciplinarity as well as more geared towards specific types of outcomes. The lenses provide added value through the SOLSTICE program by directing research toward solution-oriented knowledge outcomes and actions; examples that can be scaled, norms that can be questioned, and structures that can be made visible.

After circulation amongst the working group and national funders for their consultation, the first draft of the call was developed until Spring of 2019. Following iterative rounds of feedback and adjustments, the call was presented to the JPI Climate Governing Board and launched on October 28th, 2019, through various means including the JPI website, newsletters, word of mouth, exchange amongst colleagues and research administration offices.

7.4. Opening the Call

7.4.1 Guidelines for Applicants

The “Guidelines for Applicants”¹⁰ document included formalities such as eligibility and funding criteria, a list of participating countries and their funding bodies, reporting requirements, the thematic topics, and a more condensed conceptual background as compared with the White Paper. Although the deviations from the White Paper were significant, there was a shared premise that, *“To enable transformational change, novel interdisciplinary collaborations across social sciences and humanities and potentially beyond are required”* (pg. 5).

Regarding transdisciplinarity, the guidelines were loosened compared to the White Paper and were “highly encouraged where appropriate”. However, indirectly related to transdisciplinarity is the guideline that “impact should not be limited to scientific publications but should have the potential to trigger change in behaviour and attitudes at any level of society” (pg. 7). Thus, transdisciplinarity was promoted through encouragement to trigger change and produce actionable knowledge, as well as through the previously mentioned “three lenses” which applicants were asked to address in their proposal.

7.4.2 Proposal Evaluation

In terms of evaluation, the outline proposals were not formally reviewed by evaluators but were checked by the Call Secretariat for quality and first eligibility criteria. Based on the outlines, the Call Secretariat identified the appropriate experts to be evaluators of the 72 full proposals¹¹.

To reach consensus with participating funding bodies, the designers of the call had to compromise rather significantly regarding the funding criteria and the direction of the budget. Interviews with the designers of the call indicated that they initially wanted a stronger focus on societal impact criteria, but this had to be softened to fit the more restricted schedule of various national funding schemes. However, the evaluation was steered towards societal impact in the follow way. First, criteria of scientific quality and impact were double weighted compared to the other two criteria of proposals being in/out of scope and quality and efficiency of implementation. Secondly, impact was described explicitly as both scientific and societal. For example, a societal dimension of impact is highlighted as, “Strategy for disseminating and discussing the results of the project with a range of societal actors, including decision-makers, and ways to diffuse results “(pg. 10). Evaluation mechanisms such as this can be directly related back to the overarching ToC as the criteria directly supports projects which help achieve the desired impact of the overarching program.

However, some challenges to societal impact included national funding bodies with varying windows of eligibility for non-academic stakeholders to participate in the proposals. The result was that the call had to appeal to the least common denominator of eligibility, which in effect did not make it possible to fund the kinds of stakeholders who were sketched in the ToC as eventual end users of project outputs. The conditions of possible engagement for these stakeholders in the call determine the

¹⁰ <https://jpi-climate.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/solstice-guidelines-for-applicants.pdf>

¹¹ In total, ten countries chose to participate and contribute to funding the call (Austria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Norway, and the United Kingdom) with a total budget of 6.9 million. A total of 96 outline proposals were submitted and 72 of those were invited to submit a full proposal, with 7 projects being selected for funding and starting in Spring 2020.

difference between traditional dissemination activities and transformative activities such as those described in the guidelines as, “co-creating by-products”, “cooperation with NGOs or citizen initiatives, “involvement of non-scientific stakeholders early in the research project”.

7.5. Project kick-off

In the end, seven projects were selected to be funded for the SOLSTICE program. The projects according to their ToC are listed in Table 7 below:

Table 9: Summary of the main outputs, outcomes and impacts of the projects as described by the formative evaluation team.

Name of the project	Key outputs	Key outcomes/impacts	ToC
202CM	Open-source toolbox on climate change communication strategies	Overcoming barriers and indifference through communication that empowers citizens	Increase interaction between text- and image-centered approaches with behavioural-, social- and individual-centred to improve strategic communication and reduce apathy towards climate change.
CCC-CATAPULT	Knowledge on students and teachers sense making of climate change	Youth action platform (YAP); integration with policy initiatives	Involve children in research on a transformed climate focused education to enable climate action
CLEAN Cultures	Toolkit for decarbonisation transition initiatives	Research as change process; best practices for transformative learning process	By initiating learning processes about local, contextualized decarbonation processes, they will be more inclusive and redistributive
Just-Scapes	Findings about justice and landscape actions	Knowledge and awareness; Media and resources shared on website available to public	Understanding the social dimensions of rural transformations will help remove justice barriers
ROLES	Toolkit on digitalisation of energy systems	Integrated in event EU Sustainable Energy Week 2023; 1:1 meetings with decision makers	Enhancing citizen agency and understanding their needs in energy digitalization will steer the process to generate social benefits
SOLARIS	Identification and analysis of inequalities	Availability of resources; Blog; Handbook; practitioner’s guide; web documentary	Anticipating the distributional impacts of deliberative participation processes when forming policies will help ensure that these participatory innovations are socially just
JUST-decarb	Articles for researchers and policymakers on adverse impacts of decarbonisation	Policy briefs; events; online website and media	Identifying the vulnerable actors of decarbonisation will inform policies to include them in opportunities created by transition.

The kick-off meeting was held in April 2021 and in attendance were all projects and their consortia, the SOLSTICE advisory board, members of JPI’s Transdisciplinary Advisory Board (TAB), members of JPI Climate Action Groups, the SOLSTICE Call Secretariate and the formative evaluation team. During

this kick-off meeting, the formative evaluation team was tasked with hosting an impact session to get the projects to already think about their ToC and the mechanisms within their project to achieve their intended impact. The impact session was structured into eight breakout rooms, seven for the individual projects to discuss impact and one room dedicated to people involved in administration, funding, and the development of SOLSTICE.

Along with the impact session, the evaluation team provided feedback to a questionnaire for projects to complete prior to the kick-off meeting. The questionnaire included 13 questions total, and two questions were prepared by the evaluation team. These questions focused on helping the research projects reflect on their own project level ToC and how their research processes would connect to the desired outcomes of the call level ToC. During the impact session, the evaluation team was introduced to the projects and the responses to the two questions were presented in a word cloud featured in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and

below.

Figure 6: Word Cloud results to Q8: Which kind of societal impact do you expect from your project? Please name three most prominent aspects that come to your mind.

Figure 7: Word Cloud results to Q9: How would you define the societal transformation your project is aiming for? Please name the three most prominent aspects that come to your mind.

Although key outputs of the projects vary considerably (see Table 7), the qualitative data gathered during the Impact Session offered insight into how transformation through research was imagined from the project perspective. Figure 6 demonstrates an actor focused approach to impact, through “consciousness”, “policy”, “agency”, and social”, entailing a high emphasis on decision making and reflection. As for Figure 7, ideas about transformation resulted in “transformation” being the most salient word for respondents which suggests a slight uncertainty around ways of describing such associations.

During the session, there were suggestions such as to “look out for and value the „smaller’ impacts”, and “developing intercultural connections”, and one suggestion to take a more network approach and “improve impact by engaging with other JPI Climate projects”.

7.6. Program level evaluation

After the first workshop, the formative evaluation team prepared a second workshop with the Call Secretariate for May 2022. The workshop was focused around presenting the results of the program-level evaluation to the Call Secretariate and relating these findings to the main questions around transformation and impact from the first workshop. Overall, the aim was to develop key insights for how future calls could improve transformative potential.

The timeline below demonstrates the various activities which accumulated before the evaluation document was presented to the Call Secretariate in the second workshop May 2022. Not all timeline events correspond with primary or secondary data used in the evaluation but are key events relating to the SOLSTICE process.

- 2018, White paper
- 2019, Call development
- October 2019, the call involved a 1.5 stage process
- January 9th, 2020, outline proposals due
- February 3rd, 2020, full proposals due on
- May 2020, projects were notified of successful proposals
- November 2020, pitch meeting between SuperMoRRI and JPI about the evaluation concept
- early 2021, formative evaluation was established
- January 2021, projects start
- April 2021, impact session at the kick-off meeting
- December 2021, formative evaluation first workshop
- May 2022, formative evaluation second workshop and presentation of Program Evaluation document
- November 16th, 2022, midway evaluation of the projects
- 2023/2024, projects end

In what follows, the insights from the program evaluation, reactions from the Call Secretariate and the results from discussions in the second workshop are summarized. On the highest level of call design, the evaluation found that there could be more explicit clarification and operationalization of inter and transdisciplinarity in the call text that would support projects in “pushing beyond”

knowledge boundaries. In the seven project consortia, interdisciplinarity is mainly represented in different combinations of social sciences, e.g., linguistics, anthropology, philosophy, environmental management, human geography. In some cases, there was the inclusion of engineering and technical sciences such as civil, environmental and water engineering, however these were less represented overall.

As already mentioned, there was a shift between the White Paper and the call text as the former framed stakeholder engagement as essential to generate creative and alternative pathways to impact and the latter only encouraged stakeholder engagement “where appropriate”. Interviews provided some insight that this was in part due to the different national funding schemes participating in the call and their respective eligibility criteria to be a beneficiary of research funding. The result was that applicants were guided more towards scientific innovativeness and methodological experimentation across SSH disciplines in the pursuit of knowledge. However, this created conditions that were not as ambitiously transformative as described in the White Paper.

During discussions about these findings from the evaluation team, a JPI representative stated during the Second workshop that, “the topics and lenses¹² should push the projects into certain directions” and thus the process of responding to these elements of the call would provoke interdisciplinarity. While this might have been the intended mechanism of the lenses, their implementation in the projects was not reinforced or made binding in any way. Furthermore, as was established in the design of the call, the lenses were meant to act as a mechanism for attracting interdisciplinarity and new innovative combinations of research perspectives. Without the reinforcement of their importance, the lenses were of lesser importance compared to traditional pressures within research contexts such as scientific excellence in the form of publications. This was noted as an important lesson for future calls, particularly as a potential program level mechanism to generate synthesis and identify synergies between projects by looking at how their respective use of the lenses could interact with each other.

7.7. Midway project evaluation

The evaluation team prepared three questions for LPIs to respond to in writing, along with their other reporting requirements. These questions were intended to provoke reflection on similar aspects that were addressed during the impact session of the Kick-Off, namely inter and transdisciplinarity, societal impact and societal uptake of project outputs, and the transformative potential of project activities. The questions were as follows:

1. *Please briefly describe how SSH is contributing to social change in the context of your project. How does this compare to what you expected prior to the project?*
2. *How would you assess progress made so far towards the eventual take up and use of your projects’ outcomes?*
3. *How is the research process involving non-academic stakeholders changing or improving your plans to address the societal impact of climate change?*

In the responses to these questions, there was evidence that some LPIs could clearly link their project activities to a transformative impact. In these cases, the projects had no hesitation taking on board the idea that involving stakeholders could lead to direct impacts with transformative potential. For example, one LPI explained:

¹² As a reminder, these were (1) operational upscaling (2) deliberating norms and (3) a systemic approach.

“We have engaged heavily with diverse local stakeholders, from everyday users of energy systems (smart electric meters, forms of transport, solar panels and energy flexibility devices like batteries) to experts within sectors like transport, electricity generation, distribution and consumption, primarily at the local and urban but also in some cases at the national level. These exchanges, which have taken multiple forms (semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions, public and closed-doors seminars, webinars, hands-on workshops), have themselves been a highly effective form of exchange of information and co-produced perspectives. Thus, (the project) has been closely engaged in the case studies, to the extent that one direct impact of the project was a family-focused electric bicycle subsidy scheme from Bergen being transferred to Stavanger, a direct impact through policy mobility.”

For this LPI, involving stakeholders was a clear means of “leverage points” in their research as the overall topic they were investigating required the obvious need to shift energy infrastructure but also to shift societal practices.

In other instances, other LPIs challenged the idea projects can meaningfully achieve transformative impact on a broader scale than the research project:

“Yet we are mindful of being one research project, and proactively seek meaningful collaborations, which help to amplify our reach and effectiveness at informing action through our insights. Our results also show that despite the urgency of challenges, there are few immediate solutions commensurate to the scale of the problems that can be implemented for adequate societal impact within a project timescale (such as three years), so part of our hope is in situating relevant knowledge with key actors in the contexts where this can be actionable and help steer the course towards a better future.”

While this LPI did not have a clear path, there was a vision for how the project could find actors who would benefit from its outcomes. In such cases, mechanisms to support the SOLSTICE ToC such as the three lenses would be useful in supporting projects to think about how their projects could support or relate to each other. Such mechanisms could be useful for the projects in understanding what resources are available within the SOLSTICE program, and what knowledge or lessons have been learned from other projects.

While these were the kinds of responses reported in the written mid-way evaluation, the discussions during the meeting included some critical reflection on the idea of reporting impact. Some projects shared concerns that reporting impact at the midway stage was rather meaningless because impact had not occurred yet. Despite these comments, during the Q&A sessions the LPIs frequently shared informal, impact generating moments that occurred outside what they considered to be a strict impact pathway. Based on observations from the discussions during the midway meeting, it became clear that there is a standard practice for project reporting during such meetings, and smaller “moments of impact” (term coined by the evaluation team following the meeting) which are often more anecdotal, are not part of this practice. It is to be expected that researchers under a review process would not be comfortable straying from the standard practice, however these anecdotal, narrative meanderings about what occurs during a project are quite relevant to understanding the kinds of mechanisms attributable to transformation in the original and conceptually ambitious White Paper.

7.8. Conclusion

As a prototype for how TIPs can be translated into an actual funding program, SOLSTICE shows the journey from conceptualizing transformative research through multiple organizations, levels of governance, approval (both epistemically and administratively), and interpretative processes. The overall objective to fund, design, implement and practice research differently – in a way that is more transformative than „traditional’ research funding – entails complex negotiations and compromises. Additionally, this case investigated a further dimension of this process by experimenting with how evaluation can contribute towards transformation.

To conclude, let’s begin with the conceptual origins of SOLSTICE and how these were translated into a transformative funding program. The ambitions underlying the White Paper are clear and even though a strong definition of transformation is absent, the expectations for the necessary variables – SSH leadership in producing actionable solutions in partnership with other disciplines and stakeholders – are quite clear. With this clarity, the White Paper hopes to stretch standard practice of research programs into something transformative. However, as the White Paper is only a starting point and stretches a bit beyond what can be practically agreed upon in a multi-national funding scheme. While there are still transformative elements in the call design, the conceptual stretch starts to slowly look more like its original form.

The case demonstrates that there is some distance between the original ambitious of a TIP and its practical implementation. This is to be expected with any new practice model, particularly when it relates to changing systems and multiple actor groups and their interactions within them. This manifested itself in the necessary changes and compromises that the White Paper had to go through to become a funding program that multiple different national funding bodies could agree upon. This task itself is an experimental approach to integration within the European Research Area. In terms of research practices, project level LPIs are willing and interested in cooperating in such research projects, however the mechanisms that reinforce the program ToC, such as the trans- and interdisciplinary lenses within the SOLSTICE call, should be further developed as true resources for projects to fall back on. At the current stage, the lenses were more used as a proposal writing and development concept. This signals the start of experimentation but requires much more coordination and resources on the level of the Call Secretariate – resources which are currently under provided for transformative ambitions. For example, program level training might have helped boost confidence amongst projects when considering alternative ways to discuss or report on their impact. As the transformative aims of the program require more translation of knowledge into societal impact, networking building amongst non-scientific stakeholders and solution-oriented knowledge, the different researchers might have benefited from more opportunities to exchange with each other about these practices. Left to their own projects, it was easier for projects to fall back on more traditional forms of impact in the form of scientific article and conference presentations. These pursuits are still valuable for a TIPs, however communities are less likely to benefit from such outputs and therefore these scientific activities should not occur at the expense of stakeholder-oriented activities.

Related to the uptake of project outputs within communities is the initial aim of inter and transdisciplinarity. Although the development of the call presented some challenges when administering a climate change funding call to SSH disciplines, the projects were successfully able to attain a range of unique combinations. While the technical sciences were less represented compared to SSH overall, SOLSTICE was able to provide a unique opportunity for disciplines to work together. However, SSH led interdisciplinarity did not translate directly to an increased likelihood of

transdisciplinarity and public engagement in the research process. This aspect was opaquer since it was not an explicit eligibility criterion and it also depended on the project context and reporting practices of the LPI. While some LPIs saw their activities as impact oriented and “reportable”, others were doubtful about promising impact orientation at early to mid-stages of the project. This means that reporting on topics such as an impact and transformation is not standard practice, and it varies significantly by the LPI and their perception and willingness to embrace the concepts.

The case demonstrates that there is much ambiguity around transformation, what it looks like, how research should play a role in it and most importantly, what kind of funding structures and criteria it requires to take place. The experience from the side of the evaluation reinforces the idea that any corresponding evaluation must be equally open to not just accounting for transformation, but experimenting, correcting, and learning about transformation as a specific research aim and strategy that falls outside the normal practices of standard research funding. This case therefore supports the argument of Molars- Gallart et al. (2021) that formative evaluation is the most suitable method for evaluating TIPs.

In terms of responsibility, SOLSTICE shows us how the string of multiple actors, at varying levels, are responsible to each other and must share in their commitment to experimentation. Experimentation requires a different kind of responsibility based on trust and openness, particularly when the direction these actors are pursuing is one that is as conceptually ambiguous as transformation. The case shows how each actors have their own rules and impediments, the visionaries of the White Papers, those who turn it into a call, those who administer the call, those who evaluate the call (we read little from them in the paper), those who interpret the call and turn it into a proposal and those who turn the proposal into research and their understanding of transformation.

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8. Gendered Eco-Innovation

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8.1. Introduction and study design

Overall, the case study on gendered eco-innovations has two parts, a quantitative patent analysis that examines the patterns of green innovation and the participation of female inventors hereby on the one hand (pattern study). In addition, a qualitative, interview-based part aims to trace the causes of the relationship between gender and eco-innovation on the other hand (pathway study). This pathway study aims to understand if and how gender diversity and equality effects are manifested in eco-innovations.

The narrative presented here is largely based on the qualitative part and follows the three guiding questions set by the WP5 coordinators:

1. How and to what extent does having more women inventors make a difference in green patents and innovations?
2. Where do you see the opportunities and shortcomings through the lens of gender in green tech?
3. What does your case teach us about responsibility in research and innovation as it relates to gender in sustainable innovation?

The starting point for our case study was a comprehensive literature analysis that showed a relationship between gender diversity and eco-innovations (see below). Also, a quantitative exploration in a green patents database held at INGENIO showed an effect on women within diverse teams to produce more green innovations.

However, there are major unknowns about these phenomena, thus far mainly approached in a quantitative way that shows the pattern. Here, we are contributing to disentangling the pathway, as the crucial research gap is to understand which kind of diversity is translated into the innovation process and the underlying mechanisms to generate the observed link between gender diversity and equality and eco-innovations. Women's participation in innovation is, however, very scarce, so possible inequality and barriers and how organizations deal with them are key points in the study.

Our initial level of analysis was companies in Spain and Germany and involved the inventors and other members of the firm. We were also interested in exploring how the different stages and maturity of eco-innovations relate to gender. However, the firms did not collaborate with the study and their participation in the early stages of innovation too, so we finally focused on the inventors' perceptions. The inventors have been identified through the Green Technologies Database based on PATSTAT and through snowballing, as it will be explained in the methodological section.

The relevance of this work is derived from the fact that "The Green Economy" as well as promoting Gender Equality (GE) is at the top of the EU agenda (see "A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025"). In our view, eco-innovations reflect corporate responsibility towards the environment and a sustainable future.

To summarize, this case study aims to investigate whether gender diversity positively influences the emergence of eco-innovations (a descriptive question that identifies a pattern) and how the underlying mechanisms can be described (an analytical question that aims to identify pathways). Finally, our guiding question in contributing to the SuperMorri project is the following: Is gender

diversity a proxy indicator for openness towards societal needs and anticipatory, reflective, responsive, and inclusive innovation behaviour? Knowing more about those aspects helps us to reflect on monitoring the gender key and others.

Our results point to the fact that there is a link between gender diversity and openness towards societal needs that need to be further researched. It works through mechanisms such as different ways of doing, relating, and associated roles and positions that we are describing in section 2. We also found that organizations are not developing comprehensive measures to incorporate women, which is the main challenge. Also, the differential contributions that lead to eco-innovation are not rewarded, even if acknowledged. Finally, we argue that the consideration of gender aspects in research and innovation policy, in particular R&I funding, is vital, but also a better representation of women in the innovation processes themselves.

To answer the questions above, our paper is structured as follows: first, we briefly describe the state of the art as regards the relation between eco-innovations and gender diversity and the resulting main research questions (section 1.1). Afterwards, we present the methodological approach of the patent analysis, namely the overall identification of green patents across Europe and the role that female inventors play, and the ways to design and implement the qualitative case studies in German and Spanish companies (section 1.2). Section 2 is dedicated to the three narrative questions presented above. Section 2.1: How and to what extent does having more women inventors make a difference in green patents and innovations? Section 2.2: Where do you see the opportunities and shortcomings do you see through the lens of gender in green tech? Section 2.3: What does your case teach us about responsibility in research and innovation as it relates to gender in sustainable innovation? The narrative ends with some conclusions and lessons learned for the SuperMoRRI project (section 3). The list of references (section 4) includes both literatures cited in the narrative (in bold) and the literature that built the ground for the state-of-the-art presentation.

8.2. Summary of the literature review and research approach

Many studies report that gender equality positively influences eco-innovations. The potential causes for the observed link between gender diversity and eco-innovations are grouped in the third explained below:

- 1) Higher environmental consciousness of women (Zelezny, Chua, & Aldrich, 2000) (Schultz & Stress, 2009) (EIGE, 2012) (Hobach and Jacob, 2017: 9). (Kassinis et al., 2016, p. 9)
- 2) Different leadership behaviour (Horbach & Jacob 2017 p. 7, p. 8), (Ridgeway, 2001) (Datta Gupta & Poulsen & Villevall, 2013; Niederle & Vesterlund, 2007) (Liu, 2018), cited from (Nadeem et al. 2020, p. 3147).
- 3) Different social relations, networks and alliances; Nadeem et al. (2020) point out that women develop higher ethics of caring and are more concerned with the interests of multiple stakeholders, including society and the environment (Adams et al., 2011; Bear et al., 2010; Cumming et al., 2015)."

The references introduce different effects from women's leadership (in high positions like boards, attending to a minimum critical mass) and from – potentially - all women, derived from their education and values predisposing them to eco-sensitivity. The first conditions how the company functions and shapes its vision and mission (organizational aspects). However, women's leadership in firms is scarce. The second value/consciousness- conditions the way women inventors and female staff enrich innovation departments by bringing in diverse ideas to produce new products, services, and processes.

Nowadays, they are also underrepresented in inventions, and their potential diversity contributions could be jeopardized by inequality.

The third aspect — different networks — has been less explored, but also other studies in science show that women are building networks with more diverse actors from different professional communities (Díaz-Faes et al., 2021). Therefore, we have paid particular attention to this aspect that points to openness towards societal needs and grand challenges, as said, but is, of course, intertwined with leadership and higher environmental consciousness.

We also were interested in gendered participation in the different stages of the innovation process related to the maturity/novelty of eco-innovations. It is unexplored in gendering eco-innovations, while the innovation literature concedes great relevance to the aspect (Vona & Consoli, 2015).

To reach our main target, we have an open approach to map how perceived gender diversity is translated into eco-innovations. Previous studies used quantitative approaches that show clear patterns, and our contribution pursued to explore further aspects beyond the three cited before, opening the floor to their protagonists — women innovators — and how they perceive the enablers/constraints in their organizations.

In our interviews, we have asked about leadership, visions and values, relations/networks/alliances, and asked about specific ways of doing and material conditions (resources, time, other), but mainly we have left room for open responses. Mapping gender diversity(ies) allow/s us to explore fine-tune mechanisms that shed light on how these diversities not only exist but are integrated into the innovation process.

Finally, we have considered that the business sector's approach to equality through diversity perspectives has been found to be less ambitious than other approaches — like inclusion that also approaches from affirmative action — that seek to compensate the more vulnerable actors. An idea of diversity that does not count from the beginning on power dynamics can easily obliterate social justice and be distracted from aspects that lead to effective equality, such as the possible need for affirmative actions that compensate the more vulnerable actors (Kirton & Greene, 2000) (Kossek & Lobel, 1996) (Johansson & Ringbrom, 2017). For instance, we shall consider that corporate cultures sometimes do not acknowledge some structural factors that exclude women, such as not extending the job schedules to better conciliate with family responsibilities. In addition, we shall consider that gendered corporate cultures may consider masculine-related as the universal mean of efficiency or the right way of doing things (Acker, 1990).

So, in exploring the mechanisms to integrate diversity, we will also explore whether the diversity women can provide to the innovation process and the organizational functioning is valued and integrated with equal/unequal conditions. We approached the perceptions about this issue and possible measures of the organizations in dealing with it.

8.3. Methodological approach: Pattern results and data gathering for pathways

Our intended level of analysis was companies in Spain and Germany, and we planned to involve the inventors and other members of the firm in our interview programme. In addition, we were interested in exploring how the different stages and maturity of eco-innovations relate to gender.

However, the firms' collaboration in the study was almost non-existent, and their participation in the early stages of innovation was too, so we finally focused on the inventors' perceptions. The inventors have been identified through the Green Technologies Database (GTD) based on PATSTAT and through snowballing, as we detail in the following paragraphs.

Eco-innovations in our study are operationalized as green technologies. Specifically, the ones contained in the Green Tech Database (GTD), a resource developed to study green technologies using patent data from PATSTAT. GTD identified all the patent applications related to climate change mitigation and adaptation using the Y02 branch of the classification. This branch contains 44 technologies grouped in eight families. It identifies 425,743 patent families with at least one CPC code "Y02" from 1979-2018.

In there, we can find 85,115 families with at least one woman among the inventors (20.0%) and only 1,862 families where all inventors are women (0.4%).¹³

Table 10: Green patents by Technology group

CPC Code	Description
Y02A	Technologies for adaptation to climate change
Y02B	CCMTs related to buildings, e.g., housing, house appliances or related end-user applications
Y02C	Capture, storage, sequestration, or disposal of greenhouse gases [GhG]
Y02D	CCMTs in information and communication technologies [ICT], i.e., information and communication technologies aiming at the reduction of their own energy use
Y02E	Reduction of greenhouse gas [GHG] emissions related to energy generation, transmission, or distribution
Y02P	CCMTs in the production or processing of goods
Y02T	CCMTs related to transportation
Y02W	CCMTs related to wastewater treatment or waste management

Source : François Perruchas et al., *WP5 Gender, eco-innovation study. Data report* (2021) Internal document of the SUPER_MoRRI project

The GTD also allowed us to classify the inventions by country and stage of the life cycle of the technology (TLC): 1. emergence, 2. development, 3. diffusion and 4. maturity. The GTD was genderized using the names of inventors allowing to observing the following conclusions-patterns^[2]:

- The increasing presence of women over time among inventors of technologies for mitigation or adaptation against climate change in all technology groups.
- Along the life cycle, gender-mixed teams are a) always associated with impactful inventions, with high coefficient, b) negatively associated with novel inventions at the last stages of the technology life cycle, c) associated positively with original inventions at the beginning and the end of the TLC.

¹³ More information in François Perruchas, Susanne Bühner-Topçu, Davide Consoli, Nicolò Barbieri, Richard Woolley Gender and Eco-innovation. 6th Geography of Innovation Conference, Milan. Parallel Session 1: Green & Sustainable Innovation 4th-6th July 2022

So, the pattern or the positive relation of gender and eco-innovation was confirmed in the green technologies database, even if there are many further issues to delve into, such as regional disparities.[\[3\]](#).

Exploring the pathway or the motivations of this pattern was nowadays the primary goal of the case study, approached with qualitative methods (interviews). The initial study design involved firms in Spain and Germany. We wanted to know more about inventors' perceptions and other members of the firm that influenced the companies' innovation processes. We designed interview guidelines for the female inventors, and Human Resources directors and CEOs to gather a more comprehensive view of how gender diversity was perceived in the context of innovations and possible facilitators and barriers. We also wanted to know how gender diversity is related to the early-late stages and maturity of the technology life cycle.

We used the GTD to identify suitable firms that meet the following further criteria: a) the female rate of inventors for one patent had to be higher than 50% so we ensure a critical mass of women b) the patents were registered between 2010 and 2016 (last year included in the database) c) the technology life-cycle was between 1 and 3, the early-diffusion stages (if not enough patents were listed, the data selection was expanded to 4).

In the Spanish case, the database offered over 100 patents for the period 2010-2016, but just ten in the early stages (1, 2, 3), which were just two firms after manual database refinement. The German case was similar, with 214 for the period 2010-2016 and just 28 in the early stages.

However, the main barrier was that the firms were not willing to participate. General disinterest in social research or particularly the rejection of gender research could be at stake in the motivations. In Spain, 25 firms were approached, including all in the early stages, including mailing and diverse phone calls. In Germany, 27 people were approached. Almost all refused to provide contact, both in Spain and Germany, arguing privacy issues in the last case.

For these reasons, we focused on the inventors and used additional snowball techniques to identify female inventors from other organizational origins. The snowball strategy was the most expedient strategy for getting in contact with people directly. The resulting sample is in the **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** (Table 9):

Table 11: Information about interviewees

		Type of institution	Country	Position
i1	Researcher	Big company	Spain	Mid-management at the innovation department
i2	Researcher	Big company	Spain	Mid-management at the innovation department
i3	Researcher	Big company	Germany	Staff at the innovation department
i4	Researcher	University	Germany	Professor
i5	Professor	University	Germany	Mid-management and researcher
i6	Researcher	Research organization	Germany	Mid-management at the innovation department
i7	Researcher	Research organization	Germany	Mid-management at the innovation department

8.4. Results

How and to what extent does having more women inventors make a difference in green patents and innovations?

As presented above, the quantitative exploration in the green patents database and the literature review showed that the existence of women within diverse teams tends to produce more green innovations than homogenous inventor teams. In our interview-based case studies, we, therefore, aimed to understand how exactly which kind of diversity influences the innovation process, i.e., what the underlying mechanisms and pathways are.

The following presentation of the main results follows the main key influential factors identified in the literature:

Consciousness and perceptions: Women are already more interested than men in green issues during their studies at the university, as stated by i1. It is a question of vital purpose and going away from the already colonized white men “dinosaurs”, meaning the established and conservative hierarchies (i1). i2 sees no differences in age or mentality predominant to gender, as she exemplified in her direct boss, who promoted a positive mentality within the company towards innovation with fresh ideas from abroad. No differences regarding men and women in their global vision that concern eco-innovations are also stated in one interview in Germany, but generally, all acknowledge this differential consciousness.

Our work thus tends to confirm the literature but also shows that even if gender differences in career paths are acknowledged, neutral or individual-guided preferences are the preferred explanation for some women inventors.

Leadership styles: Our interviewees state that women at the top levels are found to be more explorative (i1), while women are, at the same time, more persuasive and more prudent (i2), which entails sometimes slowing down some processes and results. I1 and i2, from Spain, refer to men at top levels as being more aggressive when it comes to communication. However, both report a need for more women in top positions as problematic. All the interviewees agree that there still needs to be more women working in STEM and engineering-related jobs. Just i3 seems to accept that it is “natural” not having so many women working in engineering as the “typical” women-related jobs are in education and similar “social” professions.

Women inventors thus perceive that women have diverse leadership compared to men, that we connect with the different ways of doing things and behaving that will be explored below. These leadership styles can be connected with responsibility issues such as anticipation (prudence, slowing process), but, as both the literature and the interviewee remark, the effect of this diversity is limited, considering that few women are in top positions.

Continuing with less explored aspects in the literature that came out from the interviewees:

Ways of doing: In i2's case, many more women hold a PhD, which can open visions and ways of thinking. Most of the inventors thought that women work more focused (i6), more collaborative (i6), communicative, empathetic (i4), organized (i4) and are more willing to engage with the content of their work.

Women seek the project benefit over personal status, so they have intrinsic versus extrinsic motivations (i1). One of the interviewed researchers from Germany said: "Most men care about showing publicly when they were successful in an innovative development; Myself, I don't care if my name is written on it or not. (...) I am just happy to be part of something innovative." In addition, women tend to integrate hard skills (rational, pragmatism, oriented to result) with soft skills (collaboration, communication), while men tend to show more hard skills (i1).

In an open question, many issues were mentioned by women inventors as all perceived differences. Those are related to values and visions about what is needed/good for the collective, and this can lead towards more responsibility in connection with possible eco-sensitivity. However, it depends on their possibilities to shape the scope of the project.

Non-on-top management positions: i2 says that the majority of people managing at mid-level are women, recently, they hired people and most of the applications came from women. This career path's gendering is unclear, but it could affect the innovation process towards greener outputs. As i1 from Spain states, she selects projects following the roadmap of the firm (strategic plan). Therefore, with caution - as they are mid-level managers and are not holding all the decision power or are not part of the corporate vision settlement (men-dominated boards in both cases) - women may have some chances to influence the process, in the Spanish case.

The scarcity of women in high-level Management is a barrier to integrating diversity, but the possibility that women are influencing eco-innovations positively through mid-management positions is an interesting future path of research, still if just mentioned in the Spanish case.

Some interesting aspects are, how they can trigger projects that finally are implemented towards more eco-responsibility trends? Do they deal, and how, with a potentially more conservative vision of the firms? How could more collaborative mid-leadership with external and internal actors potentially contribute? Therefore, it becomes clear that there is enough expertise on the market and an opportunity to bring more women into decision-maker positions.

Team-level diversity integration: All of the interviewees prefer working in diverse teams. Diversity allows exchanging abilities but also leads to difficulties understanding each other among teammates (i2). In her context, gender roles within teams were clear: men in technical positions, women in management ones (funding and project management). Comparing the interviews conducted in Germany, there was a clear difference in the question if gender diversity matters for innovation or not. The only interviewee coming from a company did not see any difference and no influence by gender, whereas the representatives from the research institutions did. One of the interviewees from a research institution confirmed that teams in STEM still consist primarily of men. Even though, the way how men and women work is stated as being very different. In one of the Spanish firms, team-level work was clearly genderized as said: men in technical positions and women in project and funding management.

Ways of relating: i1 talks about many differences in relating outside of the company. She holds different relations with women from other companies/institutions, and they understand better as they share a perspective (see 'ways of doing'). That could be described as gender-to-gender homophily or the tendency to relate more to our own gender. In addition, interestingly, she reports a) more openness to diverse external actors, as recent research is showing with scientists (Diaz-Faes et al., 2021) and b) more collaborative ways of relating, such as not sending commercials but proposing the co-development of projects. The German professor summarized by saying: "You automatically attract

people who suit you." She believes that the contribution to innovation does not necessarily have to do with gender but with characteristics that may be related more to men or women, respectively.

That can be a central point in how eco-innovations are positively gendered, incorporating more actors with the closest visions to ecological concerns as women tend to have, but also in a more collaborative way.

Influencing other gender behaviour: In the German case, two of the interviewees said that women work more straightforwardly and orderly and that most men can be characterized by lacking communicational skills. One woman said: "Men work in a more communicative way when there are more women in the respective teams." This points to the way that participants' accommodation in a team is also gendered.

Innovation life-cycle stages and gendered participation: One of our targets in the case study was to explore participation in the innovation stages (early versus maturity stages in technologies). The firms worked with a different language (TRL) that could be translated into life-cycle categories. The interviewees confirmed the observation of the results of the Green Tech Database for Spain and Germany: firms focus on more mature technologies to only incur a few costs, except in cheaper digital developments, even if novel-risky (i1, i2). No more results could be expected with more samples as the patenting level in Spain and Germany at the initial stages is low, as explained before. Even in the mature technologies, no gender results were gathered looking at the patenting process, maybe because it was one of the first questions and more time is needed to warm up, maybe because the differences that appear in the pattern study cited before, will be situated within other detected mechanisms such as the ones discussed below.

To conclude this section, we point out that there are differential contributions of women that are generally acknowledged. Those aspects are related to the organization's practices, which is crucial as the following statements show: i6 stated that at her institute, more than women constitute 40% of the staff and that they are becoming more. In her opinion, the influence of human-centred topics leads to a higher share of women in the innovation process, and she thinks that a higher share of women has a positive influence on green innovations. i7 also works at a research institute and believes that women often respond more to keywords such as "environment", "sustainability", and she sees a noticeable effect, especially in reactions to job advertisements, which is crucial for the institute's recruiting processes: the emphasis is put less on technical but more on the perspective application. Through this, they have also recently managed to recruit two female mathematicians. i3, who is a researcher at a big multinational company in Germany, trusts that the driver for more green innovations is mainly supported by women even though, in her case, the economic benefits of producing green products are the main reason why her company supports these measures; i4 believes that there is a general "greener opinion" by women than by men which were already stated above when talking about consciousness and perceptions).

These observations support how diversity is expressed in intertwined aspects that we have dissected for analytical purposes and how the expression of diversity is connected with inequality and the scarcity of women. In the following section, we present in more detail how women inventors perceive the connection between inequality and organizational practices.

[Where are the opportunities and shortcomings through the lens of gender in green tech?](#)

The shortcomings are situated in the corporate culture regarding equality. The drivers of green innovation in the firm are clearly situated in profit, as reported by i1, i2 and i3, with no engagement

with social issues. The lack of equality measures points it out, too. In contrast, one interviewee from a research organization in Germany said that companies and research institutions are not able to change an existing system. Cultural and political changes must be the main driver because otherwise, nothing will change in a work environment.

In the organizations, if existing, there is a liberal and the same-as-equal approximation to equality: there are not many measures taken at the Spanish companies to incorporate women's possible diversity or acknowledge they could have more barriers, except in i1's case with a mentoring program that has not been discussed with the women previously. In that case, diversity can be incorporated through the extra effort of women or can be hampered, as it is shown in how firms' masculine-universal basis tends to make it difficult for women to fully participate and show their diversity in an environment that tends to have a different majority approach, that is the men majority viewpoint.

However, both Spanish companies have a gender equality plan (GEP) which is mandatory by national law; but the GEPs seem to be unknown. I2 cannot report any measure. During the covid-19 pandemic, they were allowed to work at a distance/from home just in her department because of their open-minded director, but the justification is the pandemic and not equality. I1 reports that the company's mentoring programme offended her a bit as it is like "adopting a woman". In addition, one German managing researcher from an RPO believes that some women's promotion programs are used as window dressing and sometimes to employ a woman because there is a funding scheme motivating the hire, which makes the employment cheaper.

Furthermore, most of the interviewed researchers do not support women's quota as they feel to be integrated into some activities not because of their expertise but because of their gender. This same managing director shared an experience where she was asked to be part of a conference presentation. Her male colleague agreed to leave a speaking part to her since "it would be good to have a woman on stage, too". Another researcher from Germany doubted once when she was offered a group leader position whether this was only due to fulfilling a quota or due to her as a competence bearer (i7).

The lack of women in top-management positions was a topic during most of the interviews. Both Spanish inventors report low rates of women, which is the main problem of aspired equality. They also speak about the gendering of top management-board positions, which puts women in "typical females" positions such as Corporate Social Responsibility or Communication. It happens even if the president is a woman. All the interviewees stated their observation of a small representation of women in leadership positions; one even admitted not being sure about climbing up in the hierarchy because the higher you get, the fewer women will be with you sharing the same hierarchy level.

I2 reports that the mid-management positions at her company held by women were better paid than the technical ones held by men. However, it could be related to a higher educational level (PhD) compared to her own role. I1 reports that the differences represented in relations, motivations, etc., are acknowledged but not rewarded (salary or other). The university professor from Germany explained that her female colleagues always complain of not being taken seriously by their male same-level colleagues. She observes that men need more attention and reward for their work.

Three of the seven interviewees proposed concrete measures to bring more women into engineering and STEM jobs. A cultural change has to be made already at school when pupils decide what they want to study and where they want to work. In Germany, the so-called "girls' day" is offered by companies at schools or the companies' own premises once per year to present atypical job opportunities for women. Some of the interviewees stated that in their near surroundings of friends and family, they

did not always have support when it came to choosing what to study or where to work when they were still young, as they were following a career path that was not typically meant for girls. This kind of event can break the barriers and open new opportunities for girls and women. I1 suggests a possible positive impact of promoting women networking within innovation processes.

These shortcomings can be turned into opportunities to act on equality within companies and research environments.

What can the case teach us about responsibility in research and innovation as it relates to gender in sustainable innovation?

Our case study shows that there is a pattern that connects women's participation with more eco-innovations. The pathway shows a possibility of diversity expressed in environmental consciousness but also in leadership in a more participative way, with more prudent and focused projects and different ways of working together, bringing more actors together in more collaborative ways of doing. This could lead to changes from commercialization approaches to co-development approaches that have more chances to include anticipatory visions about the impact of the innovations, both positive and negative.

Furthermore, including more perspectives in the innovation process seems crucial for out-of-the-box thinking, leading to new and future-oriented ideas. Including "women" and "men's perspectives and ways of working leads to higher quality assurance in proving the applicability of innovation results for society in general. One of the interviewees said: "The more diverse a team is, the more aspects are considered. There are just benefits."

In addition, the question of how more women in research and innovation teams could change men's attitudes towards more eco-innovation in the teams, or selecting projects at the mid-management level, together with how they interact with external actors, can be a relevant path for future research. In particular, given that the key point of the identified pathway is the scarcity both at horizontal and hierarchical levels of those actors more willing to engage in eco-innovations (women), organizations still need to sufficiently address this problematic lack of presence or reward the differential contributions.

However, even if organizational-based measures are absent, i2 reports a significant impact in their department since the gender clauses have been included in the calls for public funding, both in Spain and at the European level. Those funding calls ask for gender-diverse teams, among others. Furthermore, the inclusion of gender aspects in the definition of public research and innovation programs and their funding mechanisms are expected to have an impact on addressing societal needs.

All these aspects, increasing women in teams and decision-making positions as well as the integration of gender aspects in research and innovation processes, are strongly related to RRI as research cannot be perceived as being socially responsible if half of the population and their specific needs are neglected.

Our study points out that nowadays, more women's participation is recommended in the definition of the various policy measures, as quotas are producing unintended consequences-doubts in women, as they do not know if they are acknowledged by their gender or their professional competencies. We are not suggesting skipping quotas as it is the only cited measure functioning, and the lack of women's presence is the main problem. However, more discussions on how to improve the participation and representation of women in innovation policy are needed. In particular, future measures should

address top- and mid-management positions and not only research teams or projects. Such a discussion could also enrich the design of responsible innovation policy instruments, aiming at bringing objectives like contributing to the SDGs forward.

Consequently, some key aspects arise regarding monitoring: 1. to monitor women's presence in diverse hierarchical positions in firms, going beyond the research-academic sector or the project-based-monitoring associated with funding 2. To monitor women's participation in defining innovation policies and funding schemes.

In light of our results, more research is needed to investigate whether gender diversity can be used as a proxy indicator for openness towards societal needs, as women tend to work with a greater variety of actors. It is also helpful to shed light on how to promote more collaborative multi-actor innovation projects.

8.5. Conclusions and reflections

Even though the case studies could not be carried out as planned due to the companies' reluctance, the interviews with female inventors have yielded numerous key insights into the connection between gender diversity, equality, and eco-innovation.

First, the central assumptions from the literature were confirmed, in particular, the positive influence of diversity on the emergence of innovations in general and the particular sensitivity of women to environmental and sustainability issues. Furthermore, women and men differ in their ways of doing, their associated roles, and their collaboration networks.

More women within teams and in mid-managing positions could be changing the ways teams work towards more green perspectives. However, still, all interviewees cite the need for more women in top positions to set the strategies within the organizations to obtain broader effects of diversity. In order for this diversity to actually come to fruition, a critical mass of women in decision-making positions in organizations is necessary so that they can actually exert influence and initiate a change process. Also, their participation is needed in the systemic configuration of innovation policies, including regarding the measures addressed to inclusion and diversity.

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9. Public Engagement: Organizational Repertoires and Researchers' Practices

Thomas Kjeldager Ryan

9.1. Background

The notion of responsible research and innovation (RRI) has, over the last decade, had a prominent place in the research policy discourse. A concept driven and pushed forward largely by the European Commission through their main funding mechanisms and through European research policy in general. In particular, a large number of projects have attempted to examine, develop, and integrate the concept of RRI into the European research community with funding through Horizon 2020 (H2020). Within H2020 many studies focused on fielding and testing how RRI policies and support structures could be integrated into European research organisations. These projects, though different in scope and methods, rely to some extent on the assumption that changes in the organisation can lead to changes in the practices of the researchers they host. The logic of organisational change as a key driver of responsible research and innovation is captured well in the European Commission's performance indicators, which among others measure how many actions that promote RRI are implemented in research performing organisations (RPOs) (Delaney and Iagher 2020).

Gerber (2020) argues that "remarkable change processes have been initiated, signalling a potential deeper institutionalization of RRI principles and practices into organisations and national level policies". However, there is a risk of interpreting the uptake of RRI ideas in organisations as synonymous with institutionalization of RRI in scientific fields and research practice. In fact, researchers are highly influenced by the rules and norms of the field they belong (Becher, T., & Trowler, P. (2001).). And many studies have shown that researchers tend to identify more with their discipline than the organisation that hosts them (Henkel, M. 2000). Moreover, research organisations are often characterized as loosely coupled organisations, in which top-down policies have little influence in the bottom due to decoupling in the organisation (Weick, K.E. (1976), Meyer, J. W., and Rowan, B. (1977)). The question of how efficient organisational efforts to promote RRI among scientific practitioners is therefore an important one to shed light on.

While organisational policies are not the only vehicle of change, it is here this study takes its departure. The assumption behind policy intervention is that the appropriate organisational policies can affect research behaviour. Excluding the large number of single case studies that follow one or multiple organisational changes, no studies within the field of RRI have attempted to quantitatively assess whether and to what degree organisational policies in fact can influence the practices of researchers.

In this study, we examine public engagement in particular. Public engagement is one of the five RRI keys emphasized and pushed forward by the European Commission. Inclusion of the public in research is seen as an important part of making research more responsible. As it can contribute to research becoming more responsive to the needs of the public and considerate of the diverse needs of different groups the population. Public engagement covers "... the diversified set of situations and activities, more or less spontaneous, organized and structured, whereby non-experts become involved, and provide their own input to agenda setting, decision-making, policy-forming, and knowledge production processes" (Bucchi and Neresini 2007: 449). In the context of this study, Public Engagement is concerned with the inclusion of citizens, consumers, and patient groups in these research processes.

We assess whether researchers are more likely to engage in public engagement practices when employed in organisations that emphasize, incentivize and/or support public engagement in their organisational policies, strategies, and support structures. In this study we focus on public engagement repertoires which in short entails the set of policy instruments an organisation employs to promote, support, and incentivize public engagement in their organisation. We analyse whether the variety of policy instruments employed in the RPO is related to the average public engagement activity among the RPO's employees.

We rely on two coordinated data collection vehicles 1) a document study of 120 European RPOs and 2) a researcher survey with 4,108 respondents administered to researchers employed in the same 120 RPOs. The first data collection vehicle and coding hereof produce measures of the public engagement repertoire of the RPO, while the second data collection vehicle provides a self-reported measure of the researchers' public engagement behaviour in their most recent research projects. We report basic findings from the two data vehicles. The empirical analysis that combines the two vehicles relies on a subset of the 120 RPOs. We examine 42 RPOs for which there are at least 28 responses in the researcher survey.

The combination of the two datasets provides a great possibility to assess the degree to which policy emphasis on Public Engagement in research organisations relates to researchers' own practices. While there are some potential biases due to self-reporting in the survey and data availability in the document study, we believe that this study provides an important empirical foundation for discussing the central question: *how and to what extent institutional repertoires for public engagement make a difference in individual researchers' public engagement practices?*

The remainder of this study is structured as follows. First, we briefly describe the methods and introduce the two datasets. Second, we present the results of the analysis and discuss how it can illuminate the research question. We conclude the study with a discussion of the following two questions 1) *Where we see the opportunities and shortcomings for institutional public engagement repertoires and the goal of enhancing support for PE?* And 2) *What does the study teach us about responsibility in research and innovation as it relates to the institutional role of supporting PE?*

9.2. Measuring public engagement in European RPOs and among researchers

The SUPER MoRRI project performed two coordinated data collection exercises in 2021 and 2022. The Country Correspondent Network Study of Research Performing Organisations (CCN RPO) collected documents and website entries related to university strategies from 120 European RPO websites, focusing on strategies, support structures and actions related to responsible research and innovation. The SUPER MoRRI researcher survey (RESU) was sent to employees of the same 120 RPOs asking about the researchers' practices and perceptions of RRI. In both studies, a core section collected data on Public Engagement. This section briefly describes the two data-collection exercises and the Public Engagement activities of European RPOs and Researchers.

9.2.1 Public engagement policy in European RPOs

The aim of the CCN-RPO study was to examine a limited range of mechanisms through which research performing organisations (RPOs) enhance responsibility in research. Mechanisms in central focus in the study included 1) the overall strategic priorities of the RPO; and 2) concrete organisational policies, supporting structures and actions related to RRI, Open Science, Research Ethics and Integrity, Gender Equality, Public Engagement, and the Third Mission.

For each of the countries included in the CCN-RPO study, a selection of RPOs were selected for inclusion. Depending on the size of the country, either 2, 4 or 6 RPOs were picked. In each country, the local country correspondent (CC) carried out desk research on each of the assigned RPOs. The CC performed three major tasks: 1) Study publicly available documents and websites relating to the strategic priorities, policies, and supporting documents and actions of the organisation (See Table 10 for questions); 2) Perform a limited number of e-mail inquiries to validate and complement the information collected through publicly available documents and websites; and 3) Produce a written case report for each RPO in a template provided to the CC¹⁴. The core questions they were asked to answer are shown in Table 10 below.

Table 12: Core questions in CCN report on PE

Please note if this area is addressed in the overall strategy: Yes _____ or No _____ If yes, please describe in a few sentences, what the RPO aspires to achieve in this area:
please describe in bullet points any concrete goals, targets, or performance indicators outlined in relation to this area (if any):
please describe in bullet points any practical / operational implementation elements outlined to meet the goals (if any):
Please note, if the RPO has specific policies about Public Engagement: Yes _____ or No _____ If yes, please describe in a few sentences, what the RPO aspires to achieve in this area:
please describe in bullet points any concrete goals, targets, or performance indicators outlined in relation to this area (if any):
please describe in bullet points supporting structures outlined in relation to policies about Public Engagement (if any): please describe in bullet points supporting actions outlined in relation to policies about Public Engagement (if any):

(OSF: RPO study protocol)

A total of 120 case reports were coded by members of the SUPER MoRRI team. Four team members were continually part of the coding process. The coding process was conducted in three rounds. All case reports were coded inductively by one of the team members. Hereafter the coding was reviewed by the team and divided along RRI topics between the team members. Each team member then did a small literature review and used this and the inductive coding to develop a closed coding scheme. This coding scheme was test-coded using eight case reports, and cross-coded by two team members. Based on this coding, a third and final coding scheme was developed (as presented below). One team member coded the reports based on the closed coding scheme. To ensure coding reliability, team members swapped coded material and an ex-ante coding check was conducted.

Codes were developed by SUPER MoRRI team members in an iterative process including an inductive pre-coding and were informed by the studies and reports within the field including Ravn, Mejlgaard and Rask (2014), Arnstein, S. R. (1969), Glass, J. J. (1979) and Rowe, G., & Frewer, L. J. (2005). The coding scheme reflects the concept of the public engagement ladder.

¹⁴ The methodology of the CCN RPO study is described in more detail in Deliverable D2.4 Annotated Methodological procedures report available on the SUPER MoRRI Website.

The coding scheme for Public Engagement is presented below. Figure 8 illustrates the logic for how content was coded. There are four sub-categories in which policies, support structures and various policy statements where coded. First, all content related to Public Engagement was coded as such. Text is then coded in terms of the subject matter. *General engagement* represents text that describes the organisations aims and activities with regard to public engagement at a low level of resolution and detail. Content focused on the communication of research to the public is coded as *public communication*. Content focused on including the public in two-way communication is coded as public consultation and advice while content aimed at *public participation in science* is coded as public participation.

Figure 8: Strategic focus codes

A second layer of coding describes the type of policy mechanisms or practical implementation of policy. Practical Implementation Codes (PICs) (Table 11) were developed jointly and utilised for all four strategic focus sub-codes. Thus, a coded piece of text has both a strategic focus code (Figure 8) and a practical implementation code (Table 11). By discussing these extensively beforehand, coding reliability proved to be high in the ex-ante coding check. Each code reflects a different type of support structure, action or communication of intent related to public engagement.

Table 13: Practical implementation codes

Practical Implementation Codes (PICs)
Awareness campaigns
Dedicated unit
Events
Expressed aims (e.g., Mission statement or broad declaration of intent)
Funds/funding
Infrastructure
Networks
Policy targets

Recommendations and suggestions
Reference to networks, alliances, etc.
Reporting of progress
Rewards and recognition
Rules and requirements
Training

9.3. Measuring of public engagement repertoires

Table 12 provides an overview of the public engagement repertoires of the 120 European RPOs. PICs are divided into aims, policy instruments for supporting public engagement, and policy instruments for supporting and incentivizing Public Engagement. The first category reflects expressions of intent without any specific or tangible goals and policies. The second includes “soft” policies such as providing recommendations and guidelines for Public Engagement, setting policy targets, arranging events and similar. The third includes rewarding and recognizing Public Engagement activities through promotion, prizes etc. as well as providing training, and targeted funding for Public Engagement projects.

Table 14: Public engagement répertoires in RPOs

Category	Policy Mechanisms	PE general	PE communication	PE consultation	PE participation	No PE
No policy	-	48	38	90	94	26
Aims	Expressed aims Awareness campaigns References to (international) networks, alliances, etc.	23	21	24	12	-
Support	Networks Policy targets Events Recommendations and suggestions Reporting of progress	18	26	3	7	-
Support & incentives	Rewards and recognition Rules and requirements Training Infrastructure Dedicated unit Funds/funding	31	35	3	7	-
Total		120	120	120	120	-

The data shows that the majority of RPOs refer to Public Engagement in their publicly available strategic material. Only 26 of the 120 RPOs did not mention Public Engagement, or the concepts

related to Public Engagement on their institution website and available strategic documents. While many RPOs mention Public Engagement as an aim of their organisation, a much smaller fraction goes beyond promoting the communication of science to the general public. Similarly, policy that provides tangible support and incentives to the researchers are also rare. In particular when it comes to Public Engagement on the top of the ladder (participation and consultation).

It is difficult to provide a measure that captures the scope and variability of Public Engagement policy. The repertoires of RPOs are not easily translated into a single number or group. Yet, in order to investigate the Public Engagement repertoires further, we create a simple variable that counts the number of different types of practical implementations within each of the four sub-areas of public engagement (variety in Figure 9). This reflects the variety and scope of the public engagement repertoire of the RPO. Figure 9 shows the distribution of the measure of number of distinct policy instruments used in the RPO.

Figure 9: Distribution of PE policy instruments in 120 European RPOs

The distribution illustrates the story above, a handful of RPOs do not have any policy mechanism to support Public Engagement, the majority have between 1-6 different policy mechanisms and a small group have a diverse set of policy mechanisms to support and promote Public Engagement. This diversity is interesting as it could relate to the action space researchers have for engaging with the public when doing research. Both, in terms of sense of pressure, but certainly also how supportive they experience their organisation to be. Of course, the simple indicator does not take into account that the quantity or variety of policy instruments necessarily equates to the quality of organisational support for Public Engagement. Such questions are better suited for an in-depth qualitative study.

9.4. Public engagement among European Researchers

To shed light on European researcher’s public engagement behaviour we draw on the SUPER MoRRI researcher survey (RESU). The overall aim of this empirical study was to examine European researchers’ responsible research practices and their perceptions of, and attitudes towards, responsibility in research and innovation. The data collection from the survey was linked to the CCN-RPO Study in the SUPER MoRRI monitoring framework design. The sample of survey participants was based on the identification of (active) researchers from the RPOs included in the CCN study. On Monday, November 7th, 2022, an initial e-mail invitation was sent out to the 127.395 researchers (gross sample). A total of 4.107 researchers completed the section related to public engagement¹⁵.

The survey asked researchers how often they have included non-researchers in their research (e.g., citizens, consumers, and patients). Those that report to doing so are also asked in which parts of their research they involved these actors (e.g., problem identification, data collection, deliberation of results and communication of research). Finally, they were asked how often they engaged with non-researchers in their past and current research projects.

Three variables measure Public Engagement among researchers. 1) Public Engagement (Do researchers engage with the public?), 2) Public Engagement Frequency (How frequently do they engage with the public?) and 3) Public Engagement Ladder (At which step of the Public Engagement ladder do they engage?).

Table 13 illustrates the number of researchers in the sample that report to engage with the public and at what level they do so. A categorical variable with four categories is defined by responses to a series of survey questions. If respondents answer that they have engaged with citizens, CSOs, consumer or patient groups in the last three years, they are categorized as either “Public Communication”, “Public Consultation” or “Public Participation”. If they have not engaged, they are categorized as “No Public Engagement”. The distinction between communication, consultation and participation depends on the type of interaction they report to have had with one or more of the groups. Respondents are coded as “Participation” if they answer that they have *involved citizens in the development of research agenda*; as “Consultation” if they have *discussed the consequences of research / its application (incl. technology assessment) with citizens*, and as “Public Communication” if they have engaged in *dissemination and presentation of research results to citizens*.

Table 15: Public engagement ladder for sample of European researchers

Public engagement category	Number of researchers	Percentage of researchers
No Public engagement	1,108	26,5
Public Communication	1,596	38,2
Public Consultation	684	16,4
Public Participation	792	19,0
Total	4,180	100,1

¹⁵ The methodology of the RESU is described in more detail in Deliverable D2.4 Annotated Methodological procedures report available on the SUPER MoRRI Website.

*Does not add up to exactly 100 because of rounding.

The categorization attempts to follow the logic of the Public Engagement ladder where one-way communication to the public is on the lowest level and involving the public in decision making is on the highest level. Thus, the more intensive and collaborative the interaction, the higher on the ladder. The majority engage in public communication, while only a minority engage with the public on “higher steps of the ladder”.

In terms of frequency of public engagement there is a skewed distribution (Table 14). 11 % of respondents have engaged in some form of public engagement in all their recent projects, 30 % in some, 40 % in a few and 27 % in none. In total, 74 % of the sample report to engaging in some form of public engagement.

Table 16: Public engagement frequency among sample of European researchers

Public engagement frequency	Number of researchers	Percentage of researchers
No public engagement	1,108	26,5
In few projects	1,654	39,6
In most projects	960	23,0
In all projects	458	11,0
Total	4,180	100,1*

*Does not add up to exactly 100 because of rounding.

Table 15 illustrates that there are some clear divides between the fields of science: Social scientists and medical and health scientists are the most prolific in terms of Public Engagement. They are both more likely to engage with the public and to engage beyond communication of research. That likely relates to the epistemological and historical properties of the fields and sub-fields.

Table 17: Public engagement by field of research

Field of science	No Public engagement	Public Engagement
Structural Sciences (Mathematics, Informatics, Logic)	0,56	0,44
Natural Sciences (Physics, Chemistry, Geosciences, Astronomy, Biology)	0,38	0,62
Engineering and Technology	0,28	0,72
Agricultural and Veterinary Science	0,23	0,77
Arts and Humanities	0,23	0,77
Others	0,21	0,79
Social Sciences and Economics	0,18	0,82
Medical and Health Sciences	0,14	0,86

9.5. The empirical relationship between Public Engagement repertoires and public engagement practices

In this section, we provide a cursory analysis of the empirical relationship between organisational repertoires and researchers' Public Engagement practices. Assessing the relationship between the two can help us get closer to answering the question: *How and to what extent institutional repertoires for public engagement make a difference in individual researchers' public engagement practices?*

For practical purposes, we examine a subset of RPOs. The subset is selected based on a sufficient number of responses to the researcher survey from staff of the RPO. The cutline was set at 25, which resulted in 42 RPOs which had between 28 and 205 responding staff representing 3,371 researchers in total. The reason for having a cutline is to avoid averages to reflect outliers to a too high degree. The higher the number of researchers the more likely, that there will be regression to the mean. While an even higher cut number would be preferred vis-à-vis the law of large numbers, this was found to provide an acceptable sample of RPOs and at the same time eliminate a high degree of uncertainty of public engagement estimates among staff.

The average percentage of researchers engaged with the public in each RPO is illustrated in the figure below (Figure 10). It shows that there is a large variation from the RPO with fewest engaged researchers to the highest.

Figure 10: Proportion of staff engaged with public in 42 European RPOs

The three plots (Figure 11, Figure 12, Figure 13) below show the relationship between variety of RPO Public Engagement repertoires and three measures of public engagement. The figures are only calculated for the RPOs where at least 28 faculty responded to the super MoRRI survey. This accounts for 42 European RPOs. In Figure 11 average public engagement is plotted with the variety variable

capturing the number of policy mechanisms employed in the RPO. The plot indicates a positive (though marginal) correlation between the variety of policy mechanisms employed in the RPOs repertoire and the proportion of its staff who engage with the public. However, it is also obvious from the plot, that Public Engagement can be high in RPOs with a less varied Public Engagement repertoire. Figure 12 plots variety with average public engagement frequency. A similar picture emerges of a positive relationship between how often researchers in a RPO engage with the public and how varied the Public Engagement repertoire is. The third and final figure (Figure 13) plots the average step on the public engagement ladder for its researchers [where no PE=0, public communication=1, Public consultation=2 and public participation=3]. Again, a similar picture shows that RPOs with a varied repertoire have a higher number of researchers engaged at the higher steps on the public engagement ladder.

The three figures together thus provide an indication that there is a slight positive relationship between the variety of Public Engagement repertoires and researchers' Public Engagement practices. The directionality and causality of the relationship however is not covered in this analysis.

Figure 11: Average public engagement among staff by variety of public engagement policy mechanisms in 42 European RPOs

Figure 12: Average public engagement frequency among staff by variety of public engagement policy mechanisms in 42 European RPOs

Figure 13: Average public engagement ladder among research staff by variety of public engagement policy mechanisms in 42 European RPOs

9.6. Discussion

This study provides an initial empirical foundation for discussing the central research question of the study: How and to what extent institutional repertoires for public engagement make a difference in individual researchers' public engagement practices?

This section concludes the study with a discussion of the following two questions 1) Where do we see the opportunities and shortcomings for institutional public engagement repertoires and the goal of enhancing support for PE? And 2) What does the study teach us about responsibility in research and innovation as it relates to the institutional role of supporting PE?

We find that researchers in Europe generally report to engage with the public. However, the majority engage in Public Communication, while only a minority engage with the public on "higher steps of the ladder". Moreover, there are some clear divides between the fields of science that likely relates to the epistemological and historical properties of the fields and sub-fields. Social scientists and medical and health scientists are the most prolific in terms of Public Engagement. They are both more likely to engage with the public and to engage beyond communication of research.

The present study indicates that Public Engagement repertoires of RPOs have a positive relationship with their employees' propensity to practice Public Engagement and the type of Public Engagement they practice. The nature of the data of course makes it difficult to assess the directionality or assignment of causation. It is likely however, that a varied Public Engagement repertoire can provide assistance to many different types of researchers in different steps of their research. It is also likely that researchers who prefer public engagement seek towards environments that support and reward public engagement. Moreover, researchers who prefer involving the public in research may find less barriers and more support in RPOs with a varied repertoire, which could increase their Public Engagement activity relative to other like-minded researchers in less supportive environments.

While the relationship between Public Engagement repertoires and Public Engagement practices is clearly limited in strength, there may be the case for arguing that while organisational policies and support structures may not change preferences for how to engage in research, they may create an environment that can better support Public Engagement for researchers that already have a preference for engagement. Thus, researchers with a preference for Public Engagement may be more likely to seek out support structures such as guidelines, funding, etc., than their non-engaging colleagues. The most likely way in which RPOs can make a difference is by creating an environment that removes barriers and can make Public Engagement more effective for those that have a preference for it.

Additionally, translating organisational changes into institutional changes that can be observed in research practices may take a long time, and therefore, it is likely that while no large differences are visible in this cross-sectional study, there may be delayed effects that come from institutionalising Public Engagement. Finally, other major actors and institutions play a role in how research is done. Therefore, if organisational changes are not met with similar changes in funding organisations and in the scientific fields themselves it is unlikely that we would observe a large difference in Public Engagement practices. The clear differences in Public Engagement among field of science points to epistemological characteristics as a driving force for whether or not researchers engage with the public.

The question of organisational approach to Public Engagement in this brief study has been measured by a broad coding of the type of public engagement promoted and emphasized by the organisation.

The study simplifies Public Engagement repertoires to the variety of mechanisms employed by the RPOs. This means that some interesting details and variation are not included in this analysis and therefore a more granular study should follow. We argue that we should be careful to interpret the results as more policy is equal to more and better public engagement. In future analyses, a more fine-grained approach that differentiates between not only what the RPO focuses on but also *how* they do so, may help to find some strategies or repertoires that are good at aligning the preferences for public engagement among research staff and the support and resources devoted to PE in RPOs.

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10. Clarification of Pathways Towards Benefits

This chapter outlines the various pathways associated with the markers of responsible practices identified in the Patterns Report (D5.2).

The pathways refer to the different responsibility markers and are first introduced in terms of their expected or ideal way of realizing impact. For example, markers of responsibility could include research organisations that have explicit Public Engagement policies, or research projects that conduct inter or transdisciplinary research. The subsections include the relevant case studies where these responsibility markers are elaborated on in terms of their pathway toward impact. The cases provide a closer understanding of how and why these pathways emerge, who are the important actors and how responsibility practices are supported or are impeded.

Relating back Chapter 3 on the use of the ToC model for understanding benefits, the following pathways open our understanding about what occurs within the transducer (Figure 2). The cases provide a deeper empirical or theoretical investigation about how responsibility practices interact within a research and innovation context. The clarification of that interaction is also the clarification of the pathway.

When possible, the cases are placed within the context of a full qualitative case study (*CSOs at Science-Society Interface*, *SOLSTICE*, *Gender Eco Innovations*). In other cases, they draw upon empirical data from D5.2 with further theoretical analysis in order to clarify theoretical pathways and point to further research directions (*Public Value Research Careers*, *Public Engagement Repertoires*). In one instance, the *Ethics in AI* case represents theoretical reflections on a long-term study which did not involve any direct empirical work but did draw from expert interviews from the field.

10.1. Citizen Science Pathway

The ideal pathway that emerges from CS is that through the process of CS, new avenues for research and research application can emerge. This has benefits that are twofold, first being that the R&I system is more aligned to society and second, citizens become more empowered, engaged, and trusting towards science. In the Engaging CSOs case, the following potential benefits emerged relating to CS and its pathway effects:

- Co-production of knowledge –through cooperation between scientific experts and non-experts
- Citizen Science can provide shared knowledge and information which are prerequisites for open innovation, broader acceptance, higher market share and competitiveness
- Productive interactions in the context of collaboration on citizen science bring new ideas and creativity to the R&I system.
- Involving citizens in co-creation processes increases the likelihood that the outputs and outcomes of collaborative R&I will be adopted relatively straightforwardly by consumers/citizens, reducing costs.
- Norms, values, rules, and beliefs in the system (scientific, policy, social, etc.).

While the above benefits are associated with ideal instances of CS, the Engaging CSOs case demonstrated that CS is often used interchangeably with other responsibility markers such as PE and OS. CSOs that get involved with research projects end up representing citizens and therefore falling under the umbrella of achieving CS, however no actual CS is being performed. The same barriers that CSOs experience when joining research contexts through PE avenues (see section 10.4 Public

Engagement Pathway) are also experienced by CSOs who participate through CS opportunities. The funding and administrative constraints make it quite difficult for CSOs to do their own work while staying engaged in the research. The PE pathway further clarifies these potential barriers to PE which are often experienced in contexts where CS is the primary RRI marker.

10.2. Gender Equality Pathway

The theory of change for associated with Gender Equality (GE) is that more representation of diverse perspectives and gender balance in research teams has an intrinsic democratic value and will generate research output that is more aligned to societal needs. Newly met societal needs which are often neglected would then help alleviate inequality, and lead to more social sustainability. Thus, RRI related aspects which gender address gender and diversity in the research and innovation system focus on efforts to develop, mobilize, and leverage the talents of women and marginalized groups.

10.2.1 Gender and Eco Innovations

The case study investigates whether gender diversity positively influences the emergence of eco-innovations and how the underlying mechanisms can be described. It demonstrates a link between gender diversity and openness towards societal needs. The related mechanisms are (1) different ways of doing, (2) relating, and (3) associated roles and positions. The case study also showed that organisations do develop comprehensive measures to incorporate women. In addition, (4) the differential contributions that lead to eco-innovation are not acknowledged and rewarded. The case found that the consideration of gender aspects in research and innovation policy as well as R&I funding is important for promoting women in innovation. It is also important to improve representation of women in the innovation processes themselves. Potential pathways that stem from improved GE markers include more diverse ideas and creativity, a more diverse range of research questions and problems to solve that include women's issues and women's needs, and legitimacy.

10.3. Open Science Pathway

Open Science (OS) markers of responsibility refer to sharing knowledge and involving others to do research in a more open way for the benefits of science and society. The ToC is similar to that of PE, namely that OS has intrinsically better qualities because it is more aligned with the societal, economic and environmental needs of society and because it democratizes the research and innovation system. OS also refers to specific efforts to move towards more open knowledge structures, such as making research not published in English more accessible and efforts to improve the reusability of data reproducibility of results. The UNESCO four quarters of Open Science include:

1. Open scientific knowledge
2. Open science infrastructures
3. Open engagement of societal actors
4. Open dialogue with other knowledge systems

Looking a bit closer at possible pathways towards benefits, it is also assumed that OS helps lead to more efficient use of scientific resources such as software, hardware, and source code, as well as more readily sharing educational materials. The patterns related to OS can be found in D5.2, which identifies patterns of OS initiatives and uptake in specific RPOs and RFOs as well as individual researchers.

10.3.1 Public Value Research Careers and Open Science

The PVRC also clarifies factors that lead to more OS practices. As a reminder, the PVRC pathway refers to the better alignment of research careers with public values through institutional shifts, professional

expectations, and disciplinary norms. OS is something younger researchers are being encouraged to do, whereas older researchers have different practices. As such, the pathways towards OS benefits should consider career stage. Contributions towards the general shift to OS thus must have the support of senior researchers, mentors, and doctoral supervisors. For example, different career stage cohorts should be treated differently because leaders of the field set the example and exercise judgement about what is appropriate within their institution and discipline. Very senior scientists who have worked in a closed competitive model of science throughout long successful careers cannot be expected to switch to open science at the end of their careers – and resistance to both policy advocates and OSCs from senior researchers is well known and understood. However, senior researchers supporting (or at least not obstructing) the acquisition of OS skills and practices by junior researchers in their lab or department is an achievable objective, which could also be incentivized and supported institutionally.

10.4. Public Engagement Pathway

Public Engagement (PE) is one of the more echoed and cross-cutting markers of responsibility identified in WP5. PE can take on a variety of forms, both horizontally in the form of individual organisational activities as well as vertically through policy-oriented activities. As such, it is common for PE to have direct intersections with other responsibility practices. It can be expected that PE activities have spill over effects onto other responsibility related domains, or that a general pathway toward impact stemming from a PE activity can be described in many ways, by different actors with diverging interests who are brought together through PE. Therefore, PE has multiple and complex dimensions and only a portion of were captured in the selected WP5 case studies.

Theory of change for PE is that involving citizens and stakeholders in research, which has already an intrinsic democratic value, will generate research outputs that will be more aligned with societal needs. The cases PVCR, PER, Transdisciplinary funding and Engaging CSOs show that pathways to this benefit are far more complex and that there are several institutional and disciplinary hurdles to be considered.

The overarching expected pathway(s) for PE to achieve benefits can be broadly characterized by 1) the opening up of information flows between different parts of the R&I system and the public at large, 2) the better understanding of the positions and opinions of other stakeholders in the R&I system, and 3) the democratisation of decision-making processes regarding R&I regulation and policy (Woolley & Rafols, MoRRI D6.1). In undertaking PE activities and promoting policies that support PE, we understand these three characteristics as the driving model for why PE is a meaningful marker for responsibility in research and innovation.

Four WP5 cases included clarifications for how PE evolves from an input into a specific research context to one of many dynamic elements of a complex pathway towards benefits. These cases are “Engaging Civil Society Organisations in Research”, “Public Value Research Careers (PVRC)”¹⁶, “SOLCISTE” and “Institutional Repertoires and Researcher Practices”. In these cases, the main factors influencing how PE interacts in these pathways are:

- Barriers of civil society organisations in engaging in scientific projects
- Differences of career stage
- Different expectations of transdisciplinarity

¹⁶ link to narrative

- Decoupling relationship between researcher and institution

10.4.1 Engaging Civil Society Organisations in Research

The case “Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) at the Science-Science Interface” examines the interactions between CSOs and research projects on the topic of RRI. The case takes up the issue that when CSOs collaborate in RPO or publicly funded research projects, they often run into a number of difficulties. The form of PE involving CSO reflects the relationship between the research community and a specific “public”, i.e., CSOs, which is often on the boundary of conducting research. The case specifically focuses on RRI related research projects applied for, or funded by the European SwafS funding programme, with the assumption that these funders ostensibly support PE. The case aims to surpass the hurdle of eligibility and investigate the next challenge of PE – what PE begins to look like once it crosses from initiative to actual collaboration into the boundaries of dedicated research project.

The intended pathway of this case is to expect that PE will lead to including CSOs more systematically within the research and innovation system. It is hoped, that “the input of civil society in the research process can result in the production of alternative forms of knowledge which would otherwise be unlikely to be developed” (case study). Such knowledge would “serve the function of reducing inequalities, challenging economic and political elites, and that which would benefit thus far neglected populations and movements goes underfunded and under supported (Frickel et al., 2010)” (case study). Including CSOs might also “rais(e) public awareness to the scientific issue underlying the project, production of scientific knowledge and outputs, ensuring a sampling methodology, or facilitating the geographical and temporal coverage at scales that are impossible otherwise. Projects might be expected to be inclusive in terms of gender, ethnicity, educational attainment, and increase scientific literacy, while also finding ways to access people's resources (e.g., time) and create an enjoyable and engaging experience” (case study). In the long term, including CSOs more into research has the potential of changing research funding organisations’ practices to include non-traditional RPOs.

The case followed CSOs and funders in these projects and found that beyond PE for the sake of PE, there are multiple goals at play for all groups in collaborative projects and showed several important elements of the pathways to responsible research. These included:

- Interviewed CSO representatives voiced satisfaction and dissatisfaction with calls that should include CSO in research, but several were unaware that these funding opportunities exist.
- CSO were able to produce research question that were meaningful for them, but there are institutional hurdles.
- CSOs often lack resources to seek funding in terms of money, staff, know how in proposal writing. In addition, because opportunity costs for getting funding are high, already existing networks are rather used than new ones to create research collaboration.
- Work on trying to get funding and administering existing funds takes time away from CSO’s core mission. The situation is different for bigger and small CSOs. The bigger ones with more resources can cope better and get more funding. The smaller ones are disadvantaged.
- Accountability instruments, reports, articles, reporting are not aligned to the culture of CSOs and take away resources from their core mission. Cooperation in these matters

works better with private foundations. Often there is a culture of trust and flexibility in these foundations towards CSOs versus a culture of control and sticking to rules with funders.

- The goals of researchers and CSOs not necessarily align. So do their cultures.
- Involvement of CSOs in research projects is often tokenistic and gives them a narrowly defined role.
- The way funding instruments are designed moves CSOs away from their modes and topics of work (less ground level, more bureaucratic).

The case also showed a number of benefits of public engagement, mainly in the area of social and democratic benefits.

- Research gain legitimacy because it is more attuned with needs of society and engaging practitioners more directly. CSOs gain legitimacy because research informs their activities.
- Additionally, considering that CSOs represent certain forms of society, by reducing the thresholds of participation for CSOs and working to include a more diverse array of organisations, the research and innovation system will benefit from a greater variance of views and perspectives contained within projects.
- Research does better address societal needs.
- Benefit: Better democratic representation of groups in research that are usually excluded because of barriers.

Findings from interviews showed that there are institutional differences in operation which create barriers for involvement. In terms of the pathway towards benefits, there are overlaps and synergies between the needs of researchers and CSOs, such as a knowledge and legitimacy researchers can lend CSOs, however structural barriers of the research project context get in the way of the collaborative process. Some examples include resource constraints such as the amount of time required for lengthy research proposals which can exclude some CSOs from participating, especially smaller CSOs with less staff. Also, the reporting and accountability measures of research projects detract members of CSO from essential operational work. Lastly, the case highlighted the closed networks of the R&I system.

The barriers identified in the case also contribute to better clarifying the pathway towards benefits of this kind of PE. First, the obstruction of the pathway occurs at the beginning, where research questions could be better constructed with bolstering the legitimacy of the CSO in mind. Secondly, the pathway towards benefits does occur in sharing the sites and contexts of research projects amongst CSOs and researchers which results in a higher likelihood of societally relevant research topics with readied societal beneficiaries. Zooming out further, the inclusion of CSOs helps to bring in new actors and change the content and form of the R&I system from within.

10.4.2 Public Engagement and Public Value Research Careers

The case study on PVCR analyses different aspects of how the governance of research careers can adapt to realize greater public value, specifically in terms of incentives and rewards. Normatively, the case argues that research organisations should be more open to PE as a means of maintaining and enriching public values such as privacy, open science practices, safety, efficiency, equality, fairness, and legitimacy. A research system which produces more PVRC would thus serve as or contribute towards pathways towards benefits.

One of the evolutions of the promotion of PE has been the emergence of different role sets within the research profession. This has allowed the research system to take on the demands of societally

relevant work while buffering the epistemically necessary work, however the former role set is not valued by current forms of recognition in research careers. This leads to the importance of rewards and recognition incentives and their role in a potential shift towards closer alignment with public value. Taking the empirical component of this case study (D5.2) together with the theoretical, we can see that career stage is a factor in researchers' PE activities career stage. Following the argument of the PVRC case, PE can also be linked to rewards and recognition and how these incentive systems lead to the development of and training of individual researchers. However, the empirical data showed that rates of cooperation with stakeholders rise as research careers advance (D5.2). Additionally, there was consistently higher levels of engagement when comparing more advanced stage researchers (R3 and R4) with early or early mid-career researchers (R1 and R2) for all stakeholder types.

Taking up these results with the concept of PVRC, the empirical evidence suggests that career stage is a significant factor in how PE can be understood as interacting with research careers and their potential to contribute benefits in the form of public value to society. Further research would be needed to explain the reasons why early career researchers are not engaging as much as senior researchers in PE, but some hypotheses include the accumulation of experience and prestige, coupled with control over resources, among researchers in advanced career stages, which likely makes involving citizens more easily achievable for senior researchers over junior ones. These findings reinforce the importance of PE training and rewards to early career researchers who might not be participating in PE activities because of the lack thereof. Looking at the concept of PVRC in terms of pathway towards benefits, career stage should be more closely considered in designing effective PE structures, policies, and career models.

10.4.3 Public Engagement and Transdisciplinarity Funding

According to the WP5 case SOLSTICE, participation of multiple actors in research projects should lead to transformative research outcomes regarding the climate crises. The way that PE is operationalised in the SOLSTICE case is primarily through funding research projects that are led by Social Science and Humanities (SSH) on the topic of climate change. The underlying assumption of the SOLSTICE programme is that SSH disciplines are more likely to design and engage stakeholders in transdisciplinary project design. In the SOLSTICE case, the overarching goal of transdisciplinarity is to be transformative with research projects, or in other words, to fund projects that result not just in scientific knowledge and outcomes but societally relevant knowledge that is co-created with stakeholders in the project context. This is meant to increase the likelihood that the project results are taken up and used beyond the research community and ultimately contribute towards actionable solutions that improve resilience, adapt to and fight climate change.

The case study revealed that transdisciplinarity as a means of achieving PE is hard to operationalise because research programmes, and subsequently the projects which stem from them, tend to fall back on their accustomed ways of "doing research". The SOLSTICE funding program tried to nudge the researchers to behave differently towards more collaboration with citizens and stakeholders compared to traditional funding programs that might focus on scientific excellence. However, these behaviours are very hard to change. For example, interdisciplinary research often remained within the domain of social sciences. Also, the identification of impact is difficult to align with self-perception of researchers. Additionally, it is hard to change the practices of funders as well who are not familiar with SSH disciplinary role in climate change research, particularly when coordinating funding at a trans-European level. An additional challenge was the different reporting timelines and eligibility criteria for "who", meaning which stakeholders, could be considered legitimate project partners and how PE could be implemented in practice.

This case provides insight into transdisciplinarity as an influential factor of PE pathway in that transdisciplinarity is often used as a marker for it as such. The case illustrates how funding structures and reporting measures, such as eligibility criteria and impact reporting, often do not favour new ways of developing transformative research programs. However, the benefits are in the projects themselves, to the extent to which the SOLSTICE program was able to provide fertile ground for some of the projects to do research in a “new way”, engage stakeholders in research projects and provide useable knowledge to help build resiliency in communities.

10.4.4 Public Engagement, Institutional Repertoires and Researcher Practices

The case “Public Engagement Repertoires” (PER) looks at how the promotion of engagement practices of researchers through institutional support impacts individual researcher’s PE practices. Specifically, the case investigates the expectations of and opportunities for PE within institutions and stresses the importance of preferences and support for researchers in order realise the benefits of PE. The term repertoire describes the set of policy instruments an organisation employs to promote, support, and incentivize PE in their organisation. The organisations in this case are a collection of RPOs and their employees. Data was collected through the former through a document study of 120 and the later through a researcher survey with 4,108 respondents administered to researchers employed in the same 120 RPOs (RESU).

In terms of the pathway towards benefits, the PER study demonstrates that while many European researchers engage in PE in the form of communication, these PE activities do not entail deeper participation of actors outside research and innovation in research activities. The results also show that institutional policies do not necessarily correlate with the amount of PE activities but rather disciplines do. This implies that more than institutional policies, epistemological patterns, and historical trends within different disciplines, such as those within the social and medical sciences, play a significant role the PE practices of individual researchers. Additionally, results show that institutions respond to requests for PE support, but that the requests for this support come from researchers who are already motivated to do PE. In summary, the patterns of the PER case can guide reflection on the relationship between institutional policy and researcher’s actual perceptions of their own PE practices as they reported in the survey. In terms of the alignment between PE policy and practice within institutions, we see that there is a decoupling effect taking place which has implications for PE pathways towards benefits. The case would suggest that the specific pathway is defined more by disciplinary cultures and the epistemic relationship to public engagement.

10.5. Research Ethics and Integrity Pathway

The operational understanding of ethics in research and innovation and delineation of the institutionalization of ethics can be categorized in terms of ethical governance, ethical deliberation, and ethical reflection.

The ToC associated with Ethics is that consideration of issues around ethics and integrity is intrinsically imperative and of democratic and social value. The expectation is that bolstering a research and innovation system with ethical practices will generate research outputs that prioritize consideration of the ethical implications of research and innovation. Again, the case study shows that this is not so easy and that there are several hurdles along the pathway towards this benefit.

10.5.1 Ethical Engineering: Can you build morality into Artificially Intelligent Systems?

The case of “Coding ethics and values into autonomous systems” shows various attempts of considering ethics in the development of artificial intelligence (AI). How can different actors steer AI in a more responsible direction with better outcomes for society, doing less harm? The case asks, what happens to rights and values as they become subject to design and engineering? From empirical research, the case study distinguishes five design articulations, which in reality are not clear-cut but overlap.

Design articulation 1: Ethics rules. The main emphasis is on ethical analysis and its resolution in philosophical and ethical terms. The problem is primarily a normative one and should be settled before and outside the task of designing and implementing a technical or organisational problem. The problem framing is not emerging from a context of application but largely discipline-based. It remains unclear how a solution will be translated into material and technological practice. This question is not answered within this design articulation.

Design articulation 2: In this instance, the engineers take the lead. The problem space is defined as an engineering task and included in engineering practice as adding ethics as additional category to the development of AI. Although stakeholder involvement is stated as a necessity for creating ethical AI systems to recognize the variety of interests and values, machine readable “ethical ontologies” stay with the classics of virtue ethics, de-ontology and utilitarianism. The One main problem is whether the highly formalised language needed for machine readability is compatible with the complex, unstructured environments in which such systems should be implemented in, and the complexity of a real-world moral dilemma they might be confronted with., and with the nature of ethical (and legal) principle, which are much more loosely structured and defined.

Design articulation 3 is human-centric and tries to affect the standards on the behaviours of human creators, designers, and operators of AI systems. The idea is to teach ethics to engineers to enable them to include this in a design process to increase and improve engineers' awareness for ethical issues in their everyday work into large powerful companies at later stages. The question is whether industry is open for such engineers, thus also influencing design and coding, although in more in-direct ways than for articulation 2. Moreover, research and industry, particularly in the US, are fragmented, and there there is no concerted movement or organisation to take care of and coordinate such efforts. There is also the question, whether the standardizing approach is useful given the years it takes to develop and implement a standard. Finally, it is a question who should train the engineers, “ivory tower” ethicists who are not fully aware of the mundane and everyday problems of AI developments or “non-ethicists” who might lack philosophical training.

Design articulation 4 focuses on human designers, operators, and users for training and emphasizes standards and regulations. Regulation, however, is aggravated by the ubiquitous nature of data and information in ICT systems. In bottom-up regulatory initiatives, engineers are important but so are larger groups of stakeholders from various as government regulators, business corporations, technology developers and vendors, and (to some extent) civil society.

Design articulation 5 blurs the distinction between human intelligence and AI, through actual research on how to improve ethical decision making through computational support, or (more speculatively) through future mergers between humans and machines.

10.6. Sustainability Pathway

Although not an explicit RRI key, interventions to shift research and innovation practices towards sustainable social and environmental development is an important marker for responsibility in terms of research and innovation meeting societal needs. As such, WP5 has produced cases that highlight sustainability as a marker of achieving RRI-related benefits. The D5.2 Patterns Report outlines patterns in sustainability that relate to gender and innovation. In terms of pathways, sustainability relates more to capacity building within the research and stakeholder communities to achieve social and environmental sustainability outcomes. The theory of change is that RRI practices will lead to research outcomes that contribute to more sustainability, however this entails a transmission between the research community and societal users embedded within local communities. This ToC is evident in two of the WP5 cases which have already been introduced, SOLSTICE and Engaging CSOs. In these cases, the topic of ecological sustainability and climate change are the primary objectives of either the researchers, the CSOs, or both. In the SOLSTICE case, 7 funded projects under the funding program had a shared objective to enhance the transformative potential of research compared to other funding programs. In the Engaging CSOs case, the organisations seeking to collaborate in researcher projects were looking for research to help bolster their organisations potential to have an impact on society. In both cases, the assumption is that RRI can help move sustainability research outside of the ivory tower so that it has a sustainability benefit for society and the environment. In these cases, capacity building and perceptions within local communities viewing research as a resource to improve social and environmental sustainability.

10.6.1 Sustainability Outcomes of Research Projects

The Engaging CSOs case demonstrates a pathway of both opportunities and barriers for sustainability benefits. The case demonstrated that civil society organisations have different institutional limitations which make research funding feel more extractive to them compared to private foundations. This is a significant turn off that has the potential to turn many interested CSOs away. On the other hand, the case also highlighted an abundance of thematic overlaps between researchers interests and CSOs. Some of these potentially mutually interesting topics include:

- Impact of advertising on perpetuating the need on non-renewable energy sources
- Impact that advertising has on consumer behaviour about making more sustainable lifestyle choices.
- An exploration into the quantity of funds being invested by pension funds within Europe on fossil fuel related industries.
- The ecological impacts of a major land and water management infrastructure project in the Netherlands where the CSOs were based.
- More generally, research onto the potential impacts that the work of CSOs was having on the discourse surrounding environmental debates.

Thus, CSOs are quite ready and able to identify concrete and realistic research questions which could generate useful collaborative opportunities. However, the pathway revealed that differences in institutional practices between the R and I system and the institutional context of CSOs generate significant barriers. One of these barriers comes in the form of administration of and reporting on funds to do the research. For CSOs who have significant resource constraint and whose work involves juggling many different day to day operations, the reporting style of the research projects significantly detracted from their operational capabilities. Also relating to reporting and accountability cases, the SOLSTICE case demonstrated the difficulty in planning, implementing, and reporting the uncertainty

around transformative activities. As the projects were consistently asked about their impact during the various project milestones, some projects were successful in identifying certain actors to take up their findings and results, while others were reluctant to make claims about impact because they did not have promising interactions up until the time of reporting. Again, some of the aspects of scientific work tended to get in the way of research projects achieving their intended level of translation to solution-oriented knowledge, because they tended to focus on scientific knowledge.

These cases both demonstrate a need to shift these pathways more towards research serving as a means of sustainability outcomes, rather than research being a goal in itself. Both of these cases demonstrate non-research actors, namely funding organisations and members of CSOs, are interested and motivated to shift research towards sustainability outcomes.

This pathway demonstrates that there is an impetus and desire for researchers to conduct research which is more readily usable for the rest of society which improves the chances that research projects could have more direct beneficiaries and users. However, this requires increasing dialogue between potential users of knowledge and the research and innovation system, from the very outset of creating new research projects. This would help bring in more societally relevant research questions and topics, which have a better chance at translation into sustainability benefits, while simultaneously bolstering the work and functions of societal users.

11. Outlook

This D5.3 Pathways Report presented the six case studies developed in the empirical program of Work Package 5. The cases were carried out by members of the SUPER MoRRI consortium in order to better clarify the pathways which unfold when responsibility-oriented interventions occur in unique research and innovation contexts. The aim was to cover a wide range of interventions at different levels of research organisation, different RRI related keys and markers of practices, and different actor groups. Through this breadth of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods empirical work, D5.3 demonstrated some key findings about pathways of responsibility practices and policies. The specific pathways discussed in this report were citizen science, gender quality, open science, public engagement, research ethics and integrity, and sustainability. Often, these responsibilities markers overlap with each other and clear-cut distinctions between them can be difficult to make. Pathways cannot be taken for granted and involve complex intricacies between actors, institutions, individual motivations, administrative hurdles and translations between policy, research, and practice communities. The pathways illustrate progress and barriers that are specific to the cases. The main findings of these case studies can be used to inform users of the PROMISE monitoring portal how markers of responsibility should be seen in context.

Table 18 details the pathways for each of the six case studies and their related benefits, delineated by societal, economic, democratic, and scientific benefit. What constitutes a specific type of benefit over another will be addressed in the concluding report for WP5, D5.4 Analytical Synthesis Report.

Table 18: Pathways contributing to benefits of open and responsible research and innovation

Study	Pathway identified	Benefits
Civil Societies at Science-Society interface	CSOs gain legitimacy when participating in research.	Relationships between RRI community and CSOs established- Societal benefit
	Overlaps and potential synergies exist between researchers and CSOs. CSOS have resource constraints that make participation in research difficult. Larger CSOs are more advantaged to engage in research because of economies of scale; smaller CSOs risk little or no access to research cooperation. Research has accountability practices that distract CSOs from their main mission related work.	Increased inclusion and recognition of citizens competencies; Reduction of barriers to diversity (individuals and organisations) in participation - Democratic benefit
Coding of ethics and values into autonomous systems	Main effect in governance / policy level, as creation of expectations that ethical issues will be dealt with in future.	R&I system adopts and conforms to ethical standards, producing products that are more in line with

	<p>5 design articulations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethics Rules • Engineers in the driver’s seat • Educating the engineers • Educating the stakeholders • AI as transformation 	<p>people’s values and expectations – Societal benefit</p> <p>Introducing moral and ethical deliberation into the very process of designing and building an artefact/technology – Societal benefit</p> <p>Production of an advantage for the internal market, as customers will want products/solutions that are in line with fundamental values – Economic benefit</p>
<p>Public value research careers</p>	<p>Career stage is a determining factor in OS practices (from Patterns Study D5.2).</p> <p>Shifting research careers to integrate different types of responsible practices depends heavily on training and mentoring processes.</p> <p>Reform of evaluation systems to incentivize and reward contribution to public values is key.</p>	<p>Diffusion of good practices promoting change in R&I projects and organisations – Democratic benefit</p> <p>Exploitation of shared research data (OS) stimulates creativity and innovation, facilitates more efficient use of resources – Economic benefit</p> <p>Diffusion of research results stimulates social innovation and situated problem-solving – Societal and Economic benefit</p> <p>Improved transparency, integrity, and reproducibility of research – Scientific benefit</p>
<p>Transdisciplinary Research(funding)</p>	<p>Inter-and-transdisciplinary research funding has opportunities for new ways to evaluate, fund, and report (transformative) research processes.</p> <p>Transformation is a difficult concept in early stages of operationalisation. The research and innovation (funding) system requires more learning and experimentation to promote societally impact-oriented</p>	<p>Greater inclusion of stakeholders into the research process will produce stronger project outputs with higher potential to link to (transformative) societal outcomes - Social Benefit</p> <p>Closer alignment with local community members will lead to empowerment of citizens in the face</p>

	ways of organising research processes.	of climate change -Democratic Benefit?
	Barriers include traditional ways of creating, administering, and conducting research projects that fall back on ‘old’ ways of doing Communication and Dissemination.	Transformation-driven research led by SSH researchers will produce innovative research with higher impact for (transformative) change, e.g., fighting climate change. Social Benefit?
Gendered Eco-Innovation	<p>Link between gender diversity and openness towards societal needs exists through different mechanisms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Women promote different ways of doing research and innovation and are more sensitive to sustainability issues. • Women take on their roles and collaborate differently from men. • There are differential contributions to eco- innovation that are not acknowledge or rewarded. 	<p>Inclusion of women in research design & development improves quality of scientific outputs – Scientific? And Economic Benefit</p> <p>Openness of companies towards societal needs and challenges through women leadership – Societal and Economic? Benefit</p> <p>More representation of diverse perspectives – Democratic benefit</p> <p>Gender equality – Intrinsic democratic value</p>
Public Engagement: Organizational Repertoires and Researchers’ Practices	<p>A majority of researchers in European universities engage with the public, however a majority engages in “lower level” communication activities instead of “higher level” engagement activities.</p> <p>Disciplines and their epistemologies and histories play a role in researchers’ Public Engagement practices.</p> <p>Institutional support positively affects the amount and types of researchers’ public engagement activities, but there is evidence of decoupling between organisational policies and researcher behaviour.</p>	<p>Inclusion of citizens’ perspective in R&I policymaking – Democratic benefit</p> <p>Diffusion of good practices promoting change in R&I projects and organisations – Democratic benefit</p>

D5.4 will result in a synthesis of Table 18, along with D5.2 Patterns Report and the data vehicles developed in WP2. The outlook of WP5 is to conclude in D5.4 by validating the replicable data sources for these various data vehicles in order to identify potential new indicators for benefits of responsibility interventions in the research and innovation system. This upcoming work will also seek to put SUPER MoRRI results in context of experiences gained in other SwafS projects and recent literature on the themes of responsibility and openness in research and innovation.

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ANNEX I

Table 19: Case Study specific questionnaire

SUPER MoRRI case research project development protocol	
Question	Content requested by the partners
Title	Title of the case study.
Research Question.	The research question(s) of the case.
Which current state of problem is the project seeking to influence? Why exactly did you choose this case?	Description of the purpose of the case. Partners should elaborate why they wanted to work on the case and why the topic was burning and relevant for the overall framework.
Which concept and definition of RRI do you use in your case study?	The concept of RRI used for the case should be described, with reference to the conceptualisations used in the strategic plan (D1.2, p. 6-9). If the case was using key dimensions, it should be explained how they are defined and why this/those specific key(s) are/were selected.
RRI concept used in the case	Definition of RRI concept used.
RRI keys used in the case	Definition of RRI key(s) used.
4.b. 1) How are you going to operationalise the key(s) in focus?	Operationalisation of key(s).
Definition of "RRI practices"	Specification of RRI practices that are in focus of the research, how they are defined, which practices are expected to be dealt with in the case.
4.c. 1) How are you going to operationalise the practices in focus?	Operationalisation of key(s).
How will the three-part model of integration, implementation, and impact (i3) defined in the strategic plan be integrated in your case/project?	To align with the strategic plan, partners were asked to refer to the three-part model of integration, implementation, and impact (i3) in their case studies.
Integration:	From D1.2, p. 7-8: Integration of diverse actors, knowledges, capabilities, and interests, refers to the mobilisation of individuals, organisations, institutions, technology, and resources for R&I. Integration occurs at multiple levels of an organisation and with varying scope. It includes formal

SUPER MoRRI case research project development protocol	
Question	Content requested by the partners
	<p>vehicles such as strategic alliances, contracts, projects, and informal arrangements of cooperation. Integration is relatively responsible when it is plural, diverse, and inclusive.</p> <p>→ Who is involved? on what basis is the participation of diverse actors organised? what types of knowledge and technology are involved? how are citizens involved?</p>
Implementation:	<p>From D1.2, p. 7-8: “Implementation refers to collective research and innovation processes and practices. Implementation pathways are relatively responsible when based on negotiated and interdependent goals, mutual commitment to avoiding adverse social, environmental, and other effects, and shared (normative) expectations regarding users and beneficiaries.</p> <p>→ How are interactions organised? how are priorities developed and agreed upon? how are conflicts between goals, or among priorities, exposed, debated, and resolved? Are processes transparent and activities open and inclusive? how are emerging scientific controversies, technical obstacles and/or societal uncertainties treated? are multiple innovation pathways generated and developed?”</p>
Impact:	<p>Which kind of impact to you expect? Describe impacts and impact pathways.</p> <p>From D1.2, p. 7-8: “Impact therefore refers principally to transformations in processes, connections, capacities, attitudes, identities and anticipated possible futures, rather than to the outputs and outcomes of R&I they carry.”</p> <p>→ How do users of research and innovation provide feedback to knowledge producers and innovators? are potential beneficiaries included in the R&I cycle and at which point? how do networks of users transmit and modify innovations? do beneficiaries have the potential to become users? where do these translations spread and who do these networks include? how are emergent effects of innovations governed by users and beneficiaries and communicated to producers, innovators and/or regulators?</p>
Which definition of change do you use?	<p>The underlying theories of change and presuppositions should be specified in detail. For example, which kinds of change are expected to be observed should be described. (See also D1.2, chapter 2.2 Narratives of Transformation ⇔ Theories of Change, p. 9-11) “Which assumptions about how these changes might happen do you have? check on whether the</p>

SUPER MoRRI case research project development protocol	
Question	Content requested by the partners
	activities and outputs are appropriate for influencing change in the desired direction for this context. Which process/sequence of change do you anticipate leading to the desired long-term outcome” (Vogel 2012) ¹⁷
What changes do you expect to happen?	Partners should elaborate which kind of changes they would expect when observing RRI pathways in their study.
How will you consider contextual factors relevant for assessing pathways and impacts of RRI? (See also “credible contextualisation” in D1.2)	Which contexts for the impacts and pathways are expected to be relevant for the study, including social, political, systemic, environmental, organisational, and individual conditions/dimensions. (Blamey & McKenzie 2007, Mayne 2017). It should be described how they will be considered when implementing the study and which methods would be used to assess contextual factors.
How does the study contribute to the monitoring framework (WP1)?	With reference to the strategic plan, partners should reflect about the connection of the case to the monitoring framework.
How is the study connected to the implementation plan (WP2)?	Partners should think about how their case would connect to the implementation plan and data assessment in WP2.
How does the study contribute to answering the main question in WP5: to better understand the downstream pathways of RRI practices and policies?	All case study contributors should describe how the study contributes to clarifying subtle pathways from RRI practices and policies to the emergence of different kinds of impacts and benefits of RRI (WP5 objective). The goal was to focus on the question to what extent the study will study pathways downstream of RRI, thus studying changes in the implementation of RRI practices and policies. “Impact pathways describe causal pathways showing the linkages between a sequence of steps in getting from activities to impact. An intervention may have several pathways to impact”, Mayne (2017).
Which pathway of RRI are you addressing? Where should the pathway lead and why do you expect the pathway to happen?	Detailed description of the RRI pathways in focus.
Referring to the Grant Agreement, which kind of benefits (societal, economic, democratic, scientific) of RRI practices and policies do you expect in your study?	All partners are recommended to think in depth about the possible benefits and make clear the benefits they expect to assess.

¹⁷ http://www.theoryofchange.org/pdf/DFID_ToC_Review_VogelV7.pdf

SUPER MoRRI case research project development protocol	
Question	Content requested by the partners
Which kind of costs of RRI practices and policies do you expect in your study?	Cases should not only detect factors that support RRI, but also those which impede RRI activities and the realization of benefits. Those working on a case are required to reflect on possible costs of RRI practices and policies that were in focus of the case study.
How does the study produce knowledge relevant to the users?	Reflection on the relevance of the results and knowledge for possible users is crucial to, in the future, make best use of the results that are expected from the case studies.
Who implements the study? Who is involved? Which partners from the consortium are involved?	Partners should clarify in detail who is involved in which case, who takes over which tasks, etc.
How will it be implemented? Specific steps to complete the study. Flashing insight in steps, methods, resources needed...	Please describe in more detail the single steps and the methods for the implementation.
Timing and Resource	Partners should indicate a detailed time plan and the amount of resources they and possible collaborating consortium members would need for the implementation of the case study. This secures a planning of overall resources for WP5 as well as for single partners.

SUPER MoRRI

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